
Realizing Domain-Specific Mechanisms and Algorithms on the MM-AR Metamodeling Platform

Master Thesis

Master of Science in Business Informatics

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Abstract

Models are used in a wide variety of fields to represent a real world problem or system. However, a model only holds information. A simulation (or model transformation) mitigates this deficiency. Use cases like simulating a business process provide valuable insight for decision-making processes in an organization. Many existing metamodeling platforms fully integrate modeling methods according to Karagiannis and Kühn (2002), including mechanisms and algorithms for a simulation. But the MM-AR Platform by Muff and Fill (2021) is not yet one of them. During the conducted Design Science Research project of this work, the author evaluated the approaches for integrating mechanisms and algorithms of commercial and open-source metamodeling platforms. Specific components of the evaluated approaches were combined, a *generic concept for implementing mechanisms and algorithms on an MM-AR based platform* was developed, and implemented on the existing MM-AR Platform. The generic concept and the implementation into the MM-AR Platform was evaluated and its limitations identified. Further requirements for the MM-AR Platform and the implementation for mechanisms and algorithms were therefore derived. The results of this thesis show, that additional research and implementation effort in various domains is necessary, in order to close the capability gap to established metamodeling platforms and enable the integration of modeling in an everyday workflow.

Keywords

Metamodeling Platform for AR and VR, Model Transformations, Mechanisms, Algorithms, Augmented Reality, Metamodeling

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Abbreviations

ADL	ADOxx Model Language
ALL	ADOxx Library Language
API	Application Programming Interface
AR	Augmented Reality
AToMPM	A Tool for Multi-Paradigm Modeling
BPMN 2.0	Business Process Modeling Notation 2.0
CR	Constraint Requirement
DIGITS	Digitalization and Information Systems Group
DO	Design Objective
DS	Design Science
DSL	Domain-Specific Language
DSR	Design Science Research
DSRM	Design Science Research Methodology
EA	Enterprise Architecture
ER	Entity-Relationship
ERM	Entity-Relationship Model
FR	Functional Requirement
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HMD	Head-Mounted Display
IS	Information System
MM-AR	Metamodeling for augmented and virtual reality
OCL	Object Constraint Language
QR	Quality Requirement
SOAP	Simple Object Access Protocol
UML	Unified Modeling Language
UUID	Universally Unique Identifier
VizRep	Visual Representation
VR	Virtual Reality
WebGME	Web-based Generic Modeling Environment

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Almost every field of science defines and uses models and simulation differently. However they all have in common that they represent a "real-world" situation or behavior. The impact of models and the analysis of those models through transformation on decision-making is evident (Chung et al., 2000). Various research has been conducted in the field of modeling, conceptual modeling and computer simulation. However, the research rarely combined the two things, although it would promise a unique symbiosis which elevates the value of both elements. Especially on the part of metamodeling for augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR) and metamodeling platforms for AR and VR, the conducted research is not yet conclusive. The project *Metamodeling Platform for Augmented and Virtual Reality* (MM-AR Platform) by Muff and Fill (2021), tries to combine metamodeling, modeling, AR and VR, as well as simulating the models. However, the platform is still in its early stages of development, and the simulation of models is only a suggested feature and has not been implemented today. This thesis took the MM-AR Platform as a basis and extended its capabilities in the field of engaging with algorithms and mechanisms of modeling methods on the platform.

In this chapter, the current state of research, challenges, and the MM-AR Platform are analyzed, and based on this analysis, the research questions are derived. At the end, the overall structure of this thesis is described in detail.

1.1 Problem Statement

In the domain of computer science, Jones (2018) remarks that the implementation of behavior by using (physical and/or computer) systems is the main goal of modeling. The modeler models the specification of the system and the system behavior, and must change the model (specification) if the system or system behavior observed isn't the intended system/behavior. In other words, the model of the solution specification must satisfy correctness constraints to accurately grasp the problem specification.

This view on modeling is quite different from the natural sciences point of view. The natural sciences build hypotheses, which are tested later to see if they hold up. The discovered properties of the real world are formulated and modeled.

As we discover within all the different definitions, a model is always *a representation or description of something in the real world*. Within this thesis, the author limits the term model to

the definition of Jones for a model in computer science or data processing (Jones, 2018) and puts the specific properties of a model within the natural sciences out of scope.

Since we focus on the engineering view of modeling, we have to discuss conceptual modeling in more detail. The goal of a conceptual model is to describe an aspect of our physical or social surroundings without constraining the solution space in the technology or strategy domain (Mylopoulos, 1992; Roussopoulos and Karagiannis, 2009). The applications of conceptual modeling range from modeling and representing business and software development processes, requirements, and organizations to artificial intelligence. Its roots can be traced back to the mid-1970's when its value was recognized in the design of database systems. Chen's Entity-Relationship model is these days an established standard for designing database systems and is a prime example of conceptual models (Chen, 1976; Roussopoulos and Karagiannis, 2009).

Conceptual modeling plays a big part in understanding real-world (business) problems and transforming those problems into abstract and more formal representation. This is especially useful for developing software applications since a shared understanding is key for all stakeholders involved in the system development processes (Roussopoulos and Karagiannis, 2009).

In the past decades, modeling and computer simulations have increased their importance and capabilities on a daily basis in academia and industry (Pidd, 2008). Advancements in computational power and software capabilities allowed a broader application of modeling and simulation software. Modeling and simulation are no longer limited to experts but can be achieved by novices and non-specialists. However, this doesn't imply that modeling itself gets easier (Pidd, 1996). The goal is to model without consciously modeling but rather integrate modeling into everyday work, as Muff and Fill (2021) describe.

In the context of enterprise architecture, enterprise modeling and simulation are tempting since they provide a path for developing and exploring different structures, processes, and configurations of companies or systems without changing real-world components (Barton, 1998; Barjis, 2011). While a model can hold and represent information, the simulation brings the model to life. Additionally, the simulation, or the results respectively, allow for a more in-depth analysis of the system and its interaction with the environment (Barjis, 2011). More generally, computer simulation allows for developing and testing different theories (Nowak et al., 2013).

A simulation in a business context allows for obtaining costs, performance prediction, and validation of processes and allows the analysis of complex what-if scenarios where simple linear decisions no longer apply. That additional information obtained by simulations enables better decision-making in almost any resource-allocating context (Bahrami et al., 1998).

In a more general manner, Shannon (1998) defines simulation as "*the process of designing a model of a real system and conducting experiments with this model for the purpose of understanding the behavior of the system and/or evaluating various strategies for the operation of the system*" (Shannon, 1998, p. 7).

The universe of discourse we want to model, in a software and systems environment, gets more complex and harder to understand (Kindler, 2010). Even the advancements in usability within modeling software can't mitigate the permanently increasing complexity of precise modeling (Pidd, 1996). Over the years, huge advancements in computer simulation have been achieved. This is partially due to the increasing computational power of the available hardware, which today provides

more bang for the buck than ever before, and secondly, because of new software paradigms and technologies. For example, the discipline of artificial intelligence regularly relies upon neural net simulations. So, the huge leaps forward in recent years, especially over the last few months, wouldn't have been possible without proper simulation algorithms (Rutan, 1991).

We have seen that a model and its simulation algorithm(s) are closely related and interdependent (Sismondo, 1999). Sismondo (1999) defined the relation between models and simulations as "*endpoints on a continuum*" (Sismondo, 1999, p. 247). The close interdependency emphasizes the need for applications that combine the modeling and the simulation capabilities. There are a vast number of such applications available, both commercial and open-source. However, they often provide a very limited set of modeling methods to the user and most often prohibit them from adding additional modeling methods to the application. This limits the practical capabilities of a modeling application enormously, even though the application would, in theory, be capable of much more. One project that wants to tackle this aspect, among others, is the MM-AR Platform proposed by Muff and Fill (2021).

The MM-AR Platform is still in its early stage of development and is continuously developing further. The platform provides the capability, that the user can use the platform for defining and using his own domain-specific modeling method. Other metamodeling platforms like ADOxx, MetaEdit+, WebGME, or AToMPM allow the user to define his own meta-model as well (Fill and Karagiannis, 2013; Kelly et al., 1996; Vanderbilt University, 2017; AToMPM, 2023-07-22:1100 CEST), the key-difference of the MM-AR Platform is the possibility to use the models in AR and VR. As Muff and Fill (2021) recognized, there exist multiple domain-specific projects that try to use AR and VR in conceptual modeling. But apparently, there doesn't exist a generic, domain-detached approach for incorporating AR and VR on a (meta)-meta- and instance-level.

The traditional 2-dimensional platform ADOxx incorporates the entire concept of modeling methods by Karagiannis and Kühn (2002). This means the modeling technique, with the modeling language and the modeling procedure, as well as the mechanisms and algorithms. Currently, the MM-AR Platform lacks the capability of incorporating mechanisms and algorithms and thus also lacks the capability of simulating or transforming models. At the moment, there exists only one modeling method, the Petri Net, which incorporates an algorithm. However, this approach is hard-coded to the client side of the application and not integrated into the meta-model.

This thesis shall close the capability gap of the MM-AR Platform by evaluating the best-suited approach for implementing domain-specific and user-defined mechanisms and algorithms, and later developing a prototype that incorporates this approach in the current version of the MM-AR Platform.

In order to achieve the set goal, the current state of the prototype and research of the MM-AR Platform proposed by Muff and Fill (2021) was taken as a starting point for this thesis. Since the added capability of incorporating algorithms shall be state-of-the-art, an in-depth analysis of the existing approaches of competing metamodeling platforms is crucial. For the analysis and the later implementation of the approach, a Design Science Research (DSR) project was carried out.

1.2 Research Questions

Based on the problem statement of the previous section, the research questions were derived within the next few paragraphs.

Over the last few decades, huge software capability and performance advancements have been made. Since the MM-AR Platform is still in the development phase of its life cycle, the platform shall use modern technologies. The approach taken for a MM-AR based platform shall be state-of-the-art and easy to use. The best-suited approach for incorporating mechanisms and algorithms into a MM-AR based platform is unknown. Therefore, the author will analyze different commercial and open-source tools. Not every (meta-)modeling platform provides simulation capabilities, and from those that provide such features, not every platform uses modern technologies and designs. Thus, the author limits his analysis. The tools that are chosen for the analysis are introduced in Chapter 5.3. Therefore, the following research question will be answered:

Research Question 1 (RQ1): How are domain-specific mechanisms and algorithms implemented in commercial and open-source tools?

The previously gathered and analyzed approaches will be evaluated. The evaluation is based on a standardized rating matrix. The best-rated approach will be chosen to be pursued for the generic MM-AR concept as well. However, the author doesn't limit himself by rejecting the possibility of combining or adapting approaches accordingly. The chosen route will define specific requirements for the approach, the user, and the platform itself. The requirements supplement the current capabilities, which are going to be evaluated by a gap analysis. Those approach- and platform-specific requirements have to be identified and mapped onto the architecture requirements of an MM-AR based platform. Following this, a response to the second research question will be given:

Research Question 2 (RQ2): What approach is best suited for a MM-AR based platform, and what are the requirements?

As seen in the second step, the author will evaluate and choose one approach to incorporating mechanisms and algorithms. The previously identified requirements have to be converted into a generic concept that could be applied and implemented on any platform that is based on the MM-AR meta-model. Following this reasoning, the third research question will be answered:

Research Question 3 (RQ3): How can mechanisms and algorithms be generically implemented on an MM-AR based platform?

Since the result of this master thesis shall be a finished prototypical implementation of the generic approach, the previously developed universal concept has to be translated into concrete, platform, and technology-specific code. Therefore, the fourth and final research question will be answered:

Research Question 4 (RQ4): What changes to the existing MM-AR Platform are necessary to implement mechanisms and algorithms according to the generic concept?

1.3 Structure

In the following Chapter 2, the methodologies used are described. For this thesis, a DSR approach was chosen. The research method was extended in certain phases to better suit the specific needs of this work.

The Chapter 3 introduces all relevant theoretical foundations that are necessary to understand this work. In Section 3.1, the author explains what a system and a model itself really is. In Section 3.2, conceptual modeling is defined. Furthermore, the evolution of conceptual modeling over time is introduced. In Section 3.3, the central concept of this thesis, model transformation and simulation, is introduced. A special emphasis is put on the different categories of simulations. Afterwards, in Section 3.4, modeling methods, their individual components and their interdependence is explained. Section 3.5 introduces the central concept of meta-meta-, meta- and modeling as well as the concept of the modeling hierarchy. Lastly in Section 3.6, the MM-AR Platform of the University of Fribourg with its meta-meta model, technology and functionality is explained.

In Chapter 4, the DSR project of this thesis is introduced. In Section 4.1, the artifact of the DSR project is defined in detail. Section 4.2 defines the design objectives of the DSR project. In Section 4.3, the design objectives are transformed into requirements for the generic concept as well as the concrete implementation. In this section, also the first part of the research question RQ2 will be answered.

In Chapter 5, the generic concept is developed, based on the evaluation of other metamodeling platforms. In Section 5.1, the rating matrix for evaluating metamodeling platforms is created. Then in Section 5.2, four different existing metamodeling platforms, namely ADOxx, MetaEdit+, WebGME and AToMPM, are evaluated based on the previously developed rating matrix. Using the explanation and evaluation, the research question RQ1 is answered. Section 5.3 closes the chapter by introducing the developed *generic concept for implementing mechanisms and algorithms into a MM-AR based platform*. By developing the generic concept, the second part of the research question RQ2 and the research question RQ3 will be answered.

In Chapter 6, the previously developed *generic concept for implementing mechanisms and algorithms* is implemented into the existing MM-AR Platform. The chapter describes how the concept was implemented into the existing MM-AR Platform and therefore answers the research question RQ4. In Section 6.2, the generic concept, as well as the concrete implementation, is evaluated in detail. For this purpose, the rating matrix from Chapter 5 is reused.

Finally, in Chapter 7 the results of this thesis are discussed. Furthermore, future research topics and projects are suggested.

Chapter 2

Methodology

The following chapter describes the applied methodologies and maps the research questions, which were defined in Section 1.2, directly on the different methods and phases. In general, the Design Science Research Methodology (DSRM) approach, according to Peffers et al. (2007), was followed. This methodology was chosen because it offers a mental model for representing and assessing DSR in the domain of Information Systems (IS). However, due to special requirements, in some phases of the DSR project, the methodology was extended with additional aspects. The added aspects are introduced in the explanation of the respective phases of the DSR methodology. In addition, the different activities of the DSR project are mapped with the overall structure of this thesis.

The DSRM for IS was developed by Peffers et al. (2007) and is based on previous research in the field of Design Science (DS) and engineering. Peffers et al. recognized that within the IS research community, DSR wasn't widely used, although the engineering disciplines accept the DSR as a valuable and applicable research technique. Additionally, they remarked that some of the previous research, especially the engineering studies, suggested a commonly accepted framework for DS. In contrast to the rare use of DSR in the IS research community, multiple DS approaches have been developed over the last decades (e.g., the seven guidelines for DS in IS research by Hevner et al. (2004)). Out of those different approaches, Peffers et al. analyzed and compared a subset (Peffers et al., 2007). In their analysis of the different DS approaches, they searched for similar concepts to gain a common understanding of DSR in IS that is based on consensus.

While the literature, that Peffers et al. analyzed doesn't match one-to-one on the respective specified steps and elements, they were able to identify common core elements and process steps. All of the approaches feature some sort of problem identification, the definition of the objective, development, and evaluation. These core elements are extended in some literature by additional steps. Following the results of their analysis, Peffers et al. derived the six activities of the DSRM, which are described in the following paragraphs, after first examining the seven guidelines for DSR in IS by Hevner et al. (2004).

DSR uses the creation and application of an artifact to gain knowledge and understanding about a specific problem. The core focus is solving problems and creating new solutions for IS in terms of technology, processes, and products. Hevner et al. (2004) took this fundamental principle and developed seven guidelines for design science (DS) in IS research. The first of those seven guidelines states that an artifact that treats a significant (organizational) problem is the product

of DSR. The definition of such an artifact in DSR isn't precisely defined, and there exist multiple different definitions. Hevner et al. provide a pretty broad definition, which includes instantiations, models, constructs, and methods for developing and using IS. However, the definitions of Hevner et al. specifically exclude people or organizational elements as well as the change process of an artifact. Furthermore, Hevner et al. don't specify how that artifact shall be created and therefore leave liberty to the researcher (Hevner et al., 2004). The artifact for this thesis is the *generic concept for implementing mechanisms and algorithms on an MM-AR-based platform*.

The second guideline specifies that the artifact must address an unsolved and significant problem. As introduced in Section 1.1, the simulation brings any model to life. Only with simulation can an organization get insights and a deeper understanding of its modeled business problem. Therefore, the significance of this artifact is proven.

The researcher shall demonstrate the quality, utility, and efficacy through evaluation methods like simulations, functional or structural testing, and architecture analysis, as defined in the third guideline by Hevner et al. (2004). However, as already in the first guideline, the specific evaluation method is not clearly indicated, since it must be adapted to the concrete DSR project. In this thesis, the attributes of the artifact shall be demonstrated by evaluating the proof-of-concept prototype in Section 6.2.

The fourth guideline calls for demonstratable and distinct contributions to the research domain of the artifact. The contribution could be the improvement or extension of already existing artifacts, creative development, and application of evaluation methods, or, most often in a DSR project, a new artifact altogether (Hevner et al., 2004). Since this thesis aims to extend the existing artifact, the MM-AR meta-meta model and existing MM-AR Platform, the contribution is clear. (Hevner et al., 2004).

The design and development of an artifact isn't a straightforward process but rather a search to find the solution to a specified (business) problem (Hevner et al., 2004; Peffers et al., 2007). This problem-solving process requires creative and innovative abstraction and representation of problem-specific measures, acts, and conclusions. This sixth guideline specifies an iterative process between generating design alternatives and testing those developed designs (Hevner et al., 2004).

In the last step, the DSR project results will be introduced to the proper audience (Hevner et al., 2004; Peffers et al., 2007). This thesis serves directly as the means of communication for the DSR artifact to the appropriate technology- and management-oriented stakeholders.

Figure 2.1 summarizes the DSRM with its six steps by Peffers et al. (2007). In general, a DSR project could be started during any of the first four activities. The initiation for the DSR project in this thesis emerged from improving, respectively extending, an existing artifact, so the process starts as an *Objective-Centered Initiation* at the second activity in the DSRM process. As Peffers et al. mentioned, the six activities are not always followed in consecutive order. The researcher can, based on his initiation activity, start at any step (Peffers et al., 2007, p. 56). However, all of the activities must be done, so an outward approach starting from activity two is followed. The specifics of the six activities are now described in detail.

Figure 2.1: DSR Process Model with Objective-Centered-Initiation (Peffer et al., 2007, p. 54) Adapted from "A Design Science Research Methodology for Information Systems Research", by Peffer et al. (2007), *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 24(3), p. 54.

1. Problem identification and motivation: The first activity forces the researcher to define the research problem. Additionally, the concrete value of a solution has to be justified. The defined problem will form the basis of the development of the artifact (Peffer et al., 2007). If the chosen problem disposes of a high degree of complexity, Peffer et al. suggest to atomize the problem.

For this thesis, the concrete research problem was stated in Section 1.1, together with the importance and motivation of the artifact. Additional knowledge was gained by a literature analysis, which allowed the author to outline the benefits of simulation and model transformation in (conceptual) modeling in detail (see Section 3.3). Furthermore, the specified benefits of a generic concept for integrating mechanisms and algorithms in a MM-AR-based platform (see Chapter 5.3) further contribute to the motivation of the author, as well as the appropriate audience of the artifact.

As mentioned above, an extensive literature analysis was conducted. The relevant literature for modeling, conceptual modeling, simulation, model transformation, and the MM-AR platform was searched on multiple databases as well as search engines. Specifically the databases *IEEE Xplore* as well as the *ACM Digital Library*. The *IEEE Xplore* digital library is a database of publications by the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) and its partners. The *ACM Digital Library* is a database that collects and curates all publications of the Association for Computing Machinery (ACM) as well as selected publishers.

Many publications on both databases have been found by the search engine *elicit.org*, which is an AI-powered search assistant for scientific research. It's based on the large-language model GPT 3 and will show relevant research papers as an answer to a question.

Besides the direct database search as well as the use of the search assistant, a backward and forward search was conducted, based on the identified key literature. All the techniques combined allowed for an in-depth understanding of the research domain.

In order to gain an overview as comprehensive as possible for this thesis, the rank of a scientific journal in which the research has been published wasn't considered by purpose. However, since most of the papers used as a basis in this thesis were available through the mentioned databases, an initial curation by the IEEE or ACM has been conducted.

2. Define the objectives for a solution: In the second activity, the desired outcomes are determined based on the defining problem details and available options. The researcher shall focus on both quantifiable improvements and unique capabilities that address previously unsolved issues. The researcher must have knowledge about the technical feasibility of his artifact to define reasonable objectives. The concrete objective can be either a quantifiable attribute (e.g., performance) or a qualitative description of the expected behavior within the problem's domain (Peffer et al., 2007).

In this thesis, the definition of the objectives of the artifacts solution was the first step within the conducted DSR project. Peffer et al. provided assistance by asking the following question: "What would a better artifact accomplish?" (Peffer et al., 2007, p. 54).

This thesis emerged from a semester project of the masters-course "Emerging Technologies in Digitalization" at the University of Fribourg. During that course, the author worked on the implementation of Petri Nets with the corresponding meta-model and the token game algorithm on the existing MM-AR Platform. The objective of the respective artifact, an implementation of a domain-specific algorithm for Petri Nets, has been achieved during that course. However, the implementation was hard-coded on the client side of the MM-AR Platform, and future implementations of other domain-specific algorithms required extensive modification to the existing approach. Therefore, the need for another (better) artifact, a more generic implementation of domain-specific mechanisms and algorithms, was recognized.

Following that logic, the second activity, the definition of the objectives of the *better* artifact in this thesis, marks the starting point of the DSR project as it's an Objective-Centered Initiation. The details of the objectives for the artifact's solution are defined in detail in Chapter 4.

3. Design and development: The third activity treats the actual creation of the artifact. This step involves inferring the future functionality and architecture of the artifact. Besides the conceptual work, also the concrete artifact is created during this activity. The researcher must bring together theory and practice to design and develop a useful and innovative artifact (Peffer et al., 2007).

For this thesis, the design and development activity involves an evaluation of existing approaches of competing commercial and open-source metamodeling platforms. The evaluation is supported by a specialized rating method based on the *ISO/IEC 25010:2011 - Systems and software engineering — Systems and software Quality Requirements and Evaluation (SQuaRE) — System and software quality models*. Estdale and Georgiadou (2018) have shown that the reworked ISO/IEC 25010:2011 provides substantially more value than its predecessor ISO 9126. They further provide a guideline on how to apply the standard since it still needs some additional interpretation and can't be applied directly (Estdale and Georgiadou, 2018). The evaluation was performed along those specified guidelines with an additional emphasis on the quality and usability aspects of implementing domain-specific mechanisms and algorithms. However, the performance side was still recognized and was considered within the software quality requirements of the standard. The detailed evaluation criteria and the rating matrix are specified in Section 5.1.

After the evaluation of the different approaches for implementing mechanisms and algorithms, a generic approach for MM-AR-based platforms will be developed. Important to note is that the generic concept will be developed on the basis of the meta-meta model by Muff and Fill (2021).

4. Demonstration: The fourth activity wraps around showcasing the artifact’s ability to address and solve the specified problem through various approaches like experiments, simulations, case studies, proofs, etc. In order to conduct such a demonstration, the researcher must possess a thorough knowledge of the artifact’s use cases (Peffer et al., 2007).

In this thesis, the demonstration of the artifact is the concrete implementation into the existing MM-AR Platform of the University of Fribourg. This proof-of-concept showcases that the generic concept for implementing domain-specific mechanisms and algorithms on an MM-AR-based platform works as intended and enables the meta-modeler to implement such mechanisms and algorithms.

For this activity, the proof-of-concept prototype will be developed along the iterative process of creating modeling methods by Karagiannis and Kühn (2002). Although the process is initially developed for creating modeling methods, the same procedures can be applied to agile software development. A working prototype can be achieved at the end of the last iteration following the five phases: Create, Design, Formalize, Develop, Deploy/Validate. While the development of requirements falls more into the Create and Design phases, the adaptation and concrete implementation can be assigned to the Formalize and Develop phases (Karagiannis and Kühn, 2002). The testing of the implemented approach is assigned to the last phase, Deploy/Validate, during which the author will conduct these tests.

In combination, the author will apply the agile software development manifesto and principles summarized by Misra et al. (2012). Regular software delivery is crucial for ensuring user tests and future refinements in later iterations.

A detailed description of the platform-specific requirements, the thought process, and conducted work can be found in Section 6.1. Additionally, the author will provide the source code of the concrete implementation for reference as well as reviews. The source-code is available in appendix B.

5. Evaluation: In the fifth activity, the researcher assesses the artifact’s usefulness in resolving the addressed problem and how well it performs while doing that. The results include comparisons between the artifact’s actual performance observed during demonstrations and the targeted objectives from activity two. After analyzing these observations, researchers have the option to refine the artifact by going back to activity three before sharing their discoveries or proceeding directly to activity six (Peffer et al., 2007).

In the context of this work, the evaluation will be conducted on the basis of the set objectives in Chapter 4 and the observed performance of the tests in Chapter 6. In addition, the results of the tests will be compared to the evaluations of the competing metamodeling platforms in order to determine if the generic approach marks an improvement to the existing methods. In this evaluation, the rating matrix, developed and used in Section 5.2, is reused. The evaluation is conducted in Section 6.2 of this thesis.

6. Communication: The sixth and final activity regards the *distribution* of the artifact. The researcher shall present the problem's significance, the artifact's benefits and innovativeness, the robustness of its design, and its effectiveness. In an academic context, researchers could use this procedure for structuring their paper about the researched artifact (Peppers et al., 2007). Since this thesis followed the DSRM, the communication is considered within the entire thesis. The distribution of the thesis and communication of the results to the relevant stakeholders is considered to be achieved.

Chapter 3

Theoretical Foundations

The following chapter introduces relevant theoretical foundations, which are necessary to understand this work. First, conceptual modeling in general and then model transformations (simulations) and domain-specific algorithms, respectively, are introduced. Afterward, we dive deeper into modeling methods and their dependencies and impact on a meta- and meta-metamodeling level. This is especially important to understand the MM-AR Platform’s meta-meta model, which is introduced later in this chapter. In addition, we introduce mechanisms and algorithms as a central part of any modeling method and describe what effect this has on the DSR artifact. As mentioned, the MM-AR Platform with its technology stack, underlying meta-meta model, as well as its current capabilities is introduced, which subsequently closes this chapter.

3.1 Systems and Modeling in General

In order to understand what the goal of a model or conceptual model is, we first must introduce the definition of a system and a general model. In essence, a *system* can be described as a collection of interconnected and interdependent components that work together to form a unified and integrated whole. Systems exhibit several defining characteristics, including a clear structure composed of elements and their arrangement, observable behavior, and interconnectedness where different parts of the system feature functional and structural relationships with one another (Kern, 2016).

A *model* is an abstract representation of a system. Within a model, we can distinguish three different characteristics. As already mentioned, a model *represents* the system of interest. The *represented* system can, but not must, already exist (Kern, 2016).

Furthermore, a model is an *abstraction* of the real system since it ignores the irrelevant details and emphasizes the most important aspects. The *abstraction* is typically achieved through generalization, classification, or reduction. During abstraction, significant properties are emphasized, while less relevant ones are excluded. The determination of whether a property is considered important or unimportant relies on pragmatic considerations and varies based on the particular context or focus (Kern, 2016).

Lastly, every model is *pragmatic* in regard to its domain and purpose. The *pragmatics* of a model are determined by the purpose and context of a model. The context defines itself according to the audience (Kern, 2016).

Modeling is a significant approach employed to manage the inherent complexity of real-world systems. Through models, complex systems can be effectively demonstrated and visually represented. Notably, models enhance our comprehension of intricate systems and facilitate the discovery of fresh insights and knowledge (Kern, 2016).

3.2 Conceptual Modeling

In this section, the author introduces the foundations of *conceptual modeling*. The author explores different definitions and describes how conceptual modeling is applied. Furthermore, the author discussed how conceptual modeling evolved over time.

3.2.1 Foundations

Although there doesn't exist one precise definition for conceptual models, Roussopoulos and Karagiannis (2009) define them as follows: Models that formally describe an aspect of the physical and social world, technology and strategy independent, are called conceptual models and are created through conceptual modeling. In other words, an abstract representation of a real-world aspect (Robinson, 2013). However, a model excludes all irrelevant information about an artifact and only contains the important data (Jeusfeld et al., 2009). It's obvious that the definition of a model and conceptual model substantially overlap and cannot be clearly distinguished as of yet.

Robinson et al. (2015) provide four different definitions of a conceptual model. While Arbez and Birta think that a conceptual model "*is a concise and precise consolidation of all goal-relevant structural and behavioral features (...) in a predefined format.*" (Robinson et al., 2015, p. 2814), Robinson defines a conceptual model as something that describes the "*objectives, inputs, outputs, content, assumptions and simplifications (...)*" (Robinson et al., 2015, p. 2816). Tolk limits a conceptual model to the "*Result of the processes leading from the task to the specification of the conceptualization of the ontological structure of the problem domain, comprising assumptions and constraints on all relevant modeling decisions.*" (Robinson et al., 2015, p. 2823). Yet another definition provides Wagner. He further recognizes that there exists a fundamental difference in the interpretation of conceptual modeling in IS & software engineering, and Modeling & Simulation (Robinson et al., 2015, p. 2822). While he defines conceptual modeling in Modeling & Simulation as "*A solution independent description of a real world problem domain, from which a platform-independent simulation design model can be derived for a given set of research questions.*" (Robinson et al., 2015, p. 2823), within the domain of IS & Software Engineering, Wagner recognizes the mutual agreement on the definition "*that a conceptual model is the result of modeling a real world problem domain independently of the solution design (...)*" (Robinson et al., 2015, p. 2822). For this work, we limit our understanding to the definition by Roussopoulos and Karagiannis (2009) and the IS & Software Engineering definition by Wagner in Robinson et al. (2015). However, the definition of a conceptual model in Modeling & Simulation will be picked up again for the sake of completeness while introducing simulations.

The goal of conceptual modeling is to understand and communicate the aspects of a system or problem (Mylopoulos, 1992). It can either be an existing aspect or only a proposed aspect (Robinson, 2013). Sismondo (1999) states that a model tries to enrich an existing theory by connecting theories to data and thus can fill in missing space in the specification of a theory.

Conceptual modeling is widely used in the field of IS design, knowledge representation, and organizational contexts. Within the organizational environment, we can represent business and software development processes, requirements for any software application or system, or any other real-world component (Roussopoulos and Karagiannis, 2009). In order to call a model a conceptual model, the model has to comply with a formal notation defined within a conceptual schema. The schemata captures the elements that the affected community agrees on and assigns those elements a graphical representation and semantics. In addition, the schema explicitly describes the syntax of the conceptual model (Jeusfeld et al., 2009).

The formalization is also one of the key advantages compared to natural language descriptions. The adherence to a given set of elements with precise semantics and a clear syntax allows the unambiguous description and communication of any real-world aspect. However, the conceptual models are still targeted towards humans. This means that any conceptual model must be readable for humans as well as machines (Mylopoulos, 1992).

So conceptual modeling targets the interface between providing formal foundations to model systems while humans can still understand a model without it being too complex, but a machine can process it automatically due to its preciseness (Jeusfeld et al., 2009). The readability for machines will be of great importance when conceptual models are combined with the simulation capabilities of modeling tools and machines.

In this context, Robinson explicitly distinguishes between the conceptual model and the computer model. The computer model is a platform-specific usage of a conceptual model. In other words, the conceptual model, with all its syntax and semantics, is platform- and language-independent, while the computer model is a specific representation on a platform and in a specific programming language, respectively (Robinson, 2013). However, these models are not considered as substitutes but rather supplement one another. A computer model is always based on a conceptual model. The conceptual model, on the other hand, is persistent and can be enriched by the findings of the computer model. There's a bilateral relation between those two types of models (Robinson, 2013).

Since we introduced the interdependencies between the conceptual and computer model, we can now extend our understanding to the concept of *usage* world, *development* world, *system* world, and *subject* world of Mylopoulos (1992), which is shown in Figure 3.1. The *subject* world represents the real world, the *system* world represents the IS on multiple layers of detail, and the *usage* world represents the environment within which the IS is planned to work. The *usage* world can consist, for example, of users, activities, or projects. Lastly, the *development* world represents the processes of developing and maintaining the *system* world. It consists of methods, design decisions, and schedules (Mylopoulos, 1992).

Mylopoulos thinks of conceptual modeling in IS as an interdependent system of worlds where the *usage* world requires data about the *subject* world, uses the *system* world, and contracts the *development* world. The *development* world builds the *system* world, and the *system* world preserves data about the *subject* world (Mylopoulos, 1992).

Every conceptual model must have an objective. The objective of a conceptual model describes the *why* of a model. What and why we want to represent with a model. It aims our perspective to the problem and solution space of an aspect. Without an objective, we can't develop a meaningful conceptual model since the required abstraction and simplifications from the real world are unknown (Robinson, 2013).

The objective is supplemented by the input and output of a model. If we think about the

Figure 3.1: Interdependency of the different worlds in a conceptual model (Mylopoulos, 1992, p. 4) Adapted from "Conceptual Modelling and Telos", by Mylopoulos (1992), *Conceptual modelling, databases, and CASE: An integrated view of information systems development*, 1992, p. 49 - 68.

available input and the required output before messing with the content of a model, we are able to develop more precise and better-suited schemata as well as models (Robinson, 2013).

3.2.2 Conceptual Modeling Through Time

The roots of conceptual modeling date back to the early 1970s, when it was first used for an abstraction of software development (Roussopoulos and Karagiannis, 2009). Back then, it was, among other things, used as a synonym for semantic data modeling (Mylopoulos, 1992). The community around conceptual modeling concentrated in the early days around the modeling of data structures. For example, the suggested division of logical data and physical organization by Codd provided the basis for conceptual modeling (Codd, 1979; Roussopoulos and Karagiannis, 2009). Mylopoulos remarks that semantic data modeling is closer to the implementation than conceptual modeling since it uses simpler notations and is overall more constrained (Mylopoulos, 1992). Probably the most famous modeling method from this time is the *Entity-Relationship* Model (ERM) by Chen (1976).

In 1980, the term conceptual modeling got a much broader meaning. Since then, it has not only included semantic data modeling but also artificial intelligence, programming languages, and database management. That wide understanding of conceptual modeling allowed further developments of sub-disciplines, like requirements engineering, which again broadened the application of conceptual modeling and models over the years (Roussopoulos and Karagiannis, 2009).

The 1990s again marked a significant leap forward in the domain of conceptual modeling. The concepts of object-oriented programming, which were mainly developed in the 1980s, brought different object-oriented analysis techniques with them. Those different concepts led to the development

of the *Unified Modeling Language* (UML) in 1994 by Booch and Rumbaugh. UML is nowadays one of the most important and widely used modeling method. UML is a de facto standard within the software development community (Roussopoulos and Karagiannis, 2009).

3.3 Model Transformations

A model simulation, a computer simulation of a model, is in a theoretical sense, a model transformation since the information contained within a model is transformed and processed. Bézivin et al. (2006) call those transformation an *executable description*. In this section, the author introduces the model transformation as a concept and then more in-depth computer simulations. In order to understand what effects a computer simulation of a model can have, we first have to understand what a simulation, at its core, really is, and secondly, what kinds of simulations there exist.

3.3.1 Properties of Model Transformations

Model transformations are widely used in software development through the use of model engineering. In this domain, models are used to face the complexity of the software and its domain. Furthermore, those models are used to automatically generate code, prototypes, or other representations of the model(-data) (Sendall and Kozaczynski, 2003).

Fundamentally, a model transformation transforms the source model into a target model according to some transformation specification. The source and target model, respectively, are based on their respective meta-model. While the models don't share a common meta-model, the respective meta-models must conform to a shared meta-meta model (Bézivin et al., 2006).

Bézivin et al. (2006) state that one possible interpretation of a model transformation is the concept of the operation. The model transformation is an operation that is implemented through a programming language (e.g., JavaScript, Python, etc.) and produces the target model based on the input of the source model (Bézivin et al., 2006).

Sendall and Kozaczynski (2003) found that the input and output of a model transformation might be multiple models. Therefore, multiple source models might exist, and multiple target models might be produced (Sendall and Kozaczynski, 2003).

Model transformation can be categorized into three groups. First, the *direct model transformation* which uses the modeling toolkit's representation of the model data for the manipulation via APIs. Normally, those API operations are implemented in a widely used programming language (e.g., Python, JavaScript) since developers are more used to implementing algorithms with those languages. An example of such a metamodeling platform is WebGME or AToMPM, as we will learn in Section 5.2.3 and Section 5.2.4, respectively. Second is the *intermediate representation*, which outsources the actual transformation to an external application. The model data is shared through a standardized data format like XML or JSON. An example of an application using that approach, among others, is the Enterprise Architect by Sparx Systems. The third category is the *transformation language support*. A metamodeling platform that uses that approach enables the model transformation through a (proprietary) language with the necessary constructs and operations. An example of such a platform is ADOxx with its proprietary language *AdoScript* (Sendall and Kozaczynski, 2003).

Besides the approaches described by Sendall and Kozaczynski for transforming models into other models, Tratt (2005) found that the need for model transformation for data exchange between modeling applications is imminent. Often, (meta-)modeling platforms provide the possibility to export and import models. However, they mostly use proprietary and non-standard data formats, and the functionality is only intended to exchange models between multiple users of the same (meta-)modeling platform. The export of the model through a standardized data format is rarely enabled. Therefore, the need for model transformation from proprietary data formats or representation towards standardized data formats like XML or JSON is obvious. Tratt uses a very literal interpretation of model transformation. This view on model transformation is closely related to the *intermediate representation*, which is described by Sendall and Kozaczynski (2003) (Tratt, 2005).

3.3.2 Properties of Computer Simulations

Pidd (1994) identifies three possibilities for how we can support decision-making or verify an idea. First, we could apply the changes to a system directly in the real world and observe the consequences. Second, we could develop a complicated mathematical model which treats the system. Third, we could simulate the system with a computer-based model and simulation. A simulation allows users to deepen their understanding of a system and its relations to its environment (Pidd, 1994).

Computer simulations sit at the interface between theory and experiment. However, models and simulations are not a uniform category. Sismondo (1999) recognizes that theories can be true or false, but models and simulations are more or less useful instead of more or less true. Simulations bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and the concrete application to real-world phenomena (Sismondo, 1999). Desel (2000) states that simulation is often used for the validation of models in regard to correctness.

The results of computer simulations are, just like simulation models or conceptual models, virtual copies of a system (real or proposed). Normally, the researcher can define a set of agents with a predetermined behavior. The interaction of those agents with the simulation model, which is a virtual copy of the real/proposed system, and with each other. That means the agents react to the state of agents and to the changing state of the simulation model (Sismondo, 1999). The simulations that Sismondo describes require a dedicated simulation model and can't be achieved through a conceptual model (Pidd, 1994). This understanding of simulation is closely related to the discrete event simulation for individual entities, that Pidd (1994) described in his paper, which we introduce in Section 3.3.3.

A simulation, in another sense, is a business process simulation. This simulation is not exclusively bound to a simulation model but could be achieved by a conceptual model. It allows the analysis of business processes, or their models respectively, in regard to given metrics like cost, time, or resources (Wynn et al., 2008).

Another kind of simulation is the token game of a Petri Net. This simulation allows us to visualize the possible runs of a Petri Net and the possible states. However, Desel recognizes that it's generally impossible to generate all possible runs of a Petri Net since they can be infinite or the model is so extensive that the simulation can't be finished within a reasonable time frame (Desel, 2000).

We have seen that a simulation varies substantially within the different fields of application. For this thesis, we will focus on the definitions of a simulation within the business process and Petri Net domain. However, for comprehension purposes of the deeper concepts, we will introduce the different categories of simulations in the following section.

3.3.3 Categories of Simulations

In general, we can distinguish between three different categories of simulation. First is the discrete event simulation, which consists once again of three components. Second is the continuous simulation, which also contains three components. Since the world isn't just black and white and we can't always clearly categorize a use case in either of the two simulation categories, Pidd recognizes a third option. It's the combination of the previous two simulation types, the mixed discrete/continuous simulation (Pidd, 1994).

The *discrete event simulation* consists of individual entities, discrete events, and stochastic behavior.

The individual entities are the objects of interest. The behavior of those entities is tracked by the simulation through time. An entity can be a single object, like a machine or a person, or a group of objects, like a machine shop or a group of people.

Discrete events are the building blocks of the behavior of an entity. The entity changes state at those events, which are a point in time. This could be an arrival in a shop or that their service started. Since the event times might not be uniform and the simulation moves from event to event, the simulation flow isn't always smooth.

The last component is stochastic behavior, which states that the interval between events isn't predictable in every case. For example, Pidd states that the service time of a customer may vary. Sometimes, the variation can be perfectly explained, but in the cases where the explanation lacks certainty, we must model the behavior stochastically (Pidd, 1994).

Continuous simulation is popular within the engineering and economy fields of science. The three core components are the aggregated variables, smooth changes in continuous time, and the differential or difference in equations.

Instead of being concerned with individual entities, as is the case in the *discrete event simulation*, the *continuous simulation* focuses on the aggregated behavior of populations. For example, this could be the sales of a car through time.

While the *discrete event simulation* focuses on discrete events and the resulting state changes, in the *continuous simulation*, we concentrate on the gradual changes over time.

The last component is the differential or difference equations. Instead of the stochastic behavior in the *discrete event simulation*, a model of the *continuous simulation* consists of a set of equations that describe the variations of the behavior through time (Pidd, 1994).

The *mixed discrete/continuous simulation* uses all the previously introduced concepts and combines them into one simulation in case the modeler needs both of the approaches to fully grasp the complexity at hand. An example of such a use case might be a factory with some process that fully relies on physics, which can be simulated with a *continuous simulation* since its change is gradual and known, and a second process that has discrete properties. For example, a packing process with machines that have a stochastic behavior (Pidd, 1994).

In Section 3.3.2, we introduced the different definitions of simulations and limited our focus to the definition of business process simulation and Petri Net simulation. In this section, we can assign both of those definitions to the *discrete event simulation* since both definitions of simulations require some sort of event that changes the state of an entity or model. However, this thesis doesn't treat the implementation of *discrete event simulation* but rather the underlying capability. Therefore, no concrete, *discrete event simulation* algorithm will be implemented. The *continuous simulation* is out-of-scope for this thesis and will not be considered going further.

3.4 Modeling Methods

In order to understand the relationship between a modeling method and its domain-specific algorithm, it is crucial to introduce the formal structure of a modeling method. Therefore, we first describe the components of a modeling method and then elaborate on the concepts of the modeling hierarchy and modeling on different meta-levels.

3.4.1 General Overview

Karagiannis and Kühn (2002) suggest a concept of modeling methods where every modeling method consists of two major components, as Figure 3.2 demonstrates. First, the modeling technique, which itself consists of the modeling procedure and modeling language, and second, the mechanisms and algorithms. The set of elements with which a model can be constructed makes the modeling language. The modeling language is further defined by its syntax, semantics, and notation. The modeling process describes the different steps that the modeler has to take in the appliance of the modeling language in order to get a model. The mechanisms and algorithms perform actions, for example, computations, simulations, or constraint checking, upon the created model (Karagiannis and Kühn, 2002).

We now go into detail about the previously mentioned parts of a modeling method and illustrate their dependencies and relationships.

3.4.2 Modeling Technique

As introduced before, the modeling technique consists of the modeling language and modeling procedure. The modeling technique itself, apart from its two sub-components, doesn't define additional concepts (Karagiannis and Kühn, 2002).

Modeling Language

The modeling language contains the set of elements with which the modeler can construct and describe a model. It defines multiple individual components of any language, namely the notation, syntax, and semantics of elements.

Notation: The visual representation of the elements of a modeling language is described by the notation. Karagiannis and Kühn distinguish between two different kinds of approaches. First, the *static* approach, with which we can visualize syntactic constructs, for example, by using stationary visual elements like pixel- or vector-based graphics. However, these representations don't regard

the current state of the element or the model. In order to represent states of elements or a model, we need the *dynamic* approach. The *dynamic* approach consists of a representation component and a control component. At the same time, the representation component works the exact same way as in the *static* approach. The control component, on the other hand, influences the representation component by examining the model state through previously defined rules. In other words, the control component checks the current state with defined rules, and the representation component visualizes the state accordingly (Karagiannis and Kühn, 2002).

Syntax: Every element that is used to create a model is defined by the syntax. In addition, it describes the grammar of those elements. Karagiannis and Kühn define two different ways of defining the syntax of a modeling language. The graph grammar and meta-models. For defining a syntactical meta-model, Karagiannis and Kühn recognized that UML class diagrams are widely used. However, not every syntactical rule can be modeled with a UML class diagram. To mitigate that limitation, constraint languages like OCL (Object Constraint Language) are applied (Karagiannis and Kühn, 2002).

Semantics: Every element of the syntax must have an assigned meaning. The semantics define the meaning of any element of a modeling language. Semantics consists once again of two components: the semantic domain and the semantic mapping. The semantic domain uses ontologies to describe meaning. This construct is closely related to the *ontological aspect* of metamodeling, which is introduced in section 3.5. The semantic mapping uses the semantic domain and connects them to the syntax elements. We can define semantics either formally with axiomatic-, operational-, denotational- or algebraic-semantics or informally by textual description (Karagiannis and Kühn, 2002).

Modeling Procedure

The modeling procedure defines which activities have to be carried out in order to create a model. In addition, the modeling procedure specifies in which sequence some activities have to be fulfilled to get the desired result. The modeling procedure is often defined by the process engineer in the context of metamodeling (Karagiannis and Kühn, 2002). The modeling procedure, as proposed by Karagiannis and Kühn (2002), is closely related to the process aspect from Jeusfeld et al. (2009), which is introduced in Section 3.5.

3.4.3 Mechanisms and Algorithms

The last component of a modeling method, according to Karagiannis and Kühn (2002), is the mechanisms and algorithms. The evaluation of correctness or constraining relation to specific elements can be achieved by the use of mechanisms and algorithms. Karagiannis and Kühn classify the mechanisms and algorithms into three categories based on the level within the modeling hierarchy they're developed and applied (Karagiannis and Kühn, 2002). The different modeling hierarchy levels are introduced in Section 3.4.4.

First, the *generic algorithms* that work for all meta-models which are based on a common meta-meta model. This means the algorithm itself is implemented in the meta-meta model (Karagiannis and Kühn, 2002).

Second, the *specific algorithms*. These algorithms are implemented for one specific meta-model and only work for this specific meta-model and all models based on this meta-model, respectively (Karagiannis and Kühn, 2002).

Lastly, the *hybrid algorithms* are a combination of *generic* and *specific* algorithms. While the algorithm itself is implemented on the meta-meta level, they're always adapted to a specific meta-model. This means we can use *generic* algorithms but change some elements of them to fit a specific use case of a meta-model (Karagiannis and Kühn, 2002).

In addition to the three categories of mechanisms and algorithms, the difference between mechanisms and algorithms must be clarified. In general, algorithms are more complex than mechanisms and are only executed upon manual input from the modeler. Algorithms process the modeled information (e.g., simulations of processes, generation of code). Mechanisms, on the other hand, are less complex and feature only limited functionality (e.g., checking semantics). In contrast to algorithms, mechanisms are executed automatically. The complexity also directly depends on the runtime and performance requirements. Since mechanisms are executed automatically on any change, and therefore almost permanently, they must be very slick and can't use much computing power. However, the algorithms can use much more computing power and time since they're only executed on demand (Kühn et al., 1999).

Figure 3.2: The Components of a Modeling Method according to Karagiannis and Kühn (Karagiannis and Kühn, 2002, p. 185). Reprinted from *Proceedings of the Third International Conference on E-Commerce and Web Technologies* (p. 185), by Karagiannis and Kühn (2002) Springer.

3.4.4 Model Hierarchy

Modeling happens on multiple different levels, depending on the purpose of the model. Both Karagiannis and Kühn (2002) and Geisler et al. (1998) agree on their four-level approach to meta-modeling. Figure 3.3 shows the four levels, namely the meta-meta level, meta level, model level, and instance level. It further introduces the relations between and within the levels. The meta-meta model is created with the meta-metamodeling language and is an indirect model of the meta-model on the meta-level. Furthermore, the meta-meta model is a direct model of the metamodeling language. The same relationship applies to the relation between the meta level and model level. For the relation between the model level and instance level, or original level, respectively, we see that the instance is a model of the model level and isn't created by some sort of instance language. However, we can observe that the concept of the relations is different between the instance and model level than the rest of the modeling hierarchy.

Following the logic of relations above, we can assume that the hierarchy levels can be extended further than just on the meta-meta level, maybe on a meta³-level (Karagiannis and Kühn, 2002).

A very similar explanation of the relationships between the meta-meta level, meta level, and model level is found by Fill et al. (2013). In this concept, Fill et al. define a generic element and attribute in the meta-meta model. All elements (E_1) and attributes (A_1, A_2) of the meta-model are an instance of the meta-meta element or meta-meta attribute. The elements (ϵ_1) and attributes (α_1, α_2) of the model are once again instances of the meta-elements and meta-attributes. Within the same hierarchy level, all the attributes are attached to an element (Fill et al., 2013, p. 3).

Figure 3.4 demonstrates the relationship between a model, meta-model, and meta-meta model on the example of the Petri Net within the ADOxx platform, as Fill et al. (2013) proposed. The ADOxx platform is introduced in Section 5.2.1.

Figure 3.3: A modeling hierarchy of a four level approach: Different models on their respective modeling level created with a specific language of a four level approach (Karagiannis and Kühn, 2002, p. 185) Adapted from *Proceedings of the Third International Conference on E-Commerce and Web Technologies* (p. 185), by Karagiannis and Kühn (2002) Springer.

Figure 3.4: Relationship between a model, its meta-model and its meta-meta model over a four-level modeling hierarchy

3.5 Metamodeling

In Section 3.2, we introduced the theory of conceptual modeling. We now take this theoretical knowledge and combine it with the modeling hierarchy from the previous section. This combined knowledge allows us to understand metamodeling. First, we introduce metamodeling as a generic concept and show how generic frameworks are used in the context of metamodeling. Furthermore, we dive deeper into the different types of metamodeling that Jeusfeld et al. (2009) identified.

In short, metamodeling is the activity to create and integrate models about models. Those resulting models are called *meta-models* and may be from different domains (Geisler et al., 1998; Jeusfeld et al., 2009). Kern (2016) defines metamodeling as "*a modeling activity applied to modeling itself.*" (Kern, 2016, p. 14). Meta-models are, therefore, based on the same abstraction concept as data and meta-data. In other words, a meta-model describes the notation definition level. We can observe that applications like business process engineering and schema and data integration highly profit from that higher abstraction, with which a meta-model can describe a domain. The actions and interactions of modelers and users are constrained by the meta-model, or more precisely, the definitions modeled within the meta-model (Jeusfeld et al., 2009). Through metamodeling, we define the process of the latter modeling (Kern, 2016). The artifact of modeling is a model-instance, and the artifact of metamodeling is a modeling environment, respectively, a modeling method (Jeusfeld et al., 2009).

The definition of a meta-model is done with a metamodeling language. That means (meta-) modeling is based upon multiple different language levels, like they're introduced in Section 3.4.4 (Karagiannis and Kühn, 2002).

Figure 3.5: Four Aspects and Focus Elements of Meta-Model Based Environments (Jeusfeld et al., 2009, p. 52) Adapted from "Metamodeling for Method Engineering", by Jeusfeld et al. (2009)

There exist generic approaches to meta-models, like the Information Resource Dictionary System metamodeling framework. It describes a generic and elementary architecture for metamodeling environment and is implemented, for example, within the MetaEdit+ by Metacase. The approach provides a full architecture from data up to the meta-meta level (see Section 3.5.2), whereas each level defines the degree of freedom and precision in its syntax and semantics. While such generic approaches can be applied within multiple domains, the value of domain-specific meta-models can be substantially higher (Jeusfeld et al., 2009).

As Figure 3.5 shows, Jeusfeld et al. (2009) distinguish between ontology-based, notation-oriented and process-oriented metamodeling. These three aspects of a meta-model, in addition to the goal aspect, are not mutually exclusive but supplement each other into one complete meta-model. If one or more of the aspects are missing or incomplete, we can't guarantee that the meta-model is fully interoperable and adaptable (Jeusfeld et al., 2009).

The *ontological aspect* treats the level of abstraction of a meta-model based on meaningful and sufficient generic concepts. This means that a meta-model must provide an appropriate level of abstraction to fully grasp the essence of the artifact. With the ontology, we have a set of individual concepts and one or more relationships between them. This system of concepts and relationships forms the basis for modeling an artifact (Jeusfeld et al., 2009, p. 53).

With the *notational aspect*, we can manipulate or convey an ontological construct. A notation can either be formal, semi-formal, or informal. A notation represents an ontological construct as a matrix in textual form, tabular form, or graphically. The basis of a notation forms an ontological concept. This means that a notation is related to an underlying ontological rule (e.g., semantics). This relation isn't mutually exclusive and can be m:n. Jeusfeld et al. provide an example of an entity of Chen's ER model (Chen, 1976; Jeusfeld et al., 2009). They show that the concept of an entity can either be related to or represented by respectively, either a graphical element or a textual element (Jeusfeld et al., 2009).

Also, within metamodeling, we can define a process as a partially ordered sequence of activities or process steps that result in the wanted product or service. A similar concept is found in a modeling method that follows the structure of Karagiannis and Kühn (2002). However, as metamodeling is an abstraction of modeling, we abstract the process in order to get a process meta-model. The process meta-model is closely related to the ontology and notation and assumes certain concepts from both of them. The *process aspect* defines, therefore, the modeling process while enacting the ontological concepts and their notations (Jeusfeld et al., 2009).

The last aspect, which Jeusfeld et al. describe, is the *goal aspect*. Goals influence decisions on ontological concepts, notations, processes, and their respective relations. Jeusfeld et al. describe the following example: The goal of multi-user capability of a system implicates different requirements for the underlying concepts than single-user capability. The *goal aspect* and their influence on interoperation and adaption are not well studied for the moment and remain an interesting topic for future research (Jeusfeld et al., 2009).

3.5.1 Metamodeling Platforms

Apart from the term metamodeling platform, we can observe that the synonyms *metamodeling environment*, *metamodeling tool*, or *metamodeling framework* are used. For this thesis, we limit ourselves to the term metamodeling platform.

There exist multiple different metamodeling platforms that are built on specific architectures and meta-meta models. A metamodeling platform is a software application, that allows a modeler to define a modeling method, a meta-model respectively, on a platform specific meta-meta model. The meta-meta model of a platform provides the specific building blocks for a meta-model on the respective platform. Karagiannis and Kühn identified four different architectures and demonstrated them on four different metamodeling platforms, among them ADOxx and MetaEdit+. The conclusion of their analysis resulted in the remark that metamodeling platforms shall all have a distributable, scalable, and component-based architecture to provide great value (Karagiannis and Kühn, 2002). The specific architecture and the respective feature set of the analyzed metamodeling platforms are described in Chapter 5.3 in detail. In Section 3.6, the MM-AR Platform of the University of Fribourg is introduced.

A metamodeling platform generally consists of five components (*language workbench*, *modeling tool*, *model storage*, *model processing*, *interfaces*) and always implements a specific modeling hierarchy with a specific amount of levels. The meta-modeler can define a modeling method, respectively the meta-model of a modeling method, by means of the metamodeling platform. Furthermore, the metamodeling platform may enable the definition and execution of generic as well as domain-specific processing methods (Kern, 2016). This model processing is implemented directly within the meta-meta model of the metamodeling platform (= generic mechanism/algorithm), implemented on the meta-meta model but can be adapted to the domain-specific meta-model (= hybrid mechanism/algorithm), or gets implemented directly by the meta-modeler within the domain-specific meta-model (= specific mechanism/algorithm) (Karagiannis and Kühn, 2002; Kern, 2016).

The *language workbench* allows meta-modelers to define modeling methods with abstract and concrete syntax using dialog-based, textual, or graphical approaches, resulting in modeling language specifications as development artifacts (Kern, 2016).

Modeling tools enable the creation of models adhering to the predefined language (= meta-model). By reading the language definition, the tool establishes the modeling capabilities. Modelers are the typical users of a modeling tool and utilize it for their modeling needs (Kern, 2016).

The *model storage's* primary responsibility is to ensure the persistence of models and meta-models. It typically implements the conformity between models and their corresponding meta-models, ensuring that all models adhere to the appropriate (meta-)meta-model. Additionally, the *model storage* may offer extra functionalities like version control or multi-user support. The implementation can range from simple file systems to more complex database systems (Kern, 2016).

The *model processing* is typically enabled by purpose-built components or tools within the metamodeling platform. The metamodeling platforms differ from each other in regard to the provided processing languages and capabilities. While some allow for the use of general programming languages like JavaScript or Python (e.g., WebGME, see Section 5.2.3), others use special and purpose-built languages like AdoScript in ADOxx (see Section 5.2.1) (Kern, 2016).

Lastly, the *interfaces* allow the import and export of meta-models as well as related models. Through interfaces, a metamodeling platform can be integrated into a complete workflow, since the data created and persisted within the platform can be collected from or distributed to other tools (Kern, 2016).

3.5.2 Meta-Metamodeling

As we have seen in the introduction to meta-models, the meta-meta model (or meta²-model) is once again an additional abstraction. If we abstract the meta-model again and raise it from level 2 to level 3 (see Figure 3.3), we get the meta-meta model. Following this reasoning, the meta-model is an instance of the meta-meta model. In academia, multiple different amounts of hierarchy levels are proposed (Geisler et al., 1998; de Lara and Guerra, 2010). In recent research as well as practice nowadays, we mostly see four overall levels. The four levels consist of level 0, which is the original, the model (layer 1), the meta-model (layer 2), and the meta-meta model (layer 3) (Karagiannis and Kühn, 2002). This concept of the four levels, with their respective dependencies and relations, is illustrated in Figure 3.3 and elaborated in Section 3.4.4.

3.6 MM-AR Platform

As mentioned before, there exist multiple different metamodeling platforms like ADOxx, MetaEdit+, and the Eclipse Modeling Framework (Fill and Karagiannis, 2013). However, their current capabilities are limited to the traditional 2D space and concepts of metamodeling. The concepts of 3D metamodeling and the incorporation of new concepts like AR and VR were not included in the previously mentioned platforms (Muff and Fill, 2021). Muff and Fill describe their vision of modeling without conscious modeling, which could be achieved using AR and VR. They propose the incorporation of modeling in the daily workflow of the employee. In the end, modeling shall be an unconscious task, just like writing an email. In their research, Muff and Fill mainly focused on the representation, presentation, and scope of models. Therefore, they developed a metamodeling framework for AR and VR and implemented the concept in a prototype called the *metamodeling Platform for AR and VR* (MM-AR Platform). The *MM-AR Platform* is still in its early phase of

development and is constantly developing further. To this day, multiple meta-models for modeling methods like BPMN 2.0 (Business Process Modeling Notation), ArchiMate, UML (Unified Modeling Language), and Petri Nets are developed and available for modeling. However, none of these meta-models are capable of incorporating the mechanisms and algorithms of a modeling method. Only the Petri Net features the *token game*, although it's hard-coded on the client side and not implemented within the meta-model.

Within their work, Muff and Fill (2021) evaluated existing meta-models in order to identify the relevant concepts that are used in conventional 2D metamodeling. Based on those findings, they derived the necessary concepts for the representation of models in a 3D space. The representation within a 3D space enables the use of models in AR and VR. Muff and Fill wanted to use a state-of-the-art technology stack, which would allow them to develop any AR and VR application that uses a web-based environment (Muff and Fill, 2021). Through the combination of the meta-model findings and technical requirements, the meta-meta model in Figure 3.6 emerged. The meta-meta model allows the modeler to use the platform as well as all the models in a 2D and 3D space. However, the meta-meta model always works within a 3D space and only emulates a 2D space by setting the z-coordinates (depth axis) to a constant (Muff and Fill, 2021).

The MM-AR Platform has two major components. First, the development toolkit which allows a meta-modeler to create his own meta-model. The definition of a meta-model is done within a .JSON file, which is persisted into the database through a Representational State Transfer (REST) Application Programming Interface (API). Currently, there doesn't exist a finished meta-model editor with a Graphical User Interface (GUI) for the MM-AR Platform. However, such a client is in development.

The second component of the MM-AR Platform is the modeling toolkit itself. The modeling toolkit is web-based and allows the modeler to model his domain with the previously implemented meta-model. Further, the modeling toolkit allows the use of AR and VR. The modeling toolkit provides a fully functional GUI. The modeling toolkit is now available in the second major version and features a more modern look & feel than the prototype in the 2021 paper by Muff and Fill.

We now go into detail about the meta-meta model and modeling hierarchy of a MM-AR platform in the following section. The chapter is closed by elaborating on the current architecture and technology stack.

3.6.1 Meta-Meta Model and Modeling Hierarchy

The different levels of models also apply to the MM-AR platform, and the fundamental principles of the modeling hierarchy are described in Section 3.4.4. Since the MM-AR platform is still under development, the following description only applies to the time of writing. Future developments and changes to the meta-meta model have not been taken into account.

The platform's meta-meta model is implemented in the programming language JavaScript, and the platform's generic functionality is implemented on that level. Furthermore, the platform features an abstract meta-model that the developers developed on the same level. As introduced in Section 3.5, a meta-model is an instance of a meta-meta model. So, the abstract meta-model of the MM-AR platform is an instance of the platform's meta-meta model, which is shown in Figure 3.6. The meta-meta model includes classes, relationclasses on the classic meta-meta level as well

The meta-meta model of a MM-AR platform is shown in Figure 3.6 but only includes a subset of the actual constructs due to space limitations in this thesis. However, all relevant and used constructs are present. There exists a *meta-layer* and an *instance-layer* in order to show the relationship between the description of a modeling language and the instantiation of specific elements when defining a model. The *instance-layer* is not shown, and this thesis concentrates on the *meta-layer* of a MM-AR platform. The *meta-layer* contains the superclass *metaobject* from which the core classes *class*, *role*, *attribute*, *attribute_type*, *Port*, and *scene_type* inherit. All the core classes also count for the *meta-layer* (Muff and Fill, 2021).

The core components of the meta-layer contain *classes* and *relationclasses*, which are included in one or multiple *scene_types*. The *scene_type* represents an enclosed 3D space of any model which holds the assigned subset of *classes* and *relationclasses*. Within the modeling toolkit of the MM-AR Platform, the modeler can choose one of the available *scene_types*, and the 3D space of the model, together with the assigned *classes* and *relationclasses* are displayed and can be modified. *Classes*, *relationclasses*, and *scene_types* can have *attributes* of exactly one *attribute_type*, which specifies the characteristic of that component. The *attribute_type* can be of any type, for example, Integer or String (Muff and Fill, 2021).

A *class*, as an abstract construct, describes elements with similar characteristics, behavior, and semantics. It's comparable to the *element* of the modeling hierarchy in Figure 3.3. A *relationclass* describes the relation between *classes*, *relationclasses*, and *scene_types*. The *relationclass* isn't connected directly to any of these constructs but rather has exactly two *roles* assigned. Every *role*, more specifically a *from_role*, and *to_role*, has at least one reference to a *class*, *relationclass*, or *scene_type*, which defines to what constructs that role can connect. In addition, any *class* or *scene_type* can have *ports* to which *roles* can be assigned (Muff and Fill, 2021).

All the core components that inherit from the superclass *metaobject* have a visual representation, which is defined using the domain-specific language *VizRep* (Visual Representation). *VizRep* uses generic JavaScript functions and allows the meta-modeler to define the 3D representation and behavior of an element. This 3D representation is stored within the *geometry* attribute in the superclass *metaobject*. The meta-modeler can currently choose between a plane, cube, and sphere for representing the object. In addition, he can assign his own graphic texture, for example, a picture, to that object within the meta-model. These textures must be in the format base64 or GL transmission format (glTF). However, if the meta-modeler chooses the base64 format, he limits his object to a 2D representation even in a 3D space since the graphic as a 2D texture is projected onto the object. If the meta-modeler wants to represent an object in 3D with its own 3D texture, he must use glTF. In addition to the texture map, the meta-modeler can assign values like width, height, depth, or color if no texture is assigned (Muff and Fill, 2021).

Each object has 2D (*coordinates2D*) as well as 3D coordinates. However, the 2D coordinates can differ from the 3D coordinates. The 3D coordinates are used for the visualization in AR and VR and are stored as relative (*relativeCoordinates3D*) as well as absolute (*absoluteCoordinates3D*) coordinates. The *absoluteCoordinates3D* can be used for determining the exact positioning using the Global Positioning System (GPS) or an indoor positioning system (Muff and Fill, 2021).

This initial version of the meta-meta model of the MM-AR Platform underwent multiple refinements and was extended significantly since its initial version. While the initial meta-meta model

was user-independent, the reworked version introduces individual *users* as well as *user_groups*. Every *user* belongs to a *user_groups*, which subsequently can have read, modification, and creation permissions. Naturally, both entities inherit the properties from the superclass *metaobject*, since they're both metaobjects. A second element that was added to the initial version is the *generic_constraint*, which is a subclass of the *metaobject*.

Since we concentrate on the meta-meta level in this thesis and will only explore the concrete implementation of the MM-AR Platform of the University of Fribourg, we limit the explanation of the meta-meta model to the meta-meta-concepts and deliberately leave out the instance components.

3.6.2 Architecture and Technology Stack

The evaluation of the technical feasibility of the meta-meta model was conducted based on the prototypical implementation by Muff and Fill (2021). The prototype was developed using the programming language JavaScript and the WebXR API through the Three.js library (Muff and Fill, 2021). The WebXR Device API is based on JavaScript and allows applications to interact with AR and VR devices. The API is aimed at the interaction of web applications with AR and VR devices. The developers emphasize that those AR and VR experiences can be hosted on web servers, rather than on-premise systems (W3C, 2023-07-08:1930 CEST).

The platform uses Node.js as the runtime environment and implements the framework Aurelia for data binding. Node.js is an event-driven JavaScript runtime that allows a developer to implement scalable network applications (OpenJS-Foundation, 2023-07-08:1800 CEST). Aurelia allows developers to build modern, robust applications using modular JavaScript code designed for browsers, desktops, and mobile devices while adhering to open internet standards (BlueSpire-Inc., 2023-07-08:1845 CEST). The use of Aurelia had the additional effect of using TypeScript as the main development language. For a flexible back-end web solution, the developers chose Express.js. Node.js, Express.js and Aurelia are open-source and thus freely available.

The MM-AR Platform uses the open-source PostgreSQL database, which is an object-relational database system. The communication between the components is based on the internet standard protocol HTTP (Hypertext Transfer Protocol).

As already mentioned before, the development toolkit as well as the modeling toolkit are part of the MM-AR Platform. Both of them are web applications that can be accessed through any modern browser. If the modeler wants to access the AR and VR capabilities, he needs to access the web application directly through an AR or VR-capable device, for example, a mobile phone or tablet, or connect a head-mounted display (HMD), for example, a VR headset like the Meta Quest 2 or Apple Vision Pro. Currently, due to proprietary restrictions, the AR and VR capabilities can't be accessed on Apple mobile devices.

Chapter 4

Design Objectives for the Artifact

The following chapter treats the second activity of the DSRM by Peffers et al. (2007) in more detail than before. Section 4.1 will define and describe the artifact itself, and Section 4.2 will outline the design objectives of the artifact. The design objectives served as a basis for more detailed requirements for the solution in Section 4.3.

4.1 Definition of the Artifact

As stated in Section 2, the artifact of this thesis is the *generic concept for implementing algorithms on an MM-AR based platform*. The argumentation for this artifact is as follows: The existing MM-AR Platform of the University of Fribourg is limited to metamodeling and modeling. As we have learned, the model is a representation of an aspect of the real world. However, it's a simulation that brings the respective model to life.

The MM-AR Platform can't fully implement all components of a modeling method, according to Karagiannis and Kühn (2002). While the modeling language is covered extensively, the mechanisms and algorithms are completely missing. This means we can't use mechanisms and algorithms within the modeling procedure and can't extract data from a model or analyze the model. This prohibits the community of interest from getting insights into a model and benefiting from it.

Following the reasoning above, we can conclude that the artifact, the *generic concept for implementing algorithms on an MM-AR based platform*, addresses an important and unsolved issue and therefore satisfies the second guideline of Hevner et al. (2004).

4.2 Definition of the Design Objectives

Based on the problem statement in Section 1.1, the definition of the artifact in the previous section, as well as the knowledge about the MM-AR Platform, the detailed design objectives were defined. This section defines the design objectives and constrains the solution space of the artifact and the prototype. In order to satisfy the statement of Peffers et al. (2007) that the objectives shall be defined based on the problem definition and knowledge about the technical feasibility, the author considered different perspectives.

The thesis at hand builds upon the MM-AR Platform prototype by Muff and Fill (2021). Therefore, the platform itself provides some constraints regarding the technical feasibility of the generic concept since it has to work with the currently used technology stack. In the following Table 4.1, all the design objectives are described in detail. Each design objective has a unique identifier (DO-XX), name, short description, and source. The design objectives are either derived from the analysis of the MM-AR Platform, from the paper by Muff and Fill (2021), or from the knowledge of the author regarding the technical feasibility of solutions. The design objectives are divided into design objectives for the generic concept for implementing mechanisms and algorithms and into design objectives for the latter concrete implementation in the existing MM-AR Platform.

ID	Name	Description	Source
Concept-targeted design objectives			
DO-01	Development of the generic concept	The generic concept integrates mechanisms and algorithms into the existing MM-AR meta-meta model	Author
DO-02	Minimal changes to the MM-AR meta-meta model	The generic concept shall require minimal changes within the meta-meta model	Author
DO-03	Reuse existing concepts	The generic concept uses proven concepts which are used by other metamodeling platforms	Author
DO-04	Meta-modeler faced functionalities	The prototype provides the user with all necessary functionalities for defining domain-specific mechanisms and algorithms	Author
MM-AR Platform targeted design objectives			
DO-05	Implementation in the MM-AR Platform	The prototype of the generic concept is implemented in the MM-AR Platform	Author
DO-06	State-of-the-art technologies	The prototype uses state-of-the-art technologies	Author
DO-07	Allow meta-modeler code	The generic concept and prototype allow the meta-modeler to use predefined and individual code	Author

ID	Name	Description	Source
DO-08	Support of legacy meta-models	The prototype works with all the previously defined meta-models and doesn't restrict their functionalities	MM-AR Platform
DO-09	Minimal changes to the MM-AR Platform	The generic concept shall require minimal changes within the MM-AR Platform	Author

Table 4.1: Design Objectives for the generic concept for implementing algorithms on a MM-AR based platform

For this work, mechanisms and algorithms shall be integrated into the MM-AR meta-meta model and shall allow a meta-modeler to define mechanisms and algorithms (DO-01). However, the author aims towards minimal changes within the existing meta-meta model (DO-02).

This technology-independent concept for MM-AR based platforms will be integrated into the existing MM-AR Platform of the University of Fribourg (DO-05). As already within the meta-meta model, the changes required shall be minimized (DO-09).

In this work, the author will analyze existing metamodeling platforms and evaluate their approach to integrating mechanisms and algorithms. The identified approaches will be explored, and a state-of-the-art approach will be used to develop the generic concept (DO-03). Furthermore, the author aims to either reuse the state-of-the-art technology stack of the MM-AR Platform or use additional state-of-the-art technologies (DO-06). The meta-modeler shall be able to use generic code snippets, like a for-loop or if/else statements, as well as platform-specific code, like retrieving all connected objects of any object, for defining any mechanism or algorithm (DO-04, DO-07).

While the meta-meta model, as well as the client-side code of the MM-AR Platform, will change to some degree, all existing legacy meta-models should still work within the database and modeling toolkit (DO-08). Naturally, the legacy meta-models can be extended with the new mechanism and algorithm capability of the platform for full functionality.

4.3 Requirements

Based on the design objectives defined in the previous section, the requirements for a generic concept, as well as the platform-specific requirements, are derived. However, the platform-specific requirements can only be defined after the generic concept is developed in Section 5.3.1. Therefore, the process of deriving requirements is an iterative operation throughout the whole research process. The analysis of metamodeling platforms in Chapter 5.3 will create additional requirements or demonstrate the technical infeasibility of others. The requirements in Tables 4.2 and 4.3 were not final in their initial versions but were refined over multiple weeks of research.

According to the International Requirements Engineering Board (IREB), a requirement is: "**1.** *a need perceived by a stakeholder*, **2.** *a capability or property that a system shall have* or **3.** *a document representation of a need, capability or property*" (Glinz, 2022, p. 16). The IEEE defines a requirement as follows: "**1.** *a document used by the acquirer as a means to announce intention*

to potential bidders to acquire a specified system, product, or service. **2.** a request for services, research, or a product prepared by a customer and delivered to prospective developers with the expectation that prospective developers will respond with their proposed cost, schedule, and development approach. **3.** a type of procurement document used to request proposals from prospective sellers of products or services. In some application areas, it may have a narrower or more specific meaning. **4.** collection of formal documents that includes a description of the desired form of response from a potential supplier, the relevant statement of work for the supplier, and required provisions in the supplier agreement" (ISO et al., 2010, p. 380). The IEEE definition complies with the standard ISO/IEC/IEEE 24765 (ISO et al., 2010).

IREB, within their handbook for the certified professional for requirements engineering from Glinz et al. (2022), as well as Ebert (2012), distinguishes between three basic types of requirements. First, there's the functional requirement. A functional requirement describes the functionality that a system shall have. It further explains what a system has to do and how it has to use the input to gain the desired output (Ebert, 2012; Glinz et al., 2022).

Second, the quality requirement explains a qualitative property of a system or a specific feature of a system. The quality requirement further specifies functional requirements in regard to their performance, resilience, availability, security, or similar aspects (Ebert, 2012; Glinz et al., 2022).

The third type of requirements are constraints. Constraints limit the available solution space even further than the functional and quality requirements already do. A constraint could be a specific law (e.g., a data-security law), an organizational guideline that must be followed, or something completely different that limits our development process in some way (Ebert, 2012; Glinz et al., 2022).

Tables 4.2 and 4.3 specify the individual requirements for the generic concept as well as for the later prototypical implementation on the MM-AR Platform. The requirements are derived from the design objectives, while the MM-AR Platform or the author's knowledge provides the details.

Every requirement is categorized according to the three types of requirements (functional-, quality-, constraint-requirement). The type of requirement can be distinguished via the requirement identifier (Req-ID) since functional requirements are labeled as *FR-XX*, quality requirements as *QR-XX*, and constraint requirements as *CR-XX*. In addition, every requirement features a name and a definition. For the definition of a requirement, the template of "die SOPHISTen" was used (Kluge, 2016). As already with the design objectives, the requirements must have a source to ensure traceability of all requirements. Each requirement must address at least one design objective to contribute to the fulfillment of the goals. The requirements are grouped into the requirements for the generic concept and for the MM-AR Platform. For the generic concept, no constraint requirements were derived.

Requirements for the Generic Concept

Req-ID	Name	Definition	Source	DO-ID
Functional Requirements				
FR-01	Domain-specific mechanisms and algorithms	The meta-modeler shall be able to define domain-specific mechanisms and algorithms.	Author	DO-04, DO-07

Req-ID	Name	Definition	Source	DO-ID
FR-02	Use of platform-specific code	The meta-modeler shall be able to use platform-specific code without any knowledge about the architecture of the platform.	Author	DO-04, DO-07
FR-03	Use of generic code	The meta-modeler shall be able to use non-platform-specific code to supplement his mechanisms and algorithms.	Author	DO-07
FR-04	Support all legacy meta-models	The platform shall support all legacy meta-models which didn't implement mechanisms or algorithms.	MM-AR Platform	DO-08
FR-09	Execute algorithms	The modeler shall be able to execute an algorithm.	Author	DO-05
FR-10	Define the calling of algorithms	The meta-modeler shall be able to define how an algorithm is called.	Author	DO-05
Quality Requirements				
QR-01	Reusable concept	The developed additions to the MM-AR meta-meta model shall be usable for all MM-AR based platforms.	Author	DO-01, DO-02, DO-03
QR-02	Technology independent	The developed additions to the MM-AR meta-meta model shall be technology-independent.	Author	DO-01, DO-03

Table 4.2: Requirements for the generic concept

Requirements for the MM-AR Platform-Based Prototype

Req-ID	Name	Definition	Source	DO-ID
Functional Requirements				
FR-05	Definition of mechanisms and algorithms	The meta-modeler shall be able to define mechanisms and algorithms in the same manner as the visual representation.	MM-AR Platform	DO-05, DO-06, DO-07
FR-06	Get attribute values	The meta-modeler shall be able to read and write attribute values.	Author	DO-07
FR-07	Prompt messages	The meta-modeler shall be able to prompt messages.	Author	DO-07
FR-08	Restrict actions	The platform shall allow type-checking and restrict modeling activities.	Author	DO-05, DO-07

Req-ID	Name	Definition	Source	DO-ID
Quality Requirements				
QR-03	Same performance	The platform shall integrate mechanisms and algorithms without any performance deterioration.	MM-AR Platform	DO-09
Constraint Requirements				
CR-01	Use existing platform	The prototype shall use the already used technology stack of the MM-AR Platform.	MM-AR Platform	DO-05, DO-06, DO-09

Table 4.3: Requirements for the MM-AR Platform-based prototype

The defined requirements will serve as a foundation for the evaluation of the generic concept and prototype at the end of this thesis.

Chapter 5

Design and Development of a Generic Algorithm Specification

This chapter describes the design and development process of the *generic concept for implementing mechanisms and algorithms on an MM-AR-based platform* and, therefore, the artifact of this thesis. First, the author reviews existing approaches to the implementation of mechanisms and algorithms on other metamodeling platforms like ADOxx, MetaEdit+, WebGME, and AToMPM. For this, the author analyzes scientific research literature and conducts his own testing of the respective metamodeling platform. The approaches are going to be evaluated according to the rating matrix, which is developed in Section 5.1 in accordance with the standard ISO/IEC 25010:2011. After reviewing the existing approaches, the author suggests an MM-AR-specific approach by extending the existing meta-meta model.

5.1 Rating Matrix and Evaluation Properties

In the following section, the author introduces the ISO/IEC 25010:2011 standard specification in detail and develops the rating matrix.

First, we need to examine what a quality model for software systems actually is. The ISO/IEC 25010:2011 standard is situated within the Quality Model Division 2501n and replaces the outdated standard ISO/IEC 9126-1:2001. The Quality Model Division distinguished three quality models, namely the *Data Quality Model*, *Product Quality Model*, and *Quality in Use Model*. However, only the latter two are specified within the ISO/IEC 25010:2011. The *Data Quality Model*'s specification can be found within the ISO/IEC 25012 specification (ISO, 2012).

The *Product Quality Model* categorizes the quality properties of a system into eight different characteristics. First, the *functional suitability* assesses the functional completeness, correctness, and appropriateness. Second, the *performance efficiency* in regard to time-behavior, resource utilization, and capacity. The *compatibility* treats the co-existence and interoperability of a system and its environment. Fourth is one of the most obvious and user-faced ones: the *usability* of a system. It assesses the appropriateness, recognisability, learnability, operability, user error protection, user interface aesthetics, and accessibility. Then, the *reliability* in regard to matu-

ity, availability, fault tolerance, and recoverability. The *security* treats confidentiality, integrity, non-repudiation, accountability, and authenticity. The *maintainability* includes the modularity, reusability, analysability, modifiability, and testability of a system. Lastly, the *portability* assesses the adaptability, installability, and replaceability of a system (ISO, 2012).

Important to note is the interdependency between the different characteristics. The need for a certain property within one specific characteristic might lead to implicit requirements within another characteristic.

The *Quality in Use Model* of the standard regards the outcomes of the interaction with a system. Therefore, five different characteristics are defined: *Effectiveness*, *Efficiency*, *Satisfaction* (e.g., usefulness, trust, pleasure, comfort), *Freedom from risk* (e.g., economic risk mitigation, health and safety risk mitigation, environmental risk mitigation), and *Context coverage* (e.g., context completeness, flexibility). These characteristics describe the impact of a system on its stakeholders. However, the impact on stakeholders, respectively on the quality in use, of a system isn't exclusively determined by the quality of the software but also by the users, hardware, operating and social environment, as well as the conducted activity (ISO, 2012).

For the rating matrix, the author takes elements out of both of the introduced models of the ISO/IEC 25010:2011 standard without incorporating all of the characteristics of either model. The derived rating matrix is displayed in Table 5.1. On the following pages, the author will explain all aspects in detail and introduce the respective points of every characteristic.

Property/ Characteristic	Scale and Explanation
Functional completeness	<p>This characteristic describes how many of the demanded functionalities are fulfilled by the metamodeling platform. In the context of this work, the features required are the integration of mechanisms and the integration of algorithms. Multiple ways of implementing mechanisms or algorithms don't lead to additional points.</p> <p>2: Integration of mechanisms and algorithms possible; 1: Integration of mechanisms or algorithms possible; 0: No integration of mechanisms or algorithms possible</p>
Capacity	<p>The capacity describes how long the specified code of a mechanism or algorithm can be before reaching the platform limit. The length of the code equals the number of characters used.</p> <p>3: Unlimited length of code; 2: Limited length of code ($<2^{20} - 2$ number of characters $<2^{30} - 2$); 1: Limited length of code ($<2^{20} - 2$ characters); 0: No integration of mechanisms or algorithms possible</p>

Property/ Characteristic	Scale and Explanation
Resource utilisation	<p>The performance of a metamodeling platform is dependent on multiple factors (e.g., workload of CPU) and is very hard to measure precisely. Therefore, we consider only if the platform can use multiple cores (or multiple threads) or only one thread for the execution of mechanisms and algorithms. Web applications are treated as Multi-Core/Multi-Thread capable since they can be distributed on a scaleable server landscape.</p> <p>1: Multi-Core/Multi-Thread; 0: Single-Core/Single-Thread</p>
User error protection	<p>We evaluate how many measures are in place to protect the user from his own errors (e.g., type-checking, syntax correction etc.); the more measures are integrated, the better.</p> <p>2: Extensive error protection; 1: Limited error protection; 0: No error protection</p>
Learnability	<p>The learnability defines how much effort a meta-modeler has to put in in order to learn how to integrate a mechanism or algorithm on the metamodeling platform. The complexity of a mechanism or algorithm is not taken into account.</p> <p>5: Very low effort, intuitive usability; 4: Low effort, intuitive learning; 3: Average effort; 2: High effort, research in documentation required; 1: Very high effort, extensive research in documentation and tutorials required</p>
Documentation	<p>The amount of documentation and the detail of the available documentation are rated. Only the documentation regarding mechanisms and algorithms is considered.</p> <p>2: Extensive documentation available; 1: Limited documentation available; 0: No documentation available</p>
Reusability	<p>The degree of reusability of components in the system in regard to implementing mechanisms and algorithms. e.g., If the meta-modeler can reuse code (e.g., functions), combine code, or use outside code</p> <p>3: Highly reusable (all of the above); 2: Limited reusability (at least two, but not all); 1: Single-format reusability (one technique); 0: No reusability available</p>
Testability	<p>The author tries to evaluate how easy and fast the meta-modeler can test his developed mechanisms and algorithms. Easy/Hard in terms of effort for the meta-modeler to conduct testing, and Fast/Slow in terms of the runtime of the respective test. However, the author deliberately doesn't specify any runtime metrics since the runtime of testing will be rated relatively and not in absolute numbers.</p> <p>3: Easy & fast; 2: Easy & slow OR Hard & fast; 0: Slow & hard</p>

Property/ Characteristic	Scale and Explanation
Installability	Each metamodeling platform is rated in accordance with its operating platform support. Although this rating is not directly related to mechanisms and algorithms, it can have a direct impact on the choice of metamodeling and modeling platforms. Therefore, each supported operating platform (Windows, MacOS, Linux) and technology (x86, ARM) will earn the metamodeling platform a point.
Usefulness (For programmers)	The metric of how satisfied the meta-modeler is in using the tool and with the achieved result. We evaluate the usefulness for someone who is a technical person and wants to use non-graphical tools for the definition of mechanisms and algorithms. 3: Very satisfied; 2: Satisfied; 1: More or less satisfied; 0: Not satisfied
Usefulness (For non-technical people)	The metric of how satisfied the meta-modeler is in using the tool and with the achieved result. We evaluate the usefulness for someone who is a non-technical person and wants to use graphical tools for the definition of mechanisms and algorithms. 3: Very satisfied; 2: Satisfied; 1: More or less satisfied; 0: Not satisfied
Context completeness	The metric of how well the metamodeling platform performs its task within the specified context of use. 3: High completeness; 2: Complete; 1: More or less completeness; 0: Not complete
Flexibility	To what degree the metamodeling platform can be used outside of the specified context and requirements. 3: High Flexibility; 2: Average flexibility; 1: Low flexibility

Table 5.1: Rating matrix for metamodeling platforms derived from ISO/IEC 25010:2011

The author deliberately decided against rating the GUI, which would treat the user interface aesthetics of the *Product Quality Model*, since aesthetics are very subjective and don't significantly add value to the metamodeling platform. However, the GUI is partially included within the rating matrix through *Learnability* and *Usefulness* for non-technical people. Since the metamodeling platform shall be intuitive to learn and use, the GUI plays a substantial role in this domain.

In addition to the rating matrix, the feature sets and architecture of each metamodeling platform will be explained in detail. For the comparison of the metamodeling platforms, the list of features of metamodeling platforms according to Karagiannis and Visic (2011) is used. For reference, the list of features is shown in Table 5.2. However, the author waives a rating of the architecture or provided feature set in regard to quality for everything that isn't already rated based on the rating matrix in Table 5.1.

In addition to the feature set, any proprietary programming languages for defining mechanisms and algorithms are going to be introduced.

Feature	Description
Language Definition Approach	Graphical, form-based, hybrid
Specifying Notation	Graphical, text-based, hybrid
Syntax Highlighting and Debugging	Support for highlighting, auto-completing, debugging
Scripting	Scripting support for advanced customizing
Import and Export	Import and export of meta-models and models
Integration with Other Tools	APIs, Client-Side, Server-Side Integration
Rich Notation	More than simple symbols for nodes and arcs
Dynamic Symbol Change	Symbols change dynamically when model data changes
Different Modeling Views	Modeling, matrix, tabular view

Table 5.2: List of features used to compare metamodeling platforms (Karagiannis and Visic, 2011, p. 25). Reprinted from *Perspectives in Business Informatics Research* (p. 25), by Karagiannis and Visic (2011) Springer.

5.2 Review of Existing Approaches

The tools selected for this thesis have a big impact on the results and, thus, on the generic concept for the MM-AR platform. Therefore, a small set of properties had to be fulfilled by every metamodeling platform in order to be taken into account for the analysis. Every tool in the analysis shall provide an appropriate level of maturity. This means that it must be installable, and all features regarding mechanisms and algorithms must work appropriately. In addition, the metamodeling platform shall provide documentation of its features.

The analysis included exclusively graphical metamodeling platforms. Subsequently, all Domain-Specific Language Platforms, which limit themselves to purely code-based metamodeling and modeling (e.g., *MontiCore* by the RWTH Aachen University), are excluded from the analysis and evaluation. Therefore, their approach doesn't influence the generic concept for implementing mechanisms and algorithms on MM-AR-based platforms.

Following this, the analysis and evaluation are limited to the following platforms: *ADOxx* by the BOC Group, *MetaEdit+* by MetaCase, *WebGME* by Vanderbilt University, and *AToMPM* by the University of Antwerpen, Montreal, Alabama, and McGill University. The open-source framework *Eclipse Graphical Language Server Platform (GSLP)* wasn't taken into consideration, because it doesn't feature a GUI for defining a domain-specific modeling method and is purely code-based on a metamodeling perspective. However, *Eclipse GLSP* features a GUI for modeling, based on the previously defined meta-model.

In the following sections, the author will introduce the metamodeling platforms individually and explore their respective approaches to implementing mechanisms and algorithms. Furthermore, the rating matrix of Section 5.1 will be applied, and the four metamodeling platforms will be evaluated.

5.2.1 ADOxx

The metamodeling platform ADOxx was developed at the University of Vienna in 1995 but was later transferred into the BOC Group (Fill et al., 2013). ADOxx emerged out of the development of a business process modeling toolkit called ADONIS and is now a commercially available product. However, academic licenses can be attained through the Open Models Laboratory (OMiLAB) (Fill and Karagiannis, 2013).

ADOxx allows the creation of modeling methods and standalone modeling toolkits, as many academic and commercial projects have proven (Fill et al., 2013). The ADOxx metamodeling platform consists of two main applications. First, the development toolkit, which allows a meta-modeler to define a domain-specific meta-model. Second, the modeling toolkit, that allows the modeler to use the previously defined meta-model and create models.

The meta-meta model of ADOxx is implemented in C++ by the developers at BOC Group, as shown in Figure 5.1, within the three-tier modeling hierarchy (Fill and Karagiannis, 2013). The ADOxx meta-model is an instance of that meta-meta model and was also developed by the developers of ADOxx. The ADOxx meta-model is developed using the ADOxx Library Language (ALL). Based upon the meta-model of ADOxx, the meta-modeler can derive his own domain-specific meta-model. The model, which the modeler creates in the *ADOxx modeling toolkit*, is then an instance of the meta-model created by the meta-modeler. The meta-modeler develops his meta-model using the *ADOxx Definition Language* (ADL).

The detailed meta-meta model of ADOxx, with all its components, is shown in Figure 5.2. The core constructs of the meta-meta model are *classes* as well as *relationclasses*, which are then assembled into *model types*. So-called *views* further restrict the available *classes* and *relationclasses* of a *model type*. In addition, *attributes* can be added to *classes*, which themselves can be detailed by *facets*. The concept of inheritance applies to *classes*, and thus a subclass will inherit all attributes of its super-class (Fill and Karagiannis, 2013).

A *relationclass* is specified by two attributes: the *from-class* and the *to-class*. These attributes define which classes can be connected to one another by what relationship.

Also, within the context of *from-classes* and *to-classes*, the inheritance of *classes* applies. Therefore, if the *from-class* or *to-class* is a super-class, all its subclasses can be connected to the respective end of the *relationclass* (Fill et al., 2013). The inheritance structure, the super-classes, and subclasses are chosen by the meta-modeler. Subsequently, any meta-model features a class hierarchy specified by the meta-modeler (Fill and Karagiannis, 2013).

Figure 5.1: Modeling Hierarchy of ADOxx with its roles and languages (Fill and Karagiannis, 2013, p. 6) Reprinted from "Enterprise Modelling Information Systems Architectures - International Journal of Conceptual Modelling", by Fill and Karagiannis (2013)

Figure 5.2: Meta-Meta Model of ADOxx (Fill and Karagiannis, 2013, p. 8) Reprinted from "Enterprise Modelling Information Systems Architectures - International Journal of Conceptual Modelling", by Fill and Karagiannis (2013)

There exist two basic types of *attributes*: the *class attribute* and the *instance attribute*. While the *class attribute* is the same for all instances, the *instance attribute* can hold distinct values for different instances (Kühn et al., 1999). An example of a *class attribute* is the graphical representation in the *GRAPHREP* or notebook definition in the *ATTRREP* attribute. Both the *GRAPHREP* as well as the *ATTRREP* are specified with an individual proprietary syntax. The *instance attribute* can be of type string, integer, float, double, time, date, enumeration (predefined values for the modeler to choose from), expression, and interref. An attribute of type expression holds strings that specify code for calculating values of an attribute automatically at runtime. The code of an expression has its own syntax and only returns one value. An interref links two instances of a *class*; it doesn't matter if they're contained within the same or another model instance or links an instance of a *class* to another model instance altogether (Fill et al., 2013).

The architecture of ADOxx uses a repository-based approach. The *application library*, with its sub-libraries, *static library* and *dynamic library*, contains all the developed classes, relations, model types, and views. If the meta-modeler wants to export and import data, the data format of choice for libraries is *.abl*, and for models *.adl*. The feature set of ADOxx is implemented on top of the CORE modeling sub-system as individual components. The CORE modeling sub-system itself is a database-drive client-server repository (Fill and Karagiannis, 2013). The Table 5.3 describes the available components of ADOxx and their respective functionality in detail.

As described in Table 5.3, ADOxx itself provides some mechanisms and algorithms that a modeler can use. The scope of the thesis at hand limits the analysis on domain-specific mechanisms and algorithms and, therefore, doesn't consider built-in simulation capabilities. However, some

components allow the meta-modeler to define such domain-specific mechanisms and algorithms. Therefore, the author will concentrate on the *external coupling* component for the analysis.

Component	Explanation
Acquisition	Retrieves data from external sources (e.g., spreadsheets) and provides this data as models (Fill and Karagiannis, 2013).
Modeling	The modeling component visualizes the models and makes the graphical model editor available. The model editor and visual representation are based on the specified meta-model of the modeling method. The modeling component is responsible for handling models (Fill and Karagiannis, 2013).
Analysis	The analysis component is responsible for the mechanisms in ADOxx. It allows the meta-modeler and modeler, respectively, the formulation and execution of static queries (Fill and Karagiannis, 2013).
Simulation	ADOxx features four algorithms for simulating models based on discrete-event simulation (see Section 3.3.3), which are available through the simulation component (Fill and Karagiannis, 2013).
Evaluation	The evaluation component allows for the comparison of data from simulations of the simulation component and external real-time data (Fill and Karagiannis, 2013).
Transformation	In ADOxx, we can transform models into other data formats that are utilized by CASE tools (e.g., MetaEdit+) (Fill and Karagiannis, 2013).
Process cost calculation	ADOxx allows the modeler to calculate the cost of a process. The result is based on the simulation of the process of the simulation component (Fill and Karagiannis, 2013).
Import/Export	The import/export component provides the functionality that allows a modeler to export or import files in XML and ADL. The import/export component works on all ADOxx-based meta-models (Fill and Karagiannis, 2013).
External coupling	The External Coupling component enables the meta-modeler to define and implement mechanisms and algorithms that are not treated by any other component (Fill and Karagiannis, 2013).
Document generation	The document generation component allows the modeler to generate HTML, RTF, or DOC format documents directly from models. The modeler can configure the document generation to his own requirements (Fill and Karagiannis, 2013).

Table 5.3: Components of ADOxx and their purpose

The *external coupling component* allows the meta-modeler to implement his own domain-specific mechanisms and algorithms. ADOxx provides the proprietary languages *AdoScript*, *GRAPHREP*, and *expressions* for doing so. With *AdoScript*, the meta-modeler can access information that is stored within the model (Fill and Karagiannis, 2013). For example, a specific value of a class instance attribute can be accessed and processed. The *expressions* are stored within an *expression* attribute and can retrieve, respectively calculate, a specific value automatically. The same goes for *GRAPHREP*, which is the visual representation and is stored in the class attribute *GRAPHREP*.

Please note that in every section of mechanisms and algorithms, the terms meta-modeler and developer are used as synonyms to improve readability and mutual understanding. The term developer is used since the meta-modeler has the role of a developer during the development of mechanisms and algorithms of a modeling method.

Mechanisms in ADOxx

In this section, the author introduces the two proprietary languages, *Expressions* and *GRAPHREP*. This section provides an overview of the concepts, syntax, and semantics of the respective languages.

Expressions

Expressions allow the developer to investigate and calculate information within a model or across multiple models. ADOxx distinguished three different types of expressions: *LeoExpression*, *CoreExpression*, and *AdoScriptExpression*. The foundation of all expressions form the *LeoExpressions*. They're compatible with all LEO languages and provide a set of operators and functions from which expressions can be built. Typically, they're used to manipulate strings or calculate values. The *CoreExpressions* build upon the set of functions and operators of the *LeoExpressions* and extend them specifically with ADOxx functionality. Within an expression, the developer can mix the *LeoExpression* and *CoreExpression* to his liking without any restrictions. The third type of expressions, the *AdoScriptExpressions*, are designed to be used within AdoScript code. They're also an extension of *LeoExpressions*, and the available functions and operators can be combined too.

Figure 5.3: Architecture of ADOxx (Fill and Karagiannis, 2013, p. 8) Reprinted from "Enterprise Modelling Information Systems Architectures - International Journal of Conceptual Modelling", by Fill and Karagiannis (2013)

Expressions are stored within an attribute of type *EXPRESSION*. Normally, an expression is a class attribute, but technically, it can also be a normal attribute where every instance can have different values. A second option for storing expressions is the implementation of them into the AdoScript code, which subsequently must comply with the storage location possibilities of AdoScript code.

The syntax of expressions follows a very simple approach. Every expression must start with *EXPR* and then be followed by the specification of the return type *type:returnType*. Then, the expression itself begins with *expr: ()*, and every function and operator is now defined within those brackets. It's important that the return value is always the last term within the brackets. Expressions can only return one value, with the type specified at the beginning. Listing 5.1 demonstrates a simple example of an expression that retrieves the value of an attribute and then returns it. The returned value can, for example, be displayed within the model using GRAPHREP.

```

1 EXPR type:double expr: (
2     #Store the value of the attribute "someDoubleAttribute" of the object, with
3     also this expression attribute, in the variable "returnValue"
4     set(returnValue, aval(someDoubleAttribute)),
5     #return the variable "returnValue"
    returnValue

```

Listing 5.1: Example of an ADOxx expression

An important difference to the AdoScript code is that the expressions, which are defined within a class, are executed automatically whenever something changes within the model. A change within a model can be a newly added class or relation, the deletion of a class or relation, a change of the position of a class or relation, or the change of an attribute of a class or relation. So, while the AdoScript has to be executed manually or specified to be executed by an event, expressions are always updated and hold the most recent value.

This automatic execution of mechanisms on any event allows the developer to implement additional constraints. At the same time, the meta-modeler can define a *from-class* and *to-class*, which might not cover all the possible cases. So, the meta-modeler can specify super-classes as the *from-class* and *to-class* and restrict the possible relations. Furthermore, the same principle applies to classes, e.g., how many instances of a class can be present on a model. The developer can implement additional domain-specific consistency checks, which are not covered by the built-in functionality of ADOxx.

GRAPHREP

The *GRAPHREP* attribute is always a class attribute. However, the visual appearance can differ between instances based on the defined mechanisms within the *GRAPHREP* code. Those mechanisms use a different syntax than expressions or AdoScript.

For the definition of the graphical representation, the meta-modeler can use a graphics-design web application that is hosted on the OMILAB Node of the University of Vienna. This application can also be run on-premise. The meta-modeler can use traditional shapes, fonts, or graphics and export the result as *GRAPHREP*-code.

The *GRAPHREP* code always starts with the call sign *GRAPHREP*, then follows with the shape elements. The developer can specify its color, shadow, shape, and text, display an attribute

value, or change the representation based on some conditional statements. The position of any element is specified with *X-coordinates* and *Y-coordinates*. A simple example of a blue arrow, which also displays the instance name, is shown below in Listing 5.2.

```

1 GRAPHREP
2 FILL color:blue
3 POLYGON 7 x1:1.5cm y1:0cm x2:0.5cm y2:-1cm x3:0.5cm y3:-0.5cm
4           x4:-1.5cm y4:-0.5cm x5:-1.5cm y5:0.5cm x6:0.5cm y6:0.5cm
5           x7:0.5cm y7:1cm
6 ATTR "Name" y:1.4cm w:c h:c

```

Listing 5.2: Example of a GRAPHREP arrow representation

Algorithms in ADOxx with AdoScript

AdoScript, as a procedural programming language, builds upon the functional programming language *LEO*. For accessing different functionalities like retrieving, processing, or modifying model data, AdoScript uses the internal instances of ADOxx, called *MessagePorts*, to group and stage functionality. Parts of one or multiple components will form a MessagePorts.

The internal instances obtain strings that hold component-specific commands. The messages that a component receives contain LEO code, and the received message is executed by the respective core component. The component does either execute an action on the model or data or returns a value. The returned value is then stored in a specific runtime variable. The input and output variables are specified for each MessagePort, and command and can't be altered by the developer.

AdoScript is a type-sensitive programming language.

Whenever an algorithm wants to access the functionality of a MessagePort, the algorithm has to send a *message* to that MessagePort with the appropriate command. To send a message, the developer must specify the sending of a message with *SEND* or *CC*. Normally, *CC* is preferred because it automatically assigns the return value to a runtime variable. After the indication of sending a message, the developer has to specify to which MessagePort he wants to send this LEO text. The MessagePort has to be in quotes. In addition to the MessagePort, the developer must specify which command he wants to execute from this MessagePort. The command itself has to be in capital letters. If the developer wants to set the MessagePort call into debug mode, he has to add the term *debug* between the MessagePort and the Command.

After the MessagePort and Command are specified, the developer has to specify the required input variables. The input variables must be of the exact type which is required for this Command. If the input variable is of a different type, the developer can change the variable type by type-casting.

```

1 CC "Core" debug GET_CONNECTOR objid: (anyObjID) in
2 CC "Core" debug GET_CONNECTOR objid: (anyObjID) out

```

Listing 5.3: Example for a MessagePort Command in AdoScript

The example code in Listing 5.3 retrieves all the object IDs of all relations that one specific object has. The object of desire has to be specified by the object ID, and it further has to be specified if the relations of interest are incoming or outgoing. If we want both, just as in the example, the developer has to specify two messages that retrieve the desired information. For this Command, the return value is a list of object IDs. Furthermore, the messages sent are in debug mode, which

means every part of the receiving, decoding, and executing on the side of the MessagePort prompts a pop-up within the modeling toolkit. This allows the developer to investigate if and in which part of the Command an error occurs.

Within AdoScript, the developer can assign local or global variables. For datatypes, the developer can choose between a string or a number. However, the choice of datatype occurs implicitly by assigning a value and not by actively specifying a datatype. If required, AdoScript provides conversion functionality between those two types.

For data structures, the developer has strings, lists, and arrays at his disposal. While the strings and lists are of dynamic length, the array length has to be specified in advance when invoking the array. Therefore, arrays are only suited where the number of entries is fixed and never depends on the size of the model. The lists provide the most flexibility for the developers and should be the first choice.

As with almost any other programming language, AdoScript enables the use of conditional statements, loops, and logical, arithmetical, and comparison operators. They allow the processing of the values of assigned variables and conditional processing procedures. In addition, they provide the flexibility to develop almost any domain-specific algorithm.

For improved modularity, reusability, and readability, AdoScript features procedures and functions. A procedure can be called with or without input parameters and will conduct some processing. However, a procedure will not return any value. The function can also be called with an input parameter but will return a specified value. In the example in Listing 5.4, we want to retrieve all outgoing relations of the selected object in our model. For demonstration purposes, the author divided this AdoScript code into a function and procedure. Theoretically, this code can be written as one function or procedure.

First, we need a return value for the object ID of our selected object, and we choose the FUNCTION as a control structure. Therefore, we retrieve the active model in which our object is placed and then get the object ID of the selected object. We can now further use that returned value in our code. The example for the procedure shows that we can call a function with input parameters. We can call the PROCEDURE for any object in our model and store its outgoing relations in a variable. We simply give the object ID of our object of interest, and the procedure stores the outgoing relations in the variable *result*. Important to note is that whenever the procedure is called, the previously stored relations are overwritten.

In addition to the code in AdoScript (MessagePorts, Commands, functions, procedures etc.), the developer can also use *expressions* within his AdoScript code, which subsequently enables the integration of queries. Expressions, and their syntax is introduced in Section 5.2.1. Furthermore, AdoScript enables the integration of mechanisms for laying out a model, positioning objects, or generating new views.

```

1 FUNCTION GET_ACTIVE_OBJECT {
2     #First we get the model ID in which the desired object is
3     CC "Modeling" GET_ACT_MODEL
4     #We then retrieve the object ID of the selected object in our model
5     return CC "Modeling" GET_SELECTED modelid
6 }
7
8 PROCEDURE GET_CONNECTED_OBJECTS integer: anyObjId {
9     #Get all connectors (relations) of the object with the specified ID
10    CC "Core" GET_CONNECTORS objid: (anyObjId) out
11    #Store the retrieved connectors in a global variable, so that the value can
12    also be accessed outside of the procedure
13    SETG result: (objids)
14 }

```

Listing 5.4: Example of an AdoScript function and procedure

The developer can store the AdoScript code either in a class attribute of type PROGRAMCALL, within an external AdoScript file, or within a menu entry. The choice of storage location influences the available triggers of the AdoScript code.

The AdoScript code can be triggered through events (e.g., on "AppInitialized", on start-up of the computer etc.), from the AdoScript shell, manually through a button in the menu or notebook of a class, or through a *Hotspot*. A *Hotspot* is like a hyperlink within the visual representation of a class. The developer has to specify the respective code and trigger in the dynamic sub-library.

Evaluation of ADOxx

For the evaluation of ADOxx, the author studied the existing research literature of Karagiannis and Kühn (2002), Fill and Karagiannis (2013), Fill et al. (2013), Karagiannis and Visic (2011) and Visic et al. (2015). In addition, the author examined the documentation of ADOxx and conducted direct testing within the tool in order to be able to rate the metamodeling platform accordingly. The justification of the points received for every characteristic is stated within the respective cell in Table 5.4. The analysis and evaluation of ADOxx was conducted on Windows 11 with version 1.5 of ADOxx.

Property/ Characteristic	Scale and Explanation
Functional completeness	2 Points: Integration of mechanisms and algorithms possible ADOxx allows the integration of mechanisms within the <i>GRAPHREP</i> and <i>EXPRESSION</i> attributes. Algorithms can be implemented using the AdoScript programming language within the <i>PROGRAMMCALL</i> attribute, external or internal file, or within a menu entry.
Capacity	3 Points: Unlimited lengths of code There's no documented limitation within the <i>EXPRESSION</i> attribute. Since, for more complex algorithms, the developer can integrate additional AdoScript files, a technical ADOxx capacity limitation for AdoScript doesn't exist.

Property/ Characteristic	Scale and Explanation
Resource utilisation	1 Point: Multi-Core/Multi-Thread ADOxx uses up to four threads. The analysis was conducted on a 16-thread CPU (x86).
User error protection	1 Point: Limited error protection ADOxx itself doesn't provide any user protection in regard to Expressions, GRAPHREP, or AdoScript. However, there exist plug-ins for Integrated Development Environments (IDE) like Visual Studio Code, which highlights AdoScript, AQL, ALL, GRAPHREP, and EXPRESSION syntax and provides bracket matching. For AdoScript, the plug-in features auto-complete for MessagePorts, Commands, and invoked variables.
Learnability	2 Points: High effort, research in documentation required ADOxx introduces three new programming languages. The GRAPHREP, Expressions, and AdoScript are proprietary languages. Even though the Expressions are LEO-based, the meta-modeler has to give additional effort to learn the ADOxx-specific treats.
Documentation	2 Points: Extensive documentation available ADOxx provides very extensive documentation. Everything, down to every AdoScript Command and Expression, is documented with an example.
Reusability	2 Points: Limited reusability ADOxx allows the reuse of AdoScript code through procedures and functions. In addition, the developer can integrate external resources. Expressions or GRAPHREP can't be reused.
Testability	2 Points: Hard & fast ADOxx allows testing AdoScript code and expressions through the shell and notebook. However, the developer must develop the code completely and only then can execute the code. Dedicated testing features of Expressions and AdoScript are not provided. For the GRAPHREP, on the other hand, does exist an immediate graphical response for the developed code.
Installability	3 Points: Three platforms supported ADOxx is only available for the x86 platform. For Windows, the versions <i>Windows XP, Vista, 7, 8, 8.1, 10, and 11</i> are supported. Furthermore, ADOxx provides an experimental version for macOS <i>Mojave (10.14.3)</i> and Linux. For Linux, the distributions <i>Ubuntu (18.04, 18.10)</i> and <i>Fedora (28, 29)</i> are supported.

Property/ Characteristic	Scale and Explanation
Usefulness (Pro-grammers)	3 Points: Very satisfied A technical person is very satisfied with the approach chosen for implementing mechanisms and algorithms. GRAPHREP, expressions, and AdoScript are all code-based and provide (almost) no graphical alternative.
Usefulness (non-technical people)	0 Points: Not satisfied All mechanisms and algorithms are implemented with code. Only the GRAPHREP does provide a graphical tool for defining the GRAPHREP. However, the GRAPHREP tool is not included within the ADOxx tool suite and must be accessed via the internet.
Context completeness	3 Points: High completeness With ADOxx, the meta-modeler and modeler can achieve all their tasks within their context of use.
Flexibility	2 Points: Average flexibility Use cases like AR and VR are not possible with ADOxx; however, ADOxx provides a very versatile toolset that allows the use of the platform in multiple different domains and use cases.

Table 5.4: Rating matrix: ADOxx rated

ADOxx achieves a total of **24** points. The different properties are not weighted and count similarly.

As we can see in Table 5.5, ADOxx provides all the necessary functionality, which is demanded by Karagiannis and Visic (2011).

Feature	Description
Language Definition Approach	Form-based approach.
Specifying Notation	Hybrid approach. Notation can be defined using a combination of graphical and textual elements.
Syntax Highlighting and Debugging	No support for highlighting, auto-completing or debugging within the metamodeling toolkit.
Scripting	Scripting support for advanced customizing provided.
Import and Export	Import and export of meta-models and models with the component <i>Import/Export</i> .
Integration with Other Tools	APIs, Client-Side, and Server-Side Integration possible with AdoScript.

Feature	Description
Rich Notation	More than simple symbols for nodes and arcs. Graphical notation almost unbounded.
Dynamic Symbol Change	Symbols change dynamically when model data changes by implementing mechanisms within GRAPHREP.
Different Modeling Views	Modeling, matrix, and tabular view possible.

Table 5.5: List of features for ADOxx (Karagiannis and Visic, 2011, p. 25). Adapted from *Perspectives in Business Informatics Research* (p. 25), by Karagiannis and Visic (2011) Springer.

5.2.2 MetaEdit+

The description of MetaEdit+ is based on the literature by Kelly et al. (1996) and Kern (2016), and the documentation of the tool itself. Furthermore, the author conducted testing within MetaEdit+.

MetaEdit+ is an environment for *Computer Aided Software Engineering (CASE)* and *Computer Aided Method Engineering (CAME)*. It was developed by MetaCase in 1995 and provides extensive multi-user and multi-tool support. MetaEdit+ builds upon the existing metaCASE environment and therefore integrates the same architectural principles as object orientation, layered database architecture, and conceptual modeling (Kelly et al., 1996). MetaEdit+ consists of two main components: the *MetaEdit+ Workbench* and *MetaEdit+ Modeler*. The *MetaEdit+ Workbench* is used for the definition of meta-models, respectively, for modeling methods. The *MetaEdit+ Modeler* is used for the modeling functionality, which incorporates the meta-model that the meta-modeler defined in the *MetaEdit+ Workbench*.

MetaEdit+ implements the *Graph Object Properties Relationships Roles (GOPRR)* conceptual data model (Kelly et al., 1996), which equals the meta-meta model of MetaEdit+ in Figure 5.4 (Kern, 2016). The GOPRR of MetaEdit+ is based on the OPRR conceptual model and extends the concept of the *Graph* (Kelly et al., 1996).

The *Graph* represents the canvas of MetaEdit+. Multiple *Graphs* are grouped and defined in a *Graph Type*. Multiple representational *Graphs* can be attached to one underlying conceptual *Graph*. Therefore, multiple canvases can represent the same *Graph* from different points of view (Kelly et al., 1996).

In addition, the *Graph Type* contains *relationship types* and *object types*. A class of *Objects* is defined by the *Object Type* (Kern, 2016). An *Object* is an individual element on the canvas (e.g., a task within a BPMN 2.0 model) and is normally represented as a graphical object on the canvas (Kelly et al., 1996). The connection between multiple *Objects* is achieved by *relationships* (Kern, 2016). This association between *objects* is normally represented as lines between the respective graphical objects on the canvas, e.g., the sequence flow between tasks in a BPMN 2.0 diagram. An alternative representation of the relationship is text (Kelly et al., 1996).

The *relationship* itself is defined by *bindings*, which contain the *relationship type*, *role types*, *port types* and *object types*. While the *role type* defines the role of objects in the relationship, the *port type* defines which objects can take part in that relationship. In other words, the *port type*

restricts the connections to a subset that is possible (Kern, 2016). Every *Graph* can contain only a subset of all available objects of an underlying *conceptual graph* (Kelly et al., 1996).

Every previously introduced element can have *properties*, which is a characteristic of an element and equal to an attribute in almost any other metamodeling platform (Kern, 2016). A *property* is a single value entry, and they're only accessible through *objects* and *relationships* (Kelly et al., 1996). The *property* is either a well-known datatype (e.g., Integer, Boolean, String) or a reference to another element (e.g., another object) (Kern, 2016).

MetaEdit+ supports the inheritance of *properties* and constraints (e.g., *port types*) (Kern, 2016). Furthermore, the meta-model uses generalization and specialization to reuse elements and organize libraries (Kelly et al., 1996).

MetaEdit+ is based on the MetaEngine. The MetaEngine is responsible for the interaction with the underlying data model. Every tool within MetaEdit+ doesn't interact directly with the data but must request the operation from the MetaEngine, which subsequently executes the respective operation. This division of responsibility streamlines the code of the MetaEdit+ tools since the code for manipulating data isn't copied into every tool, and it also enables fast implementation of new tools (Kelly et al., 1996).

A tool within MetaEdit+ is an individual view with different functionalities. A tool enables the user a specific representation (e.g., statistical graph, matrix etc.), and some tools allow the user the manipulation of elements. Tools don't exchange information with each other directly but always over the MetaEngine. The MetaEngine is, therefore, also responsible for propagating changes to all tools (Kelly et al., 1996).

Figure 5.4: Meta-Meta Model of MetaEdit+ (Kern, 2016, p. 69) Reprinted from "Model Interoperability between metamodeling Environments by using M3-Level-Based Bridges", by Kern (2016)

There are 5 different families of tools available in MetaEdit+. First, the *Environment management tools*, which manage the environment and its component, and launch the environment. Second, the *Model editing tools*, which create, modify, and delete all element instances and models. Third, the *Model retrieval tools*, which retrieve objects and instances from the central repository. Fourth, the *Model linking and annotation tools*, which link objects, annotate model instances, and find elements in the design space. Finally, the *Method management tools*, which are used for method specification, method management, and method retrieval (Kelly et al., 1996).

Figure 5.5: Architecture of MetaEdit+ (Kelly et al., 1996, p. 121) Reprinted from "Advanced Information Systems Engineering", by Kelly et al. (1996)

MetaEdit+ can run on a single machine for only one user or on a central server. If the server version is chosen, the data is stored on the central repository, and multiple MetaEngines instances, exactly one per client, are connected to the central repository over the network. The repository holds all data of the models, meta-model users, and the respective locks (Kelly et al., 1996).

In order to ensure that only one user modifies a given set of data, MetaEdit+ uses pessimistic concurrency control. That means that a user locks some data and then modifies it. The changed data is then propagated to all other clients. However, it's not the user that requests that lock, but the MetaEngine that does that for the user since it's faster, more accurate, and more convenient. MetaEdit+ uses multiple levels of granularity for the locks and distinguishes between locks in meta-models, conceptual objects, representation data, and graphs (Kelly et al., 1996).

Mechanisms

MetaEdit+ provides two different types of mechanisms. The mechanisms in the *visual representation* and the *constraints*. Each concept is discussed individually in this section.

Visual representation

Just as in ADOxx, MetaEdit+ allows the change of the visual representation depending on a property value. The meta-modeler has to specify the visual representation for all cases within the *Symbol Editor*, or more specifically, the meta-modeler can specify which parts of the visual representation shall be visible under which circumstances.

MetaEdit+ will then dynamically evaluate the value of the respective property and adjust its visual representation to the previously specified version. This dynamical change of the visual representation is code-free and is defined entirely by properties and the visual representation within

the *Symbol Editor*. The change in the visual representation doesn't modify any data.

Constraints

Constraints are defined through the meta-modeler in Meta-Edit+ within the meta-model *graph tool*. The meta-modeler can define four categories of *constraints* through the GUI. First, the *connectivity constraint* where the meta-modeler can define which objects can be part of how many relationships or roles (e.g., A BPMN 2.0 *Start-object* can be at most in one *Sequence flow-relationship*). Second, the *Occurence constraint*, which limits the number of instances of an object, can be in a graph (e.g., The BPMN 2.0 *Start-object* can have at most one instance). Third, the *Port constraint* where the meta-modeler can define if all ports of an instance of any element must have the same or different value for a specific property (e.g., All ports of all BPMN 2.0 *Start-objects* must have the same value for the "*anyProperty*" property) . Finally, the *Uniqueness constraint*, with which the meta-modeler can specify which property of an object must have a unique value within each instance (e.g., a unique ID for all BPMN 2.0 *Start-objects*).

All the constraints that are specified are listed in a textual representation. The meta-modeler can gain immediate insight into which constraints are currently applied to the meta-model. The meta-modeler can add, modify, or delete constraints.

Algorithms

In MetaEdit+, algorithms are implemented either through *generators* or the MetaEdit+ API. This section introduces both concepts in detail.

Generators

The developer can specify *generators* in MetaEdit+ with the *MetaEdit+ Reporting Language (MERL)*. A *generator* is assigned to a *graph type* and, therefore, also to all its individual *graphs*. The task of a *generator* is to traverse the model structure, extract the information needed, and output the information in a specific syntax or form. The output is either an in-application window or an external file. In addition to the textual data, which can be extracted, the developer can also export diagrams or execute outside third-party applications.

Generators also enable the developer to check for consistency within a model, generate domain-specific code, or simulate the model. Listing 5.5 shows a generic skeleton of a *Generator* in MERL. Important to note is that *SomeObject*, *SomeRelation*, and *SomeOtherObject* must be defined in the meta-model. The *generator* can only work on elements which are defined in the meta-model and must use the same terminology. The detailed syntax of MERL can be found within the documentation of MetaEdit+ and isn't provided in the thesis at hand.

```
1 foreach .SomeObject{
2     do >SomeRelation.SomeOtherObject {
3         #Here the developer adds the functionality the generator shall have (e.g.,
4         transform the model into Java-Code)
5     }
}
```

Listing 5.5: Example of a MetaEdit+ Generator

The *generator* can be implemented either directly with code in the *Generator editor* or through the guidance of the *Generator editor*. The *Generator editor* provides the developer with all available elements and guides the developer to bring them into order in an interactive way. However, the logic itself and the syntax of MERL must be understood by the developer either way.

MetaEdit+ integrates strong debugging capabilities. The developer can set break-points directly in the *Generator debugger* and traverse the *Generator* step by step. The developer can develop, execute, and inspect the code and its immediate output directly in MetaEdit+ without using an external IDE.

A *Generator* is applied to a model through the *graph editor*. Within the *graph editor*, the modeler can choose one or more generators, which were mapped onto the *graph types* of the current model.

MetaEdit+ API

MetaEdit+ allows the integration of outside resources through a *Simple Object Access Protocol-Interface (SOAP)*. Through SOAP calls, the data within MetaEdit+ can be processed through third-party applications. MetaEdit+ provides guidelines for the integration of the API for Java, C#, and C/C++. However, since MetaEdit+ is called through the SOAP API, it can be integrated using any programming language, as long as the API specifications are met.

After the outside processing, MetaEdit+ allows for the reintegration of the data through the same API.

Evaluation of MetaEdit+

For the evaluation of MetaEdit+, the author studied the existing research literature of Kelly et al. (1996), Kelly and Tolvanen (2021), and Kern (2016). In addition, the author studied the documentation of MetaEdit+ and conducted direct testing within the tool in order to be able to rate the metamodeling platform accordingly. The justification of the points received for every characteristic is stated within the respective cell in Table 5.6. The analysis and evaluation of the platform was conducted on Windows 11 with version 5.5 of MetaEdit+.

Property/ Characteristic	Scale and Explanation
Functional completeness	2 Points: Integration of mechanisms and algorithms possible MetaEdit+ allows the integration of mechanisms with the <i>visual representation</i> and <i>constraints</i> . Algorithms can be implemented using the MetaEdit+ API or <i>Generators</i> .
Capacity	3 Points: Unlimited lengths of code There's no documented limitation for constraints, generators, or the MetaEdit+ API. However, a single constraint is limited to one single guardrail, but the number of constraints isn't limited.
Resource utilisation	1 Point: Multi-Core/Multi-Thread MetaEdit+ uses up to six threads. The analysis was conducted on a 16-thread CPU (x86).

Property/ Characteristic	Scale and Explanation
User error protection	<p>1 Point: Limited error protection</p> <p>MetaEdit+ provides user error protection for constraints and visual representation by only providing the possible options within the dropdown menus. The MetaEdit+ API doesn't provide any user protection apart from error protection within the IDEs for the used programming language. For the generators, MetaEdit+ provides limited user error protection through the interactive definition of generators.</p>
Learnability	<p>2 Points: High effort, research in documentation required</p> <p>For the correct specification of generators and the use of the MetaEdit+ API, extensive research is required. The meta-modeler learns intuitively to define constraints and visual representation.</p>
Documentation	<p>2 Points: Extensive documentation available</p> <p>MetaEdit+ provides very extensive documentation, examples, and tutorials.</p>
Reusability	<p>1 Point: Single-format reusability</p> <p>MetaEdit+ allows the reuse of third-party applications through the MetaEdit+ API. The generators, constraints, and the visual representation are meta-model specific.</p>
Testability	<p>2 Points: Hard & fast</p> <p>MetaEdit+ allows to test and debug generators. The code for the MetaEdit+ API can't be tested in MetaEdit+. The visual representation is directly presented to the meta-modeler in the symbol editor. The constraints are tested by directly applying the constraints to the model.</p>
Installability	<p>2 Points: Two platforms supported</p> <p>MetaEdit+ is only available for the x86 platform. For Windows, the versions <i>Windows 7, 8.1, 10, 11, Server 2008, Server 2012, and Server 2016</i> are supported. For Linux, the distribution <i>Ubuntu (14 - 18.04)</i> is supported.</p>
Usefulness (Pro-grammers)	<p>3 Points: Very satisfied</p> <p>A technical person is very satisfied with the approach chosen for implementing mechanisms and algorithms. The generators and the MetaEdit+ API are integrated by code. The constraints and visual representation are defined through a GUI.</p>
Usefulness (non-technical people)	<p>2 Points: Satisfied</p> <p>The MetaEdit+ API can't be integrated by non-technical people. However, a generator can be implemented partially by a GUI. The constraints and visual representation can only be integrated by a GUI.</p>

Property/ Characteristic	Scale and Explanation
Context completeness	3 Points: High completeness With MetaEdit+, the meta-modeler and modeler can achieve all their tasks within their context of use.
Flexibility	2 Points: Average flexibility Use cases like AR and VR are not possible with MetaEdit+; however, MetaEdit+ provides a very versatile toolset that allows the integration of outside resources. In combination with third-party applications, additional use cases can be integrated.

Table 5.6: Rating matrix: MetaEdit+ rated

MetaEdit+ achieves a total of **24** points. The different properties are not weighted and count similarly.

MetaEdit+ provides all features which are defined by Karagiannis and Visic (2011) as Table 5.7 demonstrates.

Feature	Description
Language Definition Approach	Form-based approach.
Specifying Notation	Graphical approach. Notation is defined primarily using graphical elements.
Syntax Highlighting and Debugging	Support for highlighting, auto-completing or debugging within the metamodeling toolkit for a subset of mechanisms and algorithms.
Scripting	Scripting support for advanced customizing provided.
Import and Export	Import and export of meta-models and models from/for other CASE tools possible.
Integration with Other Tools	APIs, Client-Side, Server-Side Integration possible with algorithms.
Rich Notation	More than simple symbols for nodes and arcs. Graphical notation almost unbounded.
Dynamic Symbol Change	Symbols change dynamically when model data changes by implementing mechanisms within the graphical notation.
Different Modeling Views	Modeling, matrix, tabular view possible.

Table 5.7: List of features for MetaEdit+ (Karagiannis and Visic, 2011, p. 25). Adapted from *Perspectives in Business Informatics Research* (p. 25), by Karagiannis and Visic (2011) Springer.

5.2.3 WebGME

The description and evaluation of WebGME was conducted by the author through the analysis of the available literature by Maróti et al. (2014) and the tool itself.

WebGME is a web-based, cloud-hosted, Generic Modeling Environment (GME). WebGME builds upon the desktop version of the GME, which was originally developed for single-user use and up to medium-sized models and extends it with its scalable and multi-user concepts (Maróti et al., 2014). Within this section, the terms *model* and *object* are used as synonyms since, in the context of WebGME, they're considered interchangeable and similar.

WebGME doesn't use the traditional approach of inheritance, where every model is an instance of a meta-model, but uses the prototypical inheritance approach, where every instance can have instances. That means that every "model" is some sort of meta-model, or more precisely, a classical meta-model doesn't exist anymore. The different (meta-)models inherit properties from each other, which are propagated by change. However, while properties can be added anywhere in the inheritance tree, the inherited properties can never be restricted. This approach blurs the line between metamodeling and modeling in the traditional approach (Maróti et al., 2014).

The meta-model of WebGME uses a single composition hierarchy, where every model and object is contained by the object *FCO*, which itself is contained by the object *Root*. All meta-models and models, respectively, are contained in a project. Relations between objects are achieved with *sets* and *pointers*. While the *pointer* specifies its name and the possible endpoints, the *set* restricts the valid targets to an object within the *pointer* list. All *pointer-relations* can be displayed as connections between two objects. Other than the representation, a relation is also a model, as any other object is and is not included in the meta-meta model. A *set* is a number of *pointers* and is specified the same way as *pointers* (Maróti et al., 2014).

Further, WebGME supports *attributes* in its meta-meta model. Any property of an object and, therefore, a model, respectively, is defined by an *attribute*. The default supported data-types are *Integer*, *Float*, *Enumeration*, and *String*. However, the user can extend the available data-types within his project (Maróti et al., 2014).

An *aspect*, also known as a *view*, represents a subset of the children of a model. By default, each model has its primary *aspect*, which includes all of its children. Multiple *views* allow for better management of the complexity of models and their children. An additional concept for managing the complexity of a model is the *crosscut*. Crosscuts allow a modeler to choose a subset of objects in the default context of *Root* and display them together. The user can choose the respective objects with a query language or manually by drag and drop. If the modeler deletes an object from a *crosscut* view, the object itself isn't deleted completely but only removed from the respective *crosscut* view (Maróti et al., 2014).

Typically, a *crosscut* is used for metamodeling since it allows the combination of existing models. For that, the

Figure 5.6: State-Machine Meta-Model in WebGME (Maróti et al., 2014, p. 6) Reprinted from "CEUR Workshop Proceedings", by Maróti et al. (2014)

meta-modeler adds all the relevant models onto the *crosscut*, which are needed for the definition of the modeling language. In Figure 5.6, Maróti et al. (2014) demonstrate the use of a *crosscut* for the meta-model of a state machine. The inheritance relation between the *FCO* and the *transition* and *state* are created automatically since all objects are children of the *FCO*. The inheritance relation can't be modified, but all the other relations, which are achieved by *pointers* and *sets*, can (Maróti et al., 2014).

As mentioned before, WebGME has built-in multi-user support. The developers of WebGME achieve the consistency of the models across multiple clients through the commit principle like it's applied by Git. Every version of the state of the models is stored as a hash value. Whenever a user modifies a model, a new hash version is calculated. If the user wants to distribute his changes, he can commit to the central repository. His changes are granted and distributed to all users if the previous hash value of his change corresponds to the newest hash value on the repository. It may differ if another user has already pushed a change. If the values don't match, the changes are denied, and the newest version of the models is displayed. This approach also shows the asynchronous approach to data synchronicity. The browser downloads only the necessary data and performs its activities locally. The browser interacts with the server again when synchronizing. Therefore, the user can work offline as long as all the necessary data is downloaded first (Maróti et al., 2014).

Changes to an object never occur on the object itself, but rather, a new copy is created with the changes applied. Since the inheritance uses a reference to all children elements, this process occurs recursively to all parent objects for any change. Because every element stores only the *attributes* that differ from its parent object, the database operations can be limited to a small subset. This is in accordance with downloading only the necessary data to work on. If all *attributes* are stored in every element, then the browser must download the entire project repository, which in return would increase local storage capacity requirements and transfer rate requirements and decrease overall performance (Maróti et al., 2014).

Figure 5.7: Architecture of WebGME (Maróti et al., 2014, p. 13) Reprinted from "CEUR Workshop Proceedings", by Maróti et al. (2014)

WebGME is a single-page web application based on JavaScript and is running on a Node.JS process. As a database, the developers opted for the MongoDB. The high-level architecture with its most important components is illustrated in Figure 5.7. The *core* and *client* components provide the *Model API* and the data access. The *Model API* is the basis for all components on a higher level, e.g., the visualization. The visualization is implemented in JavaScript. JavaScript must always be used if an extension is developed for the client side as well as for the server side, with the exception of Plug-ins (Maróti et al., 2014).

The interface between the browser and the server-side applications is achieved by a REST-API. The import and export of models is achieved by the standard data format JSON since this allows for a seamless integration with the REST API (Maróti et al., 2014).

Since WebGME supports multi-user use, the server-side components implement the authorization and authentication tasks, which are based on the *Passport framework* (Maróti et al., 2014).

WebGME implements multiple different model interpreters and model transformations. In the following two sections, the available features are classified into mechanisms and algorithms. In addition, all functionalities are introduced in more detail. However, since all model interpreters and model transformations employ JavaScript code, the syntax isn't treated.

Mechanisms

WebGME supports two kinds of mechanisms which are introduced individually.

Add-on

WebGME supports different kinds of mechanisms. One of them is the *Add-ons*. They're extensions of WebGME, which run on the server side. *Add-ons* run constantly while a user is working on a project tree. They're set off by changes within the project and access the WebGME APIs, excluding the project API. Add-ons can't be implemented by the meta-modeler but rather by the developer of WebGME.

Webhook

A second type of mechanism is a *Webhook*, which work the same way as *Add-ons* but can send events to external servers. The trigger for a *webhook* is an internal event in WebGME (e.g., a change in the project tree). So *webhooks* don't access internal APIs like *Add-ons* but external resources.

Algorithms

WebGME supports three kinds of algorithms which are introduced individually.

Constraint

One type of algorithm in WebGME is the *constraint*, which are defined in a meta-type and allow the developer to assign a custom JavaScript function. The JavaScript function for a constraint is a combination of predefined API calls and non-platform-specific code like loops or conditional statements.

For example, the developer can constrain the type of name to which an element can be assigned (e.g., only lower cases) or define a relation cardinality. The function that is defined in the custom constraint is only executed on demand and not automatically. When the meta-modeler wants to check if all meta-rules are satisfied, he executes a rule-checking only for one specific constraint or for all specified constraints within the project. The demand for rule-checking is always applied to the entire project tree starting from the current node or to the entire project tree starting from the *Root*. However, it can't be isolated for only an aspect or crosscut (Maróti et al., 2014; Vanderbilt University, 2017).

iCore

WebGME uses *iCore* as a visualizer for editing and executing code. *iCore* enables a developer to build familiarity with the available APIs because it uses the same APIs as *Plug-ins*. *iCore* is an

ideal way to introduce the developer to the development process of *Plug-ins* since he can profit from extensive documentation and immediate feedback. However, *iCore* is only considered as an educational application within WebGME and isn't recommended for large projects due to performance limitations.

Plug-in

WebGME uses *Plug-ins* for domain-specific algorithms. The developer can implement his own *Plug-ins* in WebGME, which are executed on demand by the (meta-)modeler. The *Plug-in* can be used for interpreting, building, and querying models. The developer of the *Plug-in* and administrator of the WebGME environment can decide on their own if the *Plug-in* shall run on the client-side (browser) or server-side. Any custom *Plug-in* has access to the invoked context and the available APIs. With a *Plug-in*, the developer can traverse the project tree, retrieve information of the model, and export that information in the desired format. For example, the developer can implement a *Plug-in* that transforms his model into a specific programming language, or he can develop the token game of a Petri Net.

A *Plug-in* isn't bound to only JavaScript but can also be developed in other programming languages like Python. However, for both, the developer must use the WebGME *Plug-in Template*, which integrates the necessary dependencies and specifications. For a JavaScript-based *Plug-in*, it further integrates the new *Plug-in* into the built-in testing framework of WebGME, which is built on the *Mocha* test suite. However, the developer must write the necessary tests for his *Plug-in* himself. For the Python-based *Plug-ins*, the WebGME template provides all the necessary files and integrates them directly into a JavaScript callable script. A limiting factor for Python *Plug-ins* is the fact that they can only run on the server side.

The created *Plug-in* can now be extended with the domain-specific logic. After implementing said logic, the meta-modeler must assign the *Plug-in* to the appropriate element. Because of the inheritance strategy of WebGME, we must assign the *Plug-in* to the highest-ranked element we want to include in our processing. The processing starts at the assigned element and traverses down the project tree (Vanderbilt University, 2017).

Another use case for a *Plug-in* is the triggering of an external third-party application. This enables the integration of powerful analysis tool suites without the need to integrate the mathematical analysis function into the *Plug-in*. WebGME uses Node.js child processes and the *WebGME executor framework* in order to achieve this outsourcing of the analysis. The *Plug-in* then calls the external application and provides it with the necessary input data. Therefore, it might be required that the *Plug-in* first has to traverse the project tree and retrieve some data. Then, the analysis tool executes its operations upon the received dataset and returns some sort of result. The *Plug-in* is then once again responsible for displaying that result to the user. Important to note is that *Plug-ins* that call an external application only work on the server side and can't be implemented on the browser. Therefore, the server must have the appropriate third-party applications installed.

During runtime, a *Plug-in* can send notifications to the user about the current state of the transformation/simulation. The results of the *Plug-in* can be stored within the model itself, or the results can be downloaded by the user. The downloadable results have the advantage that the user can profit from third-party applications that help display a specific set of data. Alternatively, the results can be viewed within the WebGME GUI.

Evaluation of WebGME

For the evaluation of WebGME, the author conducted an in-depth analysis of the online application, the available source code, the documentation, and the white paper by Maróti et al. (2014). The justification of the points received for every characteristic is stated within the respective cell in Table 5.8.

Property/ Characteristic	Scale and Explanation
Functional completeness	2 Points: Integration of mechanisms and algorithms possible WebGME allows the integration of mechanisms with <i>Add-ons</i> and <i>Webhooks</i> . Algorithms can be implemented using <i>Constraints</i> and <i>Plug-ins</i> .
Capacity	3 Points: Unlimited lengths of code There's no documented limitation for <i>Plug-ins</i> , <i>Constraints</i> , <i>Add-ons</i> , <i>Webhooks</i> or <i>iCore</i> -Projects. However, <i>iCore</i> isn't recommended for large projects due to performance reasons.
Resource utilisation	1 Point: Multi-Core/Multi-Thread WebGME is a server-based application. Its scalability is achieved by spawning new child processes. Therefore, WebGME uses multiple cores/threads on the server side and features a high performance as long as the internet connection is sufficient.
User error protection	2 Points: Extensive error protection WebGME itself does provide user protection for <i>Constraints</i> and <i>Plug-ins</i> within <i>iCore</i> projects. There, the user can profit from auto-complete and syntax highlighting. In addition, all mechanisms and algorithms can be developed in any IDE. Since all mechanisms and algorithms are JavaScript-based, the user profits from auto-complete, bracket matching, syntax highlighting etc. from the IDE itself.
Learnability	4 Points: Low effort, intuitive learning WebGME uses JavaScript for any mechanism or algorithm. The WebGME-specific APIs are well documented and are intuitive to use for a developer who is familiar with JavaScript.
Documentation	2 Points: Extensive documentation available WebGME provides very extensive documentation. Everything, down to every API, is documented. In addition, WebGME provides a full text and video tutorial for developing mechanisms and algorithms.
Reusability	3 Points: Highly reusable WebGME allows the combination of <i>Plug-ins</i> and therefore the reuse of existing code. External resources can be accessed through <i>Webhooks</i> .

Property/ Characteristic	Scale and Explanation
Testability	3 Points: Easy & fast <i>iCore</i> , as well as the IDEs, allow for a quick way to compile the JavaScript code. In addition, the debugging with breakpoints allows for easier problem identification. Furthermore, the integration of <i>Plugins</i> in the test framework <i>mocha</i> allows for automated testing.
Installability	4 Points: Four platforms supported WebGME is a web application. Therefore, all operating systems (Windows, macOS, Linux) and technologies (x86, ARM) are supported.
Usefulness (Programmers)	3 Points: Very satisfied WebGME uses only code-based implementation of mechanisms and algorithms. Therefore, a technical person is very satisfied with the approach chosen.
Usefulness (non-technical people)	0 Points: Not satisfied All mechanisms and algorithms are implemented with code. The developer of a mechanism or algorithm must have an in-depth knowledge of JavaScript.
Context completeness	3 Points: High completeness With WebGME, the meta-modeler and modeler can achieve all their tasks within their context of use.
Flexibility	2 Points: Average flexibility Use cases like AR and VR are not possible with WebGME; however, WebGME provides a very versatile tool set that allows the use of the platform in multiple different domains and use cases. The combination of metamodeling and modeling and that we can't distinguish anymore enables interesting opportunities.

Table 5.8: Rating matrix: WebGME rated

WebGME achieves a total of **30** points. The different properties are not weighted and count similarly.

Table 5.9 shows that the demanded functionality by Karagiannis and Visic (2011) is provided by WebGME in some form.

Feature	Description
Language Definition Approach	Graphical approach.
Specifying Notation	Graphical approach. Notation is defined primarily using graphical elements.

Feature	Description
Syntax Highlighting and Debugging	Support for highlighting and debugging within the meta-modeling toolkit for algorithms.
Scripting	Scripting support for advanced customizing provided.
Import and Export	Import and export of meta-models and models possible. Data format only for WebGME instances.
Integration with Other Tools	APIs, Client-Side, Server-Side Integration possible with algorithms.
Rich Notation	More than simple symbols for nodes and arcs. Graphical notation not as extensive as in MetaEdit+ or ADOxx.
Dynamic Symbol Change	Symbols change dynamically when model data changes by implementing mechanisms.
Different Modeling Views	Modeling, matrix, tabular view possible.

Table 5.9: List of features for WebGME (Karagiannis and Visic, 2011, p. 25). Adapted from *Perspectives in Business Informatics Research* (p. 25), by Karagiannis and Visic (2011) Springer.

5.2.4 AToMPM

The description and evaluation of AToMPM was conducted by the author through the analysis of the available literature of Corley et al. (2016), Syriani et al. (2013), Syriani and Vangheluwe (2013), and Corley and Syriani (2014), and through in-depth testing within the tool itself.

A Tool for Multi-Paradigm Modeling (AToMPM) is an open-source web-based domain-specific metamodeling platform that was developed by researchers from the University of Alabama (USA), the University of Antwerp (Belgium), the University of Montreal (Canada), and the McGill University (Canada). It is the advancement of *A Tool for Multi-formalism and Metamodeling (AToM)* (Syriani et al., 2013).

A meta-model and model can be created either graphically on a canvas or through text commands. Both approaches offer the same set of functionalities, but the textual command might be preferred by code-experienced meta-modelers since they're more suited for manipulations on a greater set of elements (Syriani et al., 2013). Per default, AToMPM enables the editing of models, the generation of modeling languages, the definition of abstract and concrete syntax, as well as the execution of model transformations (Corley and Syriani, 2014).

The meta-model is defined using UML class diagrams per default. However, the meta-modeler can also define his own modeling method for defining another meta-model as long as the meta-modeler provides a mapping to the default meta-model. AToMPM distinguished between the abstract and concrete syntax of a model. While the abstract syntax represents the data itself (e.g., an element instance with some attribute values), the concrete syntax is a model that displays that data in some way. Multiple concrete syntaxes and multiple models can be linked to the same abstract syntax. This enables the users to better manage the overall complexity, and they can illustrate the same domain differently (Syriani et al., 2013).

The web application allows multiple users to collaborate on the same metamodeling platform. While they share the same modeling artifacts, each user can work on a different view of the available models. AToMPM allows for the collaboration of multiple users on the same canvas or collaboration on the abstract syntax of a model, where each user has a different concrete view of the same abstract model (Syriani et al., 2013). Every view has a specific toolbar attached to it through the concrete syntax of the abstract model (Corley and Syriani, 2014). Syriani et al. provide the example that a user can change the value of an element, which subsequently might change a color for one user and a value displayed for another user (Syriani et al., 2013).

Figure 5.8: Generic Architecture of AToMPM (Syriani et al., 2013, p. 4) Reprinted from "ACM/IEEE International Conference on Model Driven Engineering Languages and Systems", by Syriani et al. (2013)

Figure 5.9: High level concrete architecture of AToMPM (Corley and Syriani, 2014, p. 2) Reprinted from "Joint Proceedings of MODELS 2014 Poster Session and the ACM Student Research Competition (SRC) - co-located with the 17th International Conference on Model Driven Engineering Languages and Systems (MODELS 2014)", by Corley and Syriani (2014)

The architecture of AToMPM is divided into a front-end web server and a back-end server. The front-end web server enables concurrent multi-client connections on the same server (Corley and Syriani, 2014). AToMPM’s front-end server is based on Node.JS and is fully extensible through the implementation of Plug-ins. The communication within the server and with its Plug-ins is enabled by the *State Chart Extensible Markup Language (SCXML)* and therefore relies on a Stateful kernel. The messages, which the web client and server exchange, are managed by the *AMS* messaging system (Corley and Syriani, 2014). Since every component within AToMPM is an individual Plug-in, there already exists an extensive number of available Plug-ins for AToMPM (Syriani et al., 2013).

The back-end server contains the Model-View-Controller structure and the modeling kernel. The Model-View-Controller structure controls the majority of requests from the front-end to the back-end regarding the different models and views. For every active model or view, a new controller is spawned and terminated if it’s no longer used. All controllers for a model or view are managed by one central *supercontroller*, which also manages the communication with the front-end server (Corley and Syriani, 2014). The consistency between multiple models and views is achieved by the respective controllers, which exchange JSON changelogs (Corley. et al., 2016).

The modeling kernel of the back-end server controls the access to the repository of AToMPM. The kernel provides the central API for activities on that repository for the creation, storing, retrieving, removal, or alteration of a model. In addition, the kernel ensures the consistency within the repository over all models. The modeling kernel is further responsible for the execution of mechanisms and algorithms. However, the kernel treats all the models the same way, and model-specific aspects are not treated within the modeling kernel but by the other components of AToMPM (Corley and Syriani, 2014).

Upon startup of AToMPM, the Plug-in Manager is activated. The Manager is responsible for all Plug-ins, predefined and custom ones, and enables the connection and use of the package system as well as the respective server endpoints. Those Plug-ins also allow the developer to communicate with outside resources, e.g., another server for analysis tasks. In addition, the Plug-ins, which communicate with external resources, will respond in Stateful. This enables the development of a back-end in another programming language than JavaScript. Since the JavaScript part, as well as the Plug-ins, all communicate in Stateful, the interaction and easy extensibility are guaranteed (Syriani et al., 2013).

However, the server side environment must be run on the own machine or server; AToMPM itself doesn’t provide a running web solution (Syriani et al., 2013). Therefore, the meta-modeler must have minimal knowledge about installing and deploying a Node.JS environment.

Furthermore, AToMPM isn’t strictly bound to a web browser as a client-side application. The architecture of AToMPM allows the implementation and use of multiple different clients, like a terminal or smartphone application. However, such applications and clients must be developed and implemented by a developer and aren’t provided by AToMPM out of the box (Corley and Syriani, 2014).

Mechanisms

AToMPM supports two kinds of mechanisms which are introduced individually.

Constraint

Constraints are the first kind of mechanisms that AToMPM supports. *Constraints* are executed or checked upon a *trigger* event. Such *triggers* could be a *pre-connect*, which executes the specified *constraint* whenever two instances are about to be connected. The developer has to specify the respective *constraint* with JavaScript code directly within the browser application. Furthermore, AToMPM distinguishes between *global constraints* and *local constraints*. While the *global constraints* are evaluated for an entire model, the *local constraints* are only evaluated within the context of an object and its neighbors. The return value, or more specifically, the last statement within a *constraint*, must return a Boolean value.

Action

A second kind of mechanism is the *actions*. They work exactly the same way as *constraints*, with the difference that *actions* don't return a Boolean value but perform an action on a model or object. For example, an action can set a value of an object whenever a new instance of that object is created. As with the *constraints*, AToMPM distinguishes between *global* and *local actions*. The differences are similar to the *constraints*. Just as *constraints*, *actions* must be implemented using JavaScript. However, AToMPM provides a predefined set of *actions* that the developer can use. Only additional code, like conditional statements or loops, can be added in JavaScript.

Algorithms

AToMPM supports two kinds of algorithms which are introduced individually.

Model Transformation

AToMPM features *model transformations* for algorithms. Those *model transformations* are a collection of *rules* that are mapped on a model in a specific sequence, and subsequently, the model is rewritten. Every *rule* has three components. The *Negative Application Condition (NAC)*, a *Left-Hand-Side (LHS)* and *Right-Hand-Side (RHS)*. The LHS specifies on what pattern the rule shall be applied. AToMPM searches for that pattern and executes the rule if the pattern can be matched on the models. The matching process results in a *match set*, which then gets processed through the NAC list. If the model is in the NAC list, the rule isn't executed. In other words, the NAC is a list of models where the *rule* shall be ignored, even if the model is within the *match set*. The last component, the RHS, specifies the post-condition pattern. It defines how the model should look like after the *model transformation* was applied. So, the *model transformation* can create, delete, or update instances. The actions called within the LHS or RHS originate from the available *actions* and are defined within the web application.

The *rules* in AToMPM are scheduled in *MoTif* (Syriani et al., 2013), which stands for *Modular Timed Graph Transformation* (Syriani and Vangheluwe, 2013). *MoTif* builds upon the *Discrete Event System Specification (DEVS)*, which enables the control flow first for modeling and then simulating discrete event systems. *MoTif* extends the DEVS formalism and enables the developer to schedule the model transformations (Syriani and Vangheluwe, 2013). The language provides a set of steps, which together build a schedule. Each step has a success and failure case, which in turn specifies the following steps. The schedule ends after any stream reaches the end step.

Plug-in

A second form of algorithm, which the developer can implement, is the *Plug-ins*. A *Plug-in* is executed either by a dedicated button or a previously defined transformation code. AToMPM

provides a set of predefined functions that enable access to the model data. These predefined functions can be supplemented by non-AToMPM-specific code like conditional statements or loops. The entire code, predefined and additional code, must be written in JavaScript. A *Plug-in* is developed in any IDE and not within the web application. The Plug-in has to be incorporated into the built version of AToMPM and therefore must run on the respective server.

Furthermore, the developer can choose between the *Client-API* and *Remote-API*. The *Client-API* can be accessed through a button in the toolbar or the console of AToMPM. On the other hand, the *Remote-API* allows access to the server for third-party applications. Important to note is that the *Remote-API* only offers a limited set of functions and doesn't allow full access like the *Client-API* does. Furthermore, differ the two kinds of APIs in the way they interact with the front-end server. While the *Client-API* directly interacts and calls functions within the front-end server, the *Remote-API* executes specific HTTP-Requests with a predefined argument towards the back-end server. Depending on the argument provided within the HTTP-Request, a different function is called.

Evaluation of AToMPM

For the evaluation of AToMPM, the author conducted an in-depth analysis of the application, the available source code, the documentation, and the available literature by Syriani and Vangheluwe (2013), Syriani et al. (2013), and Corley and Syriani (2014). In addition, the evaluation of AToMPM by Corley. et al. (2016) served as a central source for the performance evaluation. AToMPM was run locally on a Linux Fedora 38 machine with 16GB of LPDDR4 RAM (@4266 MHz) with an AMD Ryzen 7 5800H (8 Cores, 16 Threads) running at max 4.4 GHz. The specification of the machine is provided to put the results of the paper by Corley. et al. (2016) in perspective. The justification of the points received for every characteristic is stated within the respective cell in Table 5.10.

Property/ Characteristic	Scale and Explanation
Functional completeness	2 Points: Integration of mechanisms and algorithms possible AToMPM allows the integration of mechanisms with <i>Constraints</i> and <i>Actions</i> . Algorithms can be implemented using <i>Model Transformations</i> and <i>Plug-ins</i> .
Capacity	3 Points: Unlimited lengths of code There's no documented limitation for <i>Plug-ins</i> , <i>Constraints</i> , <i>Actions</i> , or <i>Model Transformations</i> .
Resource utilisation	1 Point: Multi-Core/Multi-Thread AToMPM is a server-based application. Its scalability is achieved by spawning new child processes. AToMPM uses multiple cores/threads on the server side, as Corley. et al. (2016) showed. Therefore, AToMPM features a high performance as long as the connection to the server is sufficient.

Property/ Characteristic	Scale and Explanation
User error protection	2 Points: Extensive error protection AToMPM itself doesn't provide user protection for any mechanisms or algorithms. However, since AToMPM is mainly based on JavaScript, the developer can use an IDE. There, the developer profits from auto-complete, bracket-matching, syntax highlighting etc. from the IDE itself.
Learnability	3 Points: Average effort AToMPM uses JavaScript for all of the mechanisms or algorithms. The AToMPM-specific APIs, actions, and HTTP-Requests are well documented but require some familiarity with JavaScript and HTTP-Requests.
Documentation	2 Points: Extensive documentation available AToMPM provides very extensive documentation. Everything, down to every API, is documented.
Reusability	3 Points: Highly reusable AToMPM allows the combination of <i>Plug-ins</i> and therefore the reuse of existing code. External resources can be accessed through <i>Plug-ins</i> as well.
Testability	2 Points: Hard & fast IDEs allow for a quick way to compile the JavaScript code. In addition, the debugging with breakpoints allows for easier problem identification. However, AToMPM itself doesn't provide automated testing or testing within the web application apart from the execution itself.
Installability	4 Points: Four platforms supported AToMPM is a web application. Therefore, all operating systems (Windows, macOS, Linux) and technologies (x86, ARM) are supported.
Usefulness (Pro-grammers)	3 Points: Very satisfied AToMPM uses only code-based implementation of mechanisms and algorithms; therefore, a technical person is very satisfied with the approach chosen.
Usefulness (non-technical people)	1 Points: More or less satisfied All mechanisms and algorithms are implemented with code. However, the required code for each component of a <i>constraint</i> , <i>action</i> , or <i>model transformation</i> is divided into individual fields. This enables non-technical people to understand the required code better. Nevertheless, the meta-modeler should have extensive knowledge of JavaScript.
Context complete-ness	3 Points: High completeness With AToMPM, the meta-modeler and modeler can achieve all their tasks within their context of use.

Property/ Characteristic	Scale and Explanation
Flexibility	<p>2 Points: Average flexibility</p> <p>Use cases like AR and VR are not possible with AToMPM; however, AToMPM provides a very versatile toolset that allows the use of the platform in multiple different domains and use cases. Especially the development of additional <i>Plug-ins</i> enables powerful use cases.</p>

Table 5.10: Rating matrix: AToMPM rated

AToMPM achieves a total of **29** points. The different properties are not weighted and count similarly.

The functionality, which Karagiannis and Visic (2011) demand in their paper, is provided by AToMPM, as Table 5.11 demonstrates.

Feature	Description
Language Definition Approach	Hybrid approach. Graphical as well as textual components are used to define a modeling method.
Specifying Notation	Graphical approach. Notation is defined primarily using graphical elements.
Syntax Highlighting and Debugging	Support for highlighting, auto-completing and debugging within the metamodeling toolkit for algorithms.
Scripting	Scripting support for advanced customizing provided.
Import and Export	Import and export of meta-models and models tools possible. .xmi is used as data format.
Integration with Other Tools	APIs, Client-Side, Server-Side Integration possible with AToMPM.
Rich Notation	More than simple symbols for nodes and arcs. Graphical notation very extensive.
Dynamic Symbol Change	Symbols change dynamically when model data changes by implementing mechanisms.
Different Modeling Views	Modeling view available.

Table 5.11: List of features for AToMPM (Karagiannis and Visic, 2011, p. 25). Adapted from *Perspectives in Business Informatics Research* (p. 25), by Karagiannis and Visic (2011) Springer.

5.2.5 Comparison of Metamodeling Platforms

Property/ Characteristic	ADOxx	MetaEdit+	WebGME	AToMPM
Functional completeness	Integration of mechanisms and algorithms possible (2)			
Capacity	Unlimited lengths of code (3)			
Resource utilisation	Multi-Core/Multi-Thread (1)	Multi-Core/Multi-Thread (1)	Multi-Core/Multi-Thread (1)	Multi-Core/Multi-Thread (1)
User error protection	Limited error protection (1)	Limited error protection (1)	Extensive error protection (2)	Extensive error protection (2)
Learnability	High effort, research in documentation required (2)	High effort, research in documentation required (2)	Low effort, intuitive learning (4)	Average effort (3)
Documentation	Extensive documentation available (2)			
Reusability	Limited reusability (2)	Single-format reusability (1)	Highly reusable (3)	Highly reusable (3)
Testability	Hard & fast (2)	Hard & fast (2)	Easy & fast (3)	Hard & fast (2)
Installability	Three platforms supported (3)	Two platforms supported (2)	Four platforms supported (4)	Four platforms supported (4)
Usefulness (Programmers)	Very satisfied (3)	Very satisfied (3)	Very satisfied (3)	Very satisfied (3)
Usefulness (non-technical people)	Not satisfied (0)	Satisfied (2)	Not satisfied (0)	More or less satisfied (1)
Context completeness	High completeness (3)	High completeness (3)	High completeness (3)	High completeness (3)
Flexibility	Average flexibility (2)	Average flexibility (2)	Average flexibility (2)	Average flexibility (2)
Total Points	24	24	30	29

Table 5.12: Comparison of rated metamodeling platforms

The comparison shows that all four metamodeling platforms are very closely together. Each of them has their respective field of excellence and lacks in other domains. However, the rating shows the tendency that web-based solutions are more versatile and generally better suited for (meta-)modeling. This can have many different reasons, one of them might be that the web applications are newer than the on-premise metamodeling platforms. However, this thesis doesn't prove this tendency statistically and therefore has no clear evidence or significance to support this claim.

5.3 Developing the Generic Concept

In this section, the required concepts for implementing mechanisms and algorithms on the meta-meta level of a MM-AR-based platform are introduced. The approaches of the four analyzed metamodeling platforms are taken into account, but no specific approach is chosen exclusively. This section provides only the meta-meta level concepts and doesn't consider the specific implementation into the existing MM-AR platform of the University of Fribourg. Every aspect regarding the technical implementation is described in Chapter 6.

5.3.1 Conceptual Design on the Meta-Meta Level

The existing meta-meta model is extended with two independent concepts, one for the mechanisms and one for the algorithms. The mechanisms and algorithms are divided into two individual concepts in order to automatically distinguish code that's executed on any event and only on user input. It further enables the meta-modeler to implement mechanisms without specifying algorithms and vice versa.

Mechanisms

The mechanisms are integrated within the existing *attribute_type* class. Since every *attribute* has a specified *attribute_type*, the mechanism can be integrated using an additional *attribute_type*. The *attribute* can be attached to *classes*, *relationclasses*, *ports* and *scene_types*. The *attribute_type*, however, can only be used for *scene_types* or *classes*. *Relationclasses* can also use mechanisms, since they're a sub-class of the super-class *class*. Mechanisms can thus only be attached to *classes*, *relationclasses* of a *scene_type* or a *scene_type* itself, and don't work model independent. These relations are also present in the adapted meta-meta model in Figure 5.10. Therefore, the constraint of a mechanism is fulfilled. The concept chosen for the MM-AR platform resembles the *expression-attribute* of ADOxx.

The *attribute_type* class has three different attributes itself. The *Pre-Defined*, *Default Value* and *RegExRule* were already defined previously and remain untouched by the modifications of this thesis. The definition, respectively the code, of a mechanism is stored within the *Default Value* attribute. The value is null if no mechanism is specified. Since the *attribute_type* is a *metaobject* as well, the meta-modeler shall distinguish the mechanisms from any other *attribute_type* by name (e.g., *MechanismTokenGamePN* for a token game mechanism within a Petri Net).

The meta-modeler can specify the mechanism within the meta-model using the programming language of the MM-AR-based platform. This requires however, predefined methods and functions which the meta-modeler can use, in order to read and maybe display model data. The predefined

functions and method must at least return the values of all the attributes of the current object, all the relations and neighbouring objects, and also return those values for a specific object if the object itself is provided (e.g., get an attribute value of an object with a specific UUID). The predefined methods and functions, can then be supplemented with generic code snippets like a loop or conditional statement. It is however important, that the specified mechanisms always return a value (e.g., Integer, String, Boolean).

The MM-AR meta-meta model features the concept of *users* in the newest version. Any *user* has permissions (read, modify, create) and is attached to a *user_group*. All mechanisms are independent of the permissions of a *user*. As long as the *user* has at least a *read*-permission and can open a model, the mechanisms will work. Thus, the mechanisms always work for any *user* which has at least a *read*-access to a specific *scene_type*. Mechanisms don't require *write*-permissions since they don't modify or create any data. This shall ensure that any user, who can access a model, also has access to all mechanisms. Mechanisms run with least-privileges.

All mechanisms are executed on any event. This means whenever a modification of an attribute, the creation of a new object or relation, or the deletion of an object or relation occurs, all attached mechanisms are executed. These execution rule leads to increased performance requirements. However, since the computing power increased drastically over the last decades, the almost permanent execution shouldn't lead to performance degradation. A second requirement mitigating factor is the limited set of operations available for mechanisms.

Algorithms

The algorithms are stored in a class called *procedure*, which is a child element of the superclass *metaobject*, according to the meta-meta-model in Figure 5.10. The adapted meta-meta model is available as a full scale model in appendix A.

The *algorithm* can work as a generic algorithm within an MM-AR-based platform as a modeling-method independent algorithm and is therefore not attached to any other class through a relation, except the *metaobject* of course. An example of such an algorithm would be the transformation of the model into a .xml-file or into Java-code. In addition, an algorithm can be attached to one specific *scene_type*. The attached *procedure* is therefore only available for execution for the respective models (*scene_instances*). An example of a modeling method specific algorithm is the simulation of a business process model in BPMN 2.0 or the token game of a Petri Net.

While the algorithms, which are assigned to a *scene_type*, can be specified by the meta-modeler in the meta-model, the modeling-method independent algorithms can only be implemented by the developers of an MM-AR-based platform.

The code of the algorithm will be specified and stored in the *definition* attribute of the *procedure* class. The meta-modeler must at least specify the name, description and the code itself. Additional specifications, like an icon, might be added in the future.

The *procedure* element inherits all properties (e.g., UUID, Name, Description) from the *metaobject*. In addition, the relation to the superclass *metaobject* enables the future restriction of algorithms based on *user* rights. The *user* management and the respective rights are only available for elements which inherit from *metaobject*. The idea is to couple the algorithm with the respective permissions. The algorithm can only be executed if a *user* has all the necessary rights

assigned. Furthermore, individual algorithms can be hidden for *users* or *user_groups*. This allows the administrator and data owner to control who can execute which algorithms on any model.

Every algorithm will be implemented in the programming language of the MM-AR-based environment and stored within the *procedure* object. This ensures a seamless integration into the environment and ensures that no dedicated bridges must be built in. However, just as for the mechanisms, the implementation of an MM-AR-based platform must feature predefined functions and methods. The meta-modeler must have access to all model data. Access to additional data stored within the database (e.g., user data) might enable additional use-cases. These functions and methods must be used within the algorithm which further specifies the logic with loops, conditional statements, use of outside resources etc. The integration of outside resources orients on the respective resource (e.g., REST-API, SOAP-API etc.).

Figure 5.10: Adapted UML Diagram of the meta-meta model Enabling AR and VR integrating mechanisms and algorithms (Muff and Fill, 2021, p. 51) Adapted from "Proceedings of the ER Demos and Posters 2021 co-located with 40th International Conference on Conceptual Modeling", by Muff and Fill (2021)

The algorithms are only executed upon user input. One technique for calling the algorithm is through some sort of menu, where the user can choose the algorithm and model to execute upon. A second technique is the implementation of dedicated buttons within the modeling toolkit of an MM-AR-based platform. This concept doesn't specify the approach for calling any algorithm and leaves this decision upon the developer of an MM-AR-based platform. The approach chosen for the MM-AR Platform of the University of Fribourg will be described in Chapter 6.

As mentioned before, the MM-AR meta-meta model implements in its newest version the concept of *users*. Multiple *users* can work on the same model instance on different machines. Therefore, the integration and execution of algorithms does require a technique for handling concurrency. Since the algorithm is also some sort of modification of the model (model transformation), the model can't be modified by another *user* during the execution of an algorithm. Otherwise modifications of other *users* are overwritten and lost, if the algorithm was executed upon an older version of the model, or the execution of the algorithm produces an entirely different result because the model data changed.

There exist multiple different strategies to solve concurrency like two-phase locking, time stamp ordering or multi version concurrency. For example, ADOxx locks an entire model as soon as any user conducts any modification. The lock on the model is only released when the user stores the current model version. MetaEdit+ on the other hand locks only the current object of the modification and therefore uses a more optimistic concurrency approach.

The author imagines two different approaches for solving the concurrency problem for algorithms. An algorithm can either work on a snapshot, which represents a stored stable state of the model, or always on the newest version of the model/object. The snapshot version ensures that users can still make modifications to the model while the algorithm is executed, however all modifications within the timeframe of storing the snapshot and storing the results of the algorithm execution are lost. The approach of taking always the newest version ensures that any modification until the execution of the algorithm is taken into account. However, an algorithm can therefore also be executed on non-consistent models. This thesis will not provide the solution for handling concurrency nor decide on a solution for handling concurrency for the algorithms. The concurrency handling for the algorithms will orient on the concurrency strategy of the concrete MM-AR implementation. At the moment, no such strategy exists in its final form.

Chapter 6

Technical Realization Using MM-AR

This chapter describes the concrete implementation of the generic concept of Section 5.3. First the general architecture and necessary adaptations of the current technology stack and architecture are discussed. Furthermore, the additions to the MM-AR Platform are discussed in detail and the respective code is described. The chosen approach will be evaluated and discussed. Lastly, the author shows which changes need to be done in the future to ensure a seamless integration into the productive environment.

6.1 Implementation into the MM-AR platform

The introduction of the concrete implementation is divided in two parts: The changes in the platforms architecture and the the changes within the code and instances.

6.1.1 Architectural Changes

The implementation of the generic concept into the existing MM-AR Platform prototype, which was developed by the DIGITS research group of the University of Fribourg, lead to many adaptations and additions within the existing code. However, the basic architecture and technology stack of the platform remained unchanged to minimize the overall changes required. This is in line with the design objective *DO-09* of Chapter 4.

6.1.2 Concrete Additions to the MM-AR Platform

In the generic concept, two independent useable concepts are introduced for mechanisms and algorithms. Therefore, also the elaboration on those concepts is divided in this section. First, the author introduces the changes needed for mechanisms and later the integrated changes for the algorithms. The description of the implementation will start with the additions in the database, then introduces the changes in the back-end server and lastly shows the changes in the front-end server.

Mechanisms

As the generic concept is Section 5.3 states, shall the mechanisms be implemented using the existing concepts of *attributes* and *attribute_types*, with its own attribute *default_value*. Thus,

no changes within the database are required, since all tables remain the same. However, it's important to note that every mechanism has to be specified as such in its name. For all mechanisms, the naming convention *mechanism_ YOUR-MECHANISM-NAME-HERE* applies. This naming convention is later used in the front-end to properly identify executable mechanism *attributes* from the non-executable *attributes*.

In order to be able to execute a mechanism, every mechanism must have the same distinct string-structure, which is shown in Listing 6.1. Since the implementation uses the *eval*-function of JavaScript, the name of the function must be specified. The author defined the key-word *mechanism* for this purpose. Afterwards, the string value must be defined in brackets. The string value equals to the mechanism code, which the meta-modeler wants to define.

```
1 ({mechanism: string => {INSERT YOUR MECHANISM CODE HERE;}})
```

Listing 6.1: Structure of a mechanism for the MM-AR Platform

In addition to the database, also the expressjs back-end remains unchanged. No additional API routes or functions are necessary to GET, POST, PATCH or DELETE a mechanism. All those functions are already implemented through *attributes* and *attribute_types*.

On the client side, multiple additions are required in order to enable the execution of mechanisms. The first changes were made within the instantiation of new attributes in the *instance_creation_handler*.

Before, every normal attribute was instantiated with a combination of the *default value* and a random number and a table attribute with an empty string. With the changes added, the normal attributes and table attributes are instantiated the same way, but if the meta-modeler uses a mechanism as an *attribute_type*, the attribute is instantiated only with the *default value*. Following this logic, all mechanism of the same *attribute_type* hold the same code of the mechanism. Therefore, for every kind of algorithm, another *attribute_type* must be defined.

For retrieving and executing the mechanisms, an additional service called *mechanismUtility* was created. Within this class, the function *executeMechanism()* is responsible for retrieving and executing all available mechanisms of the *scene_type* itself and all assigned *classes* of the current *scene_type*. The *mechanismUtility* iterates over all available attributes of a *scene_instance* and retrieves only the one with *attribute_type* mechanism. Currently, the definition of the mechanism is retrieved from the default-value of the *attribute_type* and not the instantiated value of the *attribute*. The author opted for this solution, because the *attribute_type* of an *attribute_instance* can't be accessed.

```

1 for (const attribute of metaclass.attributes) {
2   if (attribute.attribute_type.has_table_attribute.length == 0 && attribute.
3     attribute_type.name.slice(0,9) != 'mechanism') {
4     this.createAttributeInstance(
5       attribute,
6       null,
7       class_instance.uuid,
8       attribute.attribute_type.default_value + ',' +
9       (Math.random().toPrecision(3) as unknown
10      as number * 1000).toFixed().toString(),
11      null,
12      null,
13      null,
14      null,
15      null
16    );
17   } else if (attribute.attribute_type.name.slice(0,9) == 'mechanism'){
18     this.createAttributeInstance(
19       attribute,
20       null,
21       class_instance.uuid,
22       attribute.attribute_type.default_value,
23       null,
24       null,
25       null,
26       null,
27       null,
28       null
29     );
30   }
31   else {
32     this.createAttributeInstance(
33       attribute,
34       null,
35       class_instance.uuid,
36       "",
37       null,
38       null,
39       null,
40       null,
41       null,
42       null
43     );
44   }
45 };

```

Listing 6.2: Changes in the class *instance_creation_handler* for mechanisms

```

1 executeMechanism(){
2     let tabContext = this.gc.tabContext[this.gc.selectedTab];
3     let tabContextClasses = tabContext['sceneType'].classes;
4     for(let i in tabContextClasses){
5         let temp = tabContextClasses[i].attributes
6         for(let j in temp){
7             if(temp[j].attribute_type.name.slice(0,9) == "mechanism"){
8                 let transpiledCode
9                 ts.transpile(temp[j].attribute_type.default_value);
10                eval(transpiledCode).mechanism()
11            }
12        }
13    }
14    for(let i in tabContext['sceneType'].attributes){
15        if(tabContext['sceneType'].attributes[i].attribute_type.
16        name.slice(0,9) == "mechanism"){
17            let transpiledCode = ts.transpile(tabContext['sceneType'].
18            attributes[i].attribute_type.default_value);
19            eval(transpiledCode).mechanism()
20        }
21    }
22 }

```

Listing 6.3: Function definition of *executeMechanism* in the class *mechanismUtility*

After retrieving the code from the object, the function transpiles the stored code and executes that code using the *eval*-function of JavaScript. The mechanism code can currently hold only standardized JavaScript functions. At the moment, no platform-specific functions are defined for using in mechanisms. However, if such functions are defined in the future, the meta-modeler can use them within the defined mechanism together with non-platform-specific code.

The definition of mechanisms state that they're executed automatically e.g., on change, on an interval or any other automatic specification. For the MM-AR Platform, the concept calls for an *on-any-change-execution*. A change in a model can be one of the following events: Drawing or deleting a *class* or *relationclass*, changing the mode (DrawingMode, SelectionMode, ViewMode) and changing a value of an *attribute*. Therefore, the function *executeMechanism()* of the class *mechanismUtility* is called within the classes *InteractionHandler* and *DeletionHandler*.

The mechanisms within the MM-AR Platform can only be executed automatically and not by the user manually. Furthermore, the mechanism can only be modified through the back-end of the MM-AR Platform by modifying the respective meta-model.

Algorithms

The generic concept of Section 5.3 defines that an algorithm is stored in the class *procedure* and can be attached to one or multiple *scene_types*. Those two concepts must be implemented on the database, back-end server and must be accessible through the front-end server.

Within the database, two new tables are persisted. The table *procedure* represents the class procedure on the meta-meta level and holds all the information of the algorithm. The table has to columns, the *uuid_metaobject*, which references the uuid of the respective metaobject, and the

definition which holds the code of the algorithm in one string. The *uuid_metaobject* is a foreign key of the column *uuid* of the table *metaobject*. The reference occurs, because the procedure is also a metaobject, and thus a corresponding metaobject must exist. The delete and update rule are *cascade*, because if the *uuid* of the metaobject changes, the changes shall be propagated into the *procedure* table. If the metaobject is deleted, the algorithm is deleted and therefore the algorithm must also be deleted from the *procedure* table.

The column *uuid_metaobject* is also the primary key of the table *procedure*.

The second table which must be persisted is the *has_algorithm* table. This table serves as a utility table which defines to which *scene_type* an algorithm is assigned. The table has again two columns, but both reference the primary key of another table. The column *uuid_procedure* uses the foreign key to the *uuid_metaobject* of the table *procedure*. Because all changes and the deletion of the procedure shall be propagated, the delete and update rule are *cascade*.

The second column, *uuid_scene_type*, references the column *uuid_metaobject* of the table *scene_type*. This foreign key has once again *cascade* as the deletion and update rule. If the *scene_type* itself is deleted, also the connection of the *procedure* to the *scene_type* shall be dissolved.

Overall, the naming convention has been taken from the existing tables and columns to ensure a seamless integration. The new ER Diagram for the four tables is shown in Figure 6.1.

Figure 6.1: Entity Relationship Diagram for algorithms

The changes in the back-end server are divided into changes in the global data structure, and changes in the expressjs server itself. The global data structure now has the new object *procedure* which extends the class *MetaObject* since it's a metaobject according to the meta-meta model. The *procedure* only exists on the meta level and not on the instance level. Because every *scene_instance* of the same type must have the same, and most recent, algorithms. Therefore, the *procedure* isn't attached to a *scene_instance* but accessed on the meta-level.

The class *procedure* has only one getter and no setter defined. The getter enables the user to retrieve the definition of an algorithm. Setters are not needed, since the definition of an algorithm

is achieved directly over the back-end API. The detailed code with constructor, methods and variable declaration is shown in Listing 6.4.

```

1 class Procedure extends MetaObject {
2   @Type(() => String) public definition: string;
3   constructor(uuid: UUID, name: string, definition: string) {
4     super(uuid, name);
5     this.definition = definition;
6   }
7
8   getProcedureDefinition(){
9     return this.definition
10  }
11 }

```

Listing 6.4: Class definition *Procedure* in the global data structure

Every *procedure* must have the distinct structure in Listing 6.5 in order to be executable. The structure is almost the same as the structure of the mechanisms, since they both use the JavaScript function *eval()*. The details about the transpilation and execution of the algorithms will be provided in the following paragraphs.

```

1 ({algorithm: string => {INSERT YOUR ALGORITHM CODE HERE;}})

```

Listing 6.5: Structure of an algorithm (*procedure*) for the MM-AR Platform

The changes in the running server itself are more substantial than those of the global data structure. For better readability, the changes are divided into changes in the expressjs configuration, routes, data and the controllers.

The expressjs received multiple new paths in its configuration. Overall, nine new paths for the *procedures* were implemented. The get operation paths are used for getting all independent algorithms, get an algorithm by its uuid and get all the algorithms of a specific *scene_type*. The post operations can be used for creating a new independent algorithm or a new algorithm for a specific *scene_type*. A specific algorithm can be updated by a patch operation with its uuid as a parameter. Furthermore, the meta-modeler can delete a specific algorithm, all algorithms of a *scene_type* or all available algorithms. All available API operations for algorithms are shown in Figure 6.2. The meta-modeler can use those back-end API calls for persistence calls on the database. Furthermore, the front-end calls the API to retrieve the required data from the database and doesn't access the database directly.

In addition to the operations itself, the additional permission *can_create_procedure* had to be introduced. Otherwise, the POST operation for the *procedures* would not work.

Apart from the paths itself, also the structure of a *procedure* was specified. Once again, the initial structure of the *metaobject* was taken and extended with the *procedure*-specific attributes, just as the meta-meta model defines.

These routes further define the actions and methods called within the respective controller when executing the different operations.

Figure 6.2: Screenshot of the available API operations for algorithms on the expressjs back-end server

The controller class for the *procedures* handles all operations/requests for the *procedures* and makes the respective calls to the database connection and returns feedback. All operations for creating, getting, updating and deleting *procedures* are available in the controller. In the following, the method *get_procedure_by_uuid* is examined in detail as an example in Listing 6.6. All the other methods work the same way and differ only in their executed operations. The structure and order of operation resembles the already existing controllers of the back-end server.

First, the controller establishes a connection to the database through the class *Metamodel_procedureConnection* which will be introduced later. Afterwards, the controller calls the function *getByUuid* of the connection class and provides this function with the required parameters. These parameters are embedded in the request. The return value of the called function is then assigned to the variable *sc*. If that variable is now an instance of the class *Procedure*, therefore a *procedure-object*, the variable is returned with the HTTP status code 200 (successful operation). However, if the type of the variable *sc* is undefined, therefore not a *procedure-object*, the procedure with the specified UUID could not have been found. Thus, the error-code 404 (resource not found) is returned.

The controller returns the error-code 403, if the user doesn't have the necessary permissions to do that operation. This case only occurs, if the variable *sc* is neither of type *Procedure* nor undefined. Only if the operation was executed without an error are the changes, made by the transaction, stored ("COMMIT"). However, if anywhere in the process an error gets thrown, the

operation is undone and the error message and code are returned to the user.

In any case, the active connection to the database is released.

```
1 get_procedure_by_uuid: RequestHandler = async (req, res, next) => {
2   const client = await database_connection.getPool().connect();
3   try {
4     await client.query("BEGIN");
5     const sc = await Metamodel_procedure_connection.getByUuid(
6       client,
7       req.params.uuid,
8       req.body.tokendata.uuid
9     );
10    if (sc instanceof Procedure) {
11      res.status(200).json(filter_object(sc, req.query.filter));
12    } else if (typeof sc === "undefined") {
13      throw new API404Error(`Cannot find the meta procedure ${req.params.uuid}.`);
14    } else {
15      throw new HTTP403NORIGHT(
16        req.body.tokendata.username +
17        " does not have the right for the meta procedure: " +
18        req.params.uuid
19      );
20    }
21    await client.query("COMMIT");
22  } catch (err) {
23    await client.query("ROLLBACK");
24    next(err);
25  } finally {
26    (await client).release();
27  }
28 };
```

Listing 6.6: Method *get_procedure_by_uuid* of the class *Metamodel_procedureController*

The class *Metamodel_procedureConnection* handles the CRUD-operations (Create, Read, Update, Delete) for the *procedures*. This class executes the operations called by the *Metamodel_procedureController* and therefore runs the respective SQL-Queries. The *Metamodel_procedureConnection* is one of two major changes in the data-package.

As already for the controller, the function *getByUuid* in Listing 6.7 will serve as an example of the available functions in the class *Metamodel_procedureConnection*. The available functions, the overall structure and logic resembles the existing classes for handling the CRUD operations.

```

1  async getByUuid(client: PoolClient, procedureUuid: UUID, userUuid?: UUID):
2      Promise<Procedure | undefined | 403> {
3      const procedure_query = queries.getQuery_get("procedure_uuid_query");
4      try {
5          let newProcedure: Procedure | undefined;
6          let res_procedure;
7          if (userUuid !== undefined) {
8              const addon_read_check = queries.getQuery_get(
9                  "addon_right_read_check");
10             res_procedure = await client.query(procedure_query +
11                 addon_read_check, [procedureUuid, userUuid]);
12         } else {
13             res_procedure = await client.query(procedure_query,
14                 [procedureUuid]);
15         }
16         if(res_procedure.rowCount == 1){
17             newProcedure = Procedure.fromJS(res_procedure.rows[0]) as Procedure
18             return newProcedure
19         }
20         if (
21             (await client
22                 .query(procedure_query, [procedureUuid])
23                 .then((res) => res.rowCount == 1)) &&
24             userUuid !== undefined
25         ) {
26             return 403;
27         }
28         return newProcedure;
29     } catch (err) {
30         throw new Error(`Error getting the procedure ${procedureUuid}: ${err}`)
31     }
32 }

```

Listing 6.7: Method *getByUuid* of the class *Metamodel_procedureConnection*

With those adaptations and additions, the database and back-end are fully functional for the use of algorithms. The meta-modeler can define, store, update and delete algorithms. Those algorithms can be stored as independent algorithms, or can be assigned to one or more *scene_type*.

The available algorithms can be accessed through an algorithm dialog window, which can be opened through a button in the navigation-bar. As soon as the dialog opens, the independent algorithms and the assigned algorithms of the current *scene_type* are retrieved from the database and shown as a toggle menu. Within the same dialog, shown in Figure 6.4, the user can execute the chosen algorithm, upon the currently active model.

The algorithm menu information and information about the *Procedures* is stored as arrays. One array of type *Procedure* holds all the independent algorithms as *Procedure*-objects and a second array holds the *scene_type* specific algorithms as *Procedure*-objects. Two separate arrays of type *String* hold the names of the algorithms either for the independent or *scene_type* specific algorithms. Those arrays are used for displaying the data in the algorithm dialog.

Whenever an algorithm is executed by the user, the client searches for that specific algorithm in the array of type *Procedure*, see Listing 6.8 for reference. As soon as the algorithm is found, the

Figure 6.3: Screenshot of the MM-AR Platform modeling client with the menu entry for algorithms

Figure 6.4: Screenshot of the MM-AR Platform modeling client with the opened Algorithm Dialog and available algorithms

definition of the *Procedure* object is assigned to the variable *procedureCode*. The code held in this variable gets transpiled and again assigned to a variable. The transpiled code, then gets executed using the *eval()* function.

The implementation allows for a simultaneous call of one independent and one scene_type-specific algorithm. The execution itself however is in sequence and the implementation is similar.

```

1 execute(generalAlgorithmName:string, specificAlgorithmName:string){
2     let procedureCode = "";
3     let transpiledCode = "";
4
5     if(generalAlgorithmName != undefined || generalAlgorithmName != "none"){
6         for(let i in this.procedures){
7             if(this.procedures[i].name == generalAlgorithmName){
8                 procedureCode = this.procedures[i].definition
9             }
10        }
11        transpiledCode = ts.transpile(procedureCode);
12        eval(transpiledCode).algorithm()
13    }
14
15    if(specificAlgorithmName != undefined || specificAlgorithmName != "none"){
16        for(let i in this.assignedProcedures){
17            if(this.assignedProcedures[i].name == specificAlgorithmName){
18                procedureCode = this.assignedProcedures[i].definition
19            }
20        }
21        transpiledCode = ts.transpile(procedureCode);
22        eval(transpiledCode).algorithm()
23    }

```

Listing 6.8: Method *execute* of the service class *procedure_utility*

The algorithm is always executed on the *scene_instance* on the client side. Therefore, all changes are only stored locally in the *GlobalObjectDefinition*. The changes in the model are only persisted to the database if the user actively stores the model in the database. Otherwise, the changes of the algorithm to the model are lost as soon as the modeling client is closed.

6.2 Evaluation of Approach

The generic concept and the later concrete implementation into the existing MM-AR Platform will be evaluated based on the requirements, subsequent the design objectives and finally the rating matrix. Furthermore, the current capability gap regarding mechanisms and algorithms will be discussed. The description of the capability gap is divided into mechanisms and algorithms. The evaluation of the design objectives and rating matrix will be applied on the entire concept and implementation. The evaluation is based on the analysis of the competing metamodeling platforms and the experiences of the author during the implementation of the generic concept. No statistically proven evaluation of the generic concept or implementation will be provided.

The fulfillment status of the requirements and design objectives is shown in the Tables 6.1, 6.2 and 6.3 in the separate Section 6.2.4. The fulfillment of the design objectives will be referenced within the respective paragraph as well.

6.2.1 General Evaluation

Multiple design objectives are generic and can't be clearly assigned to mechanisms or algorithms. These design objectives will be evaluated and discussed in this section.

The generic concept for implementing mechanisms and algorithms into an MM-AR-based meta-modeling platform adapts concepts which could be identified through the analysis of ADOxx, MetaEdit+, WebGME or AToMPM. The concepts of *expressions* of ADOxx can be found in the generic concept for the mechanisms. The approach for the *procedure* strongly resembles the concepts of the *Plug-in* within WebGME and *PROGRAMMCALL* of ADOxx. Therefore, the generic concept and the later implementation reuses proven approaches of other meta-modeling platforms. This leads to the achievement of the design objective DO-03.

The technology stack of the existing MM-AR Platform remains unchanged by the integration of mechanisms and algorithms. Since no changes in the used technologies are required, the platform still uses state-of-the-art technologies. Therefore, the design objective DO-06 is achieved.

6.2.2 Mechanisms

The overall verdict for implementing mechanisms into the MM-AR meta-meta model and the existing MM-AR Platform is positive. The mechanisms could be integrated fully functional and can now be used as a prototype in the MM-AR Platform. Therefore, the design objectives DO-01 and DO-05 are achieved for mechanisms.

The generic concept assumes no changes for implementing mechanisms into a MM-AR-based platform. For the concrete implementation into the existing MM-AR Platform, this is true. The meta-meta model, database and back-end servers remain unchanged and need no modifications for implementing mechanisms into the platform. The front-end modeling client, however, needs some changes in order to retrieve, transpile and execute mechanisms at runtime. Those changes were expected from the beginning and were done as modular as possible with the class *mechanismUtility*. Further changes in the instantiation of attributes were done in order to instantiate the mechanisms with the correct value. For integrating mechanisms, only this additional class and change in the instantiation were necessary. The design objectives DO-02 and DO-09 are thus achieved for mechanisms.

For the definition of a mechanism, the meta-modeler can use the existing expressjs back-end without any modification. The meta-modeler can add an attribute and specify the mechanisms code within the *default_value* attribute of the *attribute_type*. Therefore, the design objective DO-04 is achieved for mechanisms.

One of the major advantages of this approach is that all meta-models of all MM-AR-based platforms are still interchangeable. If one MM-AR-based platform integrates mechanisms, the defined mechanisms of the meta-model are executed. If the MM-AR-based platform doesn't integrate mechanisms, the meta-model still works, but no mechanisms are executed. The same principles are valid for meta-models with or without mechanisms. Following this, the design objective DO-08 is fulfilled for mechanisms.

Every mechanism is implemented like a *class-attribute* in ADOxx. This means that every instance has the same value for this attribute. All instances of any element have the exact same mechanism defined to ensure consistency within the model and the model elements. This approach prohibits the modeler from modifying a mechanism during runtime. Nevertheless, this approach was assessed as suitable for mechanisms.

Almost every metamodeling platform uses a different approach for exporting models and the contained model data. The approach chosen for the MM-AR Platform includes the mechanism code but excludes the result of the respective mechanism. A very brief analysis discovered no major advantage for storing the mechanism code and the result, since the code should always lead to the same result if the model state is consistent. However, a more in-depth analysis might discover advantages which could lead to a model storage strategy change.

All mechanisms are executed on any-change. This means that the function *executeMechanism()* is executed very often. Since the function always iterates over all *classes* and the attached *attributes*, the performance might be impacted. During the conducted tests, no performance deteriorations were found. However, those test results are inconclusive since only small *scene_instances* and very basic mechanisms (e.g., logging a value to the console) were used.

The performance might be impacted when the modeler uses a large model and more complex mechanisms. For a conclusive answer to the performance impact of mechanisms, more in-depth testing and analysis must be conducted.

Current Limitations

The implementation of mechanisms within the existing MM-AR Platform has its limitation due to out-of-scope analysis and implementation effort.

The first limitation is the lack of predefined functions which the meta-modeler can use for accessing the model data. Currently mechanisms can only execute generic JavaScript code. The predefined methods must be carefully chosen since unwanted modifications of model-data might occur. An in-depth analysis is necessary to determine which functions are useful for mechanisms, and which operations must be prohibited to ensure model consistency. Overall, the design objective DO-07 is only partially achieved for mechanisms.

Secondly, the meta-modeler can't specify on which events a mechanism shall be executed. At the moment, all mechanisms are executed on any-change and the limitation of a mechanism execution on a specific event isn't possible.

Third, mechanisms concern the performance aspect. While no definitive answer can be given if many and complex mechanisms affect the performance of the MM-AR platform, it's very likely. The function *executeMechanism()* iterates over the entire *scene_instance*, its classes and attributes, in a very inefficient way whenever any-change occurs in the model.

Fourth, the *eval()* function might lead to security issues. An additional analysis is required if a change in the overall approach or only in the function used is necessary.

6.2.3 Algorithms

The generic concept for implementing algorithms in a MM-AR-based platform, which was described in Section 5.3, uses very subtle and as small as possible changes to the existing meta-meta model. The changes made limit themselves on one new class, but no changes to the existing classes. The overall goal of integrating algorithms into the MM-AR meta-meta model is achieved with those changes. The design objectives DO-01 and DO-05 could be achieved for algorithms.

The concrete implementation of the generic concept followed the same modular logic. The integration of algorithms only extends the platform with new concepts, without changing the existing ones.

The additional required concepts within the database were added, without modifying existing tables or references. The extraction and storing to the Global Data Structure of the algorithm from the database follows the same approach as the rest of the platform for extracting data. Only the additional required routes, controllers, connections, and SQL-Statements were added. Therefore, the performance aspect of retrieving algorithms is negligible.

In addition to the controllers, connections, routes, and the object *Procedure* were added. The object *Procedure* includes the object definition and inheritance from the *metaobject*. The design objective DO-02 is therefore evaluated as achieved.

On the front-end modeling client side, where the algorithm itself is transpiled and executed, the performance plays a bigger role. During testing, no performance issues were found, and all the code ran smoothly without any performance deterioration for the rest of the platform. Nevertheless, further performance testing is required to ensure that the platform's performance wasn't influenced negatively by the implementation of algorithms. While the functional tests were very extensive, the performance tests of the algorithms were very lean.

Overall, the changes required within the existing MM-AR Platform were fairly limited, but the design objective DO-09 can be rated as achieved.

The author chose to store the changes of an algorithm to a model only locally because this is the current approach of the platform prototype for storing changes to a model. Therefore, if the approach for storing modifications to a model changes, e.g due to the implementation of a specific concurrency solution, the implementation of the algorithms might need additional work. The implementation of storing modifications to a model will always orient on the general approach of the MM-AR-based platform.

Every algorithm is always stored on the meta-level directly in the database, and not within a *scene_instance*. This has the advantage that the algorithm is only stored once for all *scene_instances* and every *scene_instance* always executes the most recent version of the algorithm. But it has the disadvantage that every MM-AR-based platform, where the *scene_instance* is modeled and the algorithm executed, must have the respective algorithm implemented. If the *scene_instance* is exported as a JSON-file, no reference to an independent or *scene_type* specific algorithm exists.

In the future the need for a reference of all *scene_type* specific algorithms in the *scene_instance* might occur. If so, the reference strategy of *scene_instances* and *procedure*-instances must be adapted, respectively the *procedure_instance* must be integrated on the meta-meta level.

The integration of algorithms, using the additional *procedure*-object, allows the usage of legacy meta-models since they work the same way as meta-models without any specific algorithms.

Current Limitations

The implementation of algorithms within the existing MM-AR Platform has its limitation due to out-of-scope analysis and implementation effort.

First, the algorithms can't use predefined functions to access model data or additional data

within the MM-AR Platform, because no such predefined functions exist. As already with the mechanisms, an in-depth analysis must be conducted to define which operations are useful for algorithms, without enabling malicious or unwanted modifications. Therefore, the design objective DO-07 is only partially fulfilled for algorithms.

Second, a *scene_instances* has no reference to an algorithm. While this might not be an issue as long as the *scene_instances* remains within the same MM-AR-based platform instance, issues will start to occur when sharing *scene_instances* between MM-AR-based platform instances with different meta-level algorithms.

Third, the integration of outside resources is not possible at the moment. This is due to the lack of predefined functions.

Fourth, the security implications, respectively concerns, following the use of the *eval()* function must be investigated in detail. A change in the approach or function might be necessary to fulfill future security requirements.

6.2.4 Evaluation of Design Objectives and Requirements

In this section, the fulfillment status and the respective reasoning of the requirements and design objectives is shown. The requirements are divided into requirements towards the generic concept (Table 6.1) and towards the concrete implementation into the existing MM-AR Platform (Table 6.2) according to Section 4.3.

After the evaluated requirements, the design objectives are listed in Table 6.3, with their fulfillment status and respective reasoning.

Requirements for the Generic Concept

Req-ID	Name	DO-ID	Status	Reasoning
Functional Requirements				
FR-01	Domain specific mechanisms and algorithms	DO-04, DO-07	Fulfilled	The meta-modeler can define mechanisms using the <i>attribute_type</i> concept. Algorithms can be integrated using the <i>procedure-object</i> .
FR-02	Use of platform-specific code	DO-04, DO-07	Fulfilled	The generic concept doesn't limit the kind of code. The concept allows for platform-specific as well as non-platform-specific code.
FR-03	Use of generic code	DO-07	Fulfilled	Generic JavaScript code can be run without any issues. The <i>eval()</i> function enables the execution of code.
FR-04	Support all legacy meta-models	DO-08	Fulfilled	Any meta-model with or without mechanisms or algorithms can be run. No changes within the structure of the meta-model are required for legacy meta-models.

Req-ID	Name	DO-ID	Status	Reasoning
FR-09	Execute algorithms	DO-05	Fulfilled	The execution of algorithms is started through an additional dialog in the front-end. The <i>eval()</i> function enables the execution itself.
FR-10	Define calling of algorithms	DO-05	Not fulfilled	The meta-modeler can't define how an algorithm is called. The generic concept doesn't allow for an execution specification.
Quality Requirements				
QR-01	Reusable concept	DO-01, DO-02, DO-03	Fulfilled	The generic concept can be implemented in any metamodeling platform which is based on the MM-AR meta-meta model.
QR-02	Technology independent	DO-01, DO-03	Fulfilled	The meta-meta model is technology independent and can be implemented using any technology stack.

Table 6.1: Evaluation of the requirements for the generic concept

Most of the requirements towards the generic concept could be fulfilled. The only current capability gap is that the meta-modeler can't define how an algorithm is executed (e.g., Hotspot of ADOxx, Menu-item etc.). The generic concept doesn't provide any means for defining the kind of calling. However, the concept of the *procedure* could easily be extended to incorporate this capability in the future.

Requirements for the Prototype

Req-ID	Name	DO-ID	Status	Reasoning
Functional Requirements				
FR-05	Definition of mechanisms and algorithms	DO-05, DO-06, DO-07	Fulfilled	The meta-modeler can define mechanisms and algorithms using the same JSON meta-model file. The definition of mechanisms or algorithms can be pushed to the database using the same expressjs back-end.
FR-06	Get attribute values	DO-07	Not fulfilled	Currently no platform-specific functions are defined. Therefore, model data can't be accessed by mechanisms or algorithms.

Req-ID	Name	DO-ID	Status	Reasoning
FR-07	Prompt messages	DO-07	Fulfilled	Generic JavaScript code can be executed. Therefore, the meta-modeler can prompt a message using the <i>alert()</i> function.
FR-08	Restrict actions	DO-05, DO-07	Not fulfilled	No platform-specific functions are defined. Since no model data can be accessed, type-checking or the restriction of modeling activities can't be restricted using mechanisms or algorithms.
Quality Requirements				
QR-03	Same performance	DO-09	Partially fulfilled	During testing, no performance deterioration due to mechanisms or algorithms could be detected. However, further performance testing, with larger models and more complex mechanisms and algorithms, must be conducted to arrive to a final conclusion.
Constraint Requirements				
CR-01	Use existing platform	DO-05, DO-06, DO-09	Fulfilled	No changes to the used technology stack was done. The use of the concepts of <i>attribute_type</i> and <i>procedure</i> enabled a seamless integration into the existing MM-AR Platform.

Table 6.2: Evaluation of the requirements for the MM-AR Platform based prototype

The generic concept could be implemented into the existing MM-AR Platform. However, some requirements for the implementation couldn't be fulfilled.

At the moment, no platform-specific functions are defined. Therefore, the model data can't be accessed by mechanisms or algorithms. Since the model data can't be accessed automatically, type-checking or restricting model activities isn't possible as well. This leads to a substantial capability gap regarding mechanisms and algorithms. However, this issue is easily resolvable by providing the necessary platform-specific functions.

It's important to note that the developers of the MM-AR platform must clearly define which functions shall be available. An in-depth analysis can help to determine which predefined functions are needed and what implications this has regarding performance, security or additional factors.

Design Objectives

ID	Name	Status	Reasoning
Concept targeted design objectives			
DO-01	Development of the generic concept	Fulfilled	The generic concept for integrating mechanisms and algorithms into the existing MM-AR meta-meta model was achieved. For the mechanisms the concepts of <i>attributes</i> and <i>attribute_types</i> were reused. The new concept of <i>procedures</i> was introduced for implementing algorithms.
DO-02	Minimal changes to the MM-AR meta-meta model	Fulfilled	The generic concept introduced only minimal changes to the existing MM-AR meta-meta model. The changes limit themselves on the <i>procedures</i> and their relations for the algorithms. For the mechanisms, the only changes are additional relations from the <i>attribute_type</i> to the <i>class</i> and <i>scene_type</i> .
DO-03	Reuse existing concepts	Fulfilled	The generic concept does use the concept of the <i>Expression-attribute</i> for mechanisms, which is implemented in ADOxx. Furthermore, the <i>procedure</i> strongly resembles the concept of <i>PROGRAMMCALL</i> of ADOxx or the <i>Plug-in</i> of WebGME. Thus, proven concepts have been reused for implementing mechanisms and algorithms into the MM-AR platform.
MM-AR platform targeted design objectives			
DO-04	Meta-modeler faced functionalities	Fulfilled	A meta-modeler can implement mechanisms and algorithms using the existing expressjs back-end solution. All mechanisms are executed automatically. For executing algorithms, the prototype provides an additional menu, where the modeler can execute the desired independent and <i>scene_type</i> specific algorithms.
DO-05	Implementation in the MM-AR platform	Fulfilled	The existing MM-AR Platform fully implements the generic concept for implementing mechanisms and algorithms. Mechanisms and algorithms can be defined and executed.
DO-06	State-of-the-art technologies	Fulfilled	The MM-AR platform prototype still uses the previous technology stack without any modifications. Therefore, the MM-AR platform still uses state-of-the-art technologies.

ID	Name	Status	Reasoning
DO-07	Allow meta-modeler code	Partially fulfilled	The meta-modeler can implement non-platform-specific code like loops and conditional statements in their mechanisms and algorithms. Currently, the prototype doesn't provide platform-specific functions to access model data.
DO-08	Support of legacy meta-models	Fulfilled	All legacy meta-models without <i>procedures</i> or mechanisms still work in the new MM-AR prototype without any issue.
DO-09	Minimal changes to the MM-AR platform	Fulfilled	The implementation of <i>procedures</i> required additional components within the MM-AR platform but almost no changes to existing components. The implementation of mechanisms required the addition of one component and no changes to the existing ones. Therefore, the changes in the MM-AR platform are minimal.

Table 6.3: Design Objectives for the generic concept for implementing algorithms on a MM-AR-based platform

Overall, no design objective couldn't be fulfilled. Apart from the platform-specific functions, all design objectives have been achieved. The development of the generic concept for implementing mechanisms and algorithms into a metamodeling platform for AR and VR and its implementation into the existing MM-AR Platform can be labeled as a success.

6.2.5 Rating Matrix for the MM-AR Platform

Property/ Characteristic	Scale and Explanation
Functional completeness	2 Points: Integration of mechanisms and algorithms possible The MM-AR Platform is capable of integrating mechanisms through the additional <i>attribute_types</i> . Algorithms can be implemented using the new <i>procedure</i> object, which can be attached to <i>scene_types</i> and <i>classes</i> .
Capacity	3 Points: Unlimited lengths of code There's no limitation for the length of <i>mechanisms</i> or algorithms using <i>procedures</i> .
Resource utilisation	1 Point: Multi-Core/Multi-Thread The MM-AR Platform uses NodeJS as a technology stack. NodeJS can run as a multi-core application using child-processes. Currently, the MM-AR Platform uses single-core for the servers. Since multiple servers are used for the MM-AR Platform, multi-core/multi-thread is satisfied.

Property/ Characteristic	Scale and Explanation
User error protection	<p>0 Points: No error protection</p> <p>Currently, the MM-AR Platform doesn't provide any user error protection. Only if the code for the mechanism or algorithm is written in an IDE bracket matching or error highlighting is provided. The error highlighting will not be of great value since the platform-specific variables and functions will be unknown to the IDE.</p>
Learnability	<p>1 Point: Very high effort</p> <p>The definition of a mechanism or algorithm is hard to learn since the definition can only be achieved through the definition of a JSON file. The code itself is JavaScript and therefore easy to learn, but platform-specific functions must be learned. Furthermore, there currently doesn't exist any help or guide for defining mechanisms or algorithms.</p>
Documentation	<p>0 Points: No documentation available</p> <p>Any documentation for implementing mechanisms and algorithms doesn't exist at the moment. In addition, no predefined functions are available. Therefore, the meta-modeler must have an in depth knowledge about the MM-AR Platform and programming in JavaScript.</p>
Reusability	<p>1 Point: Single-format reusability</p> <p>The implementation of mechanisms and algorithms allow the use of outside resources, e.g., with HTTP-Requests. The combination or re-utilisation of code isn't possible at the moment.</p>
Testability	<p>0 Points: Slow & hard</p> <p>The MM-AR Platform doesn't provide a way for testing mechanisms and algorithms separately. The only way for testing mechanisms and algorithms is executing them in the modeling toolkit.</p>
Installability	<p>4 Points: Four platforms supported</p> <p>The MM-AR Platform is a web-application. Therefore all operating systems (Windows, macOS, Linux) and technologies (x86, ARM) are supported.</p>
Usefulness (Pro-grammers)	<p>3 Points: Very satisfied</p> <p>The MM-AR Platform uses only code-based implementation of mechanisms and algorithms therefore is a technical person very satisfied with the approach chosen.</p>
Usefulness (non-technical people)	<p>0 Points: Not satisfied</p> <p>All mechanisms and algorithms are implemented with code. The meta-modeler must have an extensive knowledge about JavaScript.</p>

Property/ Characteristic	Scale and Explanation
Context completeness	<p>2 Points: Complete</p> <p>With the MM-AR Platform the meta-modeler and modeler can achieve most of their tasks within their context of use. However, the feature-set isn't quite as extensive as established platforms and applications.</p>
Flexibility	<p>2 Points: Average flexibility</p> <p>Use cases like AR and VR are possible with the MM-AR Platform. Other use cases might need additional capabilities of integrating outside resources and files within their mechanisms or algorithms.</p>

Table 6.4: Rating Matrix for the MM-AR Platform

Overall, the MM-AR Platform in its current state gathers fewer points than any of the established metamodeling platforms. The total points achieved for the MM-AR Platform is **19 Points**. Since the MM-AR Platform is only a prototype and will be further developed over the next few years, the gap to the established platforms is likely to shrink.

Chapter 7

Discussion of Results and Outlook

Over the last few years, the impact of models within academia and organizations throughout industries has grown (Chung et al., 2000; Pidd, 2008). Models without simulations don't unlock their full potential since not all information can be extracted (Barjis, 2011). As Sismondo (1999) recognized, one can't divide models and simulations into independent parts. Their respective interdependence leads to a forced, combined consideration. Therefore, the (meta-)modeling platform must support simulation capabilities for the available modeling methods.

Enterprise architecture is one of the key domains where modeling is applied. Besides knowledge representation, knowledge generation using simulations of the models is a widely used technique. Through simulations, organizations can gain insights into their business processes, systems, structure and real-world problems. Different solutions and configurations of systems can be evaluated without changing any parameters within the real world (Barton, 1998; Barjis, 2011).

Not only models and simulations provide us with promising use cases and opportunities. The advancements in AR and VR technology over the last few years enabled unknown applications in work practices throughout all industries. Improved decision-making by enhancing the quality of the decisions made through increased information processing is only one application in EA, which profits from AR and VR (Rehring et al., 2018). The research conducted on this field of application of AR and VR mostly limits themselves to interacting with existing models in AR and VR.

On the other hand, Muff and Fill (2021) found that models in AR and VR unlock their true potential if the activity of modeling can be embedded in the daily work. The role model for embedding technology in work practices can be found in the Microsoft Office Suite. AR and VR can be embedded in the daily workflow using real-world positioning systems, which correspond to coordinates in the 3D space of the augmented and virtual world (Muff and Fill, 2021). Since models and simulations can't be divided, modeling or representing models in AR and VR must enable simulations.

Muff and Fill (2021) developed a generic concept for conceptual modeling in AR and VR on the meta-meta level. Their meta-metamodeling framework for AR and VR forms the basis for their prototype, the MM-AR Platform. The MM-AR Platform allows the integration of conceptual models in everyday work activities by using AR and VR. The MM-AR Platform is still in its early phase of development and, therefore, doesn't yet support the full feature set of a metamodeling platform. One of the missing features was the capability of integrating model transformations. In order to close this gap and provide the means for integrating mechanisms and algorithms into the MM-AR Platform, a DSR project was conducted.

In this thesis, the author showed that mechanisms and algorithms could be integrated into the existing meta-meta model for AR and VR. Furthermore, the demonstration of a concrete implementation into the existing MM-AR Platform showed that the generic concept is applicable to a specific technology stack of an MM-AR based platform. The implementation of mechanisms and algorithms leads to no functional degradation, and a meta-modeler can now define his own mechanisms, scene_type specific algorithms, and independent algorithms. This enhanced capability enables (meta-)modelers to use domain-specific modeling methods with automated processing, transformations, or other additional abilities within their daily activities.

The MM-AR Platform now has the capability of incorporating use cases like simulating a business process, which is modeled in BPMN 2.0. The business process model can be represented in AR or VR using an HMD. The simulation, however, has only an effect on the static elements of the model and doesn't provide a dynamic representation.

Another use case could be the representation of a system using a Petri Net. The meta-modeler can now define a complete modeling method, according to Karagiannis and Kühn (2002). Therefore, not only the representation of the system is enabled, but also the discrete simulation of the Petri Net's states. It's up to the meta-modeler to design and develop the suiting mechanism or algorithm for a discrete event simulation with Petri Nets.

The focus of this work was on the development of a generic concept for implementing mechanisms and algorithms into an MM-AR-based platform. Overall, this goal has been achieved. The generic concept was developed in Section 5.3 based on the best practices and state-of-the-art approaches of open-source and commercially available metamodeling platforms. Furthermore, the appropriateness of the approach chosen by the generic concept could be demonstrated by implementing it directly into the existing MM-AR Platform. Afterward, the generic concept and the concrete implementation were evaluated using the previously defined design objectives, requirements, and rating matrix.

The current implementation of the generic concept for implementing mechanisms and algorithms on an MM-AR-based platform lacks key features, which allow a meta-modeler an easy implementation of mechanisms and algorithms. Therefore, further steps are necessary to close the gap. First, functions that can access model data must be defined and provided to the meta-modeler. Currently, only mechanisms and algorithms without accessing any model data can be defined. Second, the impact on the platform's performance must be assessed in more detail. The analysis might lead to the realization that the execution of mechanisms and/or algorithms should be outsourced to another component of the MM-AR Platform. Third, the documentation for the integration of mechanisms and algorithms is non-existent. Before integrating the artifact of this thesis onto the production server of the MM-AR Platform, extensive documentation on mechanisms and algorithms should be provided.

Besides the obvious work needed for closing the capability gap that is left with the current implementation, other opportunities now present themselves that build upon the concept of mechanisms and algorithms. First, the scope and quality of the definition of a mechanism or algorithm are very dependent on the meta-modeler's knowledge of JavaScript and TypeScript. The integration of a low-code or no-code mechanism/algorithm definition should be considered. Such a

low-code/no-code definition-client could be integrated into a new back end client. An in-depth analysis is strongly advised to further improve usability and user satisfaction.

Second, the current concept and implementation of integrating mechanisms and algorithms only impact the static components of the MM-AR Platform and its meta-meta model. However, the impact of mechanisms and algorithms on dynamic components or behavior of the MM-AR Platform has not been considered. More research on the dynamic behavior of mechanisms and algorithms within the MM-AR meta-meta model and platform is a very interesting topic.

This section concludes the conducted DSR project. The artifact itself, its use, relevance, and importance have been demonstrated. The research which has been conducted by Muff and Fill (2021) and other students at the University of Fribourg could be supplemented by this work. The goal of embedding modeling into normal working activities as an unconscious task seems closer than ever before.

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Appendix A

Complete Meta-Meta Model

The complete meta-meta model of the MM-AR platform with the additional concepts of mechanisms and algorithms is available on the GitLab of the University of Fribourg. The meta-meta model is available as a Bee-up (ADOxx based) format (.abl) and as a vector graphics (.svg). The subset, that was used as graphics in this thesis, as well as the full meta-meta model is provided.

GitLab Repository: diuf-gitlab.unifr.ch/buehlmma/mmar-thesis

Appendix B

Source Code

The source code of the concrete implementation is available the GitLab of the University of Fri-bourg. The following link will provide the full prototype with the basis of the existing MM-AR Platform and the additional functionality of this thesis.

GitLab Repository: diuf-gitlab.unifr.ch/buehlmma/mmar-thesis

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ERKLÄRUNG

Ich bestätige mit meiner Unterschrift, dass ich die Arbeit persönlich erstellt und dabei nur die aufgeführten Quellen und Hilfsmittel verwendet sowie wörtliche Zitate und Paraphrasen als solche gekennzeichnet habe.

Es ist mir bekannt, dass andernfalls die Fakultät gemäss der Entscheidung des Fakultätsrats vom 09.11.2004 das Recht hat, den auf Grund dieser Arbeit verliehenen Titel zu entziehen.

Ich erkläre hiermit weiterhin, dass diese Arbeit bzw. Teile daraus noch nicht in dieser Form an anderer Stelle als Prüfungsleistung eingereicht worden sind, gemäss der Entscheidung des Fakultätsrats vom 18.11.2013.

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